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**A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS ON ECOLOGICAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT
WITHIN BRGY. ALICIA, QUEZON CITY AMIDST COVID-19 PANDEMIC**

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14 October 2023

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Acceptance Page

This special problem titled **“A Qualitative Analysis on Ecological Solid Waste Management Within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Cherry Winsom Faller Holgado

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ABSTRACT

COVID – 19 pandemic has altered the lives of the people across the globe. Due to lockdowns and social distancing, the delivery of basic urban services was disrupted, including the disposal of solid wastes. As such, this research is conducted to: (1) Conduct comparative analysis on the solid wastes generated before and during the COVID-19 pandemic within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City; (2) Identify the good practices being implemented at the barangay level; (3) Assess the possible gaps of the policies at the barangay/local level related to proper solid waste management in response to the COVID-19 pandemic; and (4) Formulate the recommendations for the effective waste management in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City.

The data gathered through interviews, fieldwork, and observations were analyzed and this study has found that an effective and efficient solid waste management is not only centered on technological advancements but also institutional, economic, environmental, and socio-cultural linkages to allow the whole system to work. Further, acknowledging the informal economy is a significant step towards the formation of a localized solid waste management policy in which the concerned stakeholders are highly participating. This interaction will create a purposeful dialogue among them to catalyze inclusive solid waste management and improve the lives and livelihoods of those that are involved during the post-COVID period. Lastly, issues in relation to waste management is linked to the people's way of living that evolves through time and the continuous search for a better life. Solving waste management problems do not only cover environmental concerns but also economical, social, and behavioral concerns.

Keywords: social distancing, solid waste management, COVID-19, gaps, good practices, dialogue, stakeholders.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Solid waste management is an underrated public health service that is being paid attention to by the community due to the rise of COVID-19 pandemic. When the solid waste management challenge evolved into a public health emergency, then its real importance as an essential service becomes more evident (Nzeadibe and Ejike-Alieji, 2020).

According to UN Habitat (2020), the world has already been facing issues in the waste management sector, where over “two billion people lack access to waste collection whereas over three billion people lack access to waste disposal.” Hence, the existence of the COVID-19 pandemic along with the needed social distancing measures aggravates the condition of the sectors affected.

This COVID-19 pandemic led to the practice of new normal such as implementation of distancing measures which resulted to panic buying of resources including food, face masks, gloves, toilet papers, cleaning products, etc. (Sarkodie and Owusu, 2020). This panic buying ultimately increased the disposal of various biodegradables and non-biodegradables leading to tons of wastes generated. Moreover, the use of protective equipment such as masks to avoid the COVID-19 virus have surmounted the attempts to address the plastic pollution.

While governments enacted stay at home orders and varying degrees of state emergencies, there was continued generation of waste from our homebases (Plastic Smart Cities, 2020). In this regard, proper waste management within the period of COVID-19 pandemic warrants the safety of waste service workers and sustainability

of waste services. Thus, there is a need for adjustments of recycling services to include the safety measures which contain the spread during the collection, disposal and treatment of the medical wastes (ISWA, 2020).

The International Solid Waste Association (ISWA) has stated the three (3) major objectives in order to properly manage the generated wastes during the pandemic. These are the following: (1) the biomedical wastes should be disposed and processed properly so that it does not generate secondary infections; (2) communities should be well-aware of the safe recycling activities in order to avoid infection and contamination; and (3) sustainable waste management should be maintained such that the health of the waste workers should not be compromised by safeguarding that they have the proper safety equipment.

At the national level, the rates of waste generation have been produced based on the generated data on waste analysis and characterization studies (WACS) which was presented in EMB regional reports and local 10-Year Solid Waste Management Plans. According to the National Solid Waste Management Status Report (2015), it stated that “the yearly amount of waste in the country is expected to rise from 13.48 million tons last 2010 to 14.66 million tons in 2014 to 16.63 million tons in 2020. On the other hand, Metro Manila’s waste generation continues to surge as it contributes 22.2%, 24.5% and 26.7% to the country’s solid waste in the years 2010, 2014 and 2020, respectively.”

At the local level, especially on the urban areas of the country such as the Quezon City, the Task Force on Solid Waste Management (TFSWM) delivers sanitation services for the entire city including consistent waste management operations at known sources, such as for instance, households and institutions.

Statement of the Problem

The following research questions were addressed by the researcher through the conduct of this study:

1. What are the different types of wastes generated before and during the COVID-19 pandemic within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City?
2. What are the good practices relative to solid waste management that is being implemented during the pandemic period within Brgy Alicia, Quezon City?
3. What are the gaps in the solid waste management policies being locally implemented in addressing the COVID-19 pandemic?
4. What might be recommended to address the identified policy gaps and other issues related to solid waste management during COVID-19 pandemic within the barangay?

Research Objectives

This study aims to evaluate the ecological solid waste management in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City during COVID-19 pandemic through qualitative analysis. Specifically, it aims to:

1. Conduct comparative analysis on the solid wastes generated before and during the COVID-19 pandemic within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City;
2. Identify the good practices of solid waste management that is being implemented at the barangay level during COVID-19 pandemic;
3. Assess the possible gaps of the solid waste management policies at the barangay/local level to address the COVID-19 pandemic; and

4. Formulate recommendations for the effective waste management in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City.

Conceptual Framework

This research paper adopted the Integrated Sustainable Waste Management (ISWM) Model which permits the studies of intricate multidimensional perspective into a more integral way. This was crafted by the WASTE advisers and partners which focuses on the urban environment and development while working on developing countries during the period of mid-1980s. This was further enhanced by the Collaborative Working Group on solid waste management during the 1990s (Anschütz et al., 2004).

This model recognizes the significance of the three (3) dimensions when improving a waste management system. These dimensions are the following: (1) aspects on the movement of materials from the generation phase up to the final disposal; (2) perspective through which the whole system of the solid waste management is being examined; and (3) relevant stakeholders (Müller et al., 2002; Müller and Scheinberg, 2002; Zurbrügg et al., 2005; Zuilen, 2006; ISSOWAMA Consortium, 2009; Wilson et al., 2009; Scheinberg et al., 2010, 2011).

Figure 1. The integrated sustainable waste management model from WASTE, 2004.

It is also significant to highlight the synergy in the interrelationships among economy, environment, and society. An ecological solid waste management system (ESWMS) emphasizes that various waste characterizations alter the environment differently, considering the population and other societal influences. Likewise, these population within the communities can generate additional income, promoting public participation while abiding to the set laws and rules and diverting wastes from landing to their final disposal. As such, the cooperation done by the waste generators is a proof of social recognition and attitudinal shift towards proper solid waste management, resulting to waste reduction and increased waste recovery and segregation.

Significance of the Study

Looking at the small scale specifically within the local barangay level, the researcher used qualitative methods (i.e. semi-structured interviews with the key informants) in order to analyze the effects of COVID-19 on the generation, recycling, and disposal of solid wastes within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City.

The study also aims to characterize the different wastes generated before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Data and information generated will be subjected under comparative and thematic analysis in order to provide corresponding recommendations. This will also serve as reference for the main audiences and stakeholders such as the local governments, private service providers, academes, NGOs, and others who are directly or indirectly affected in the localized solid waste management within the developing countries.

Scope of the Study

This study concentrated on management of the solid wastes generated within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City amidst COVID-19 pandemic. Waste characterization and comparative analysis were also conducted before and during the said pandemic in order to address the policy gaps and its implementation at the barangay level, and to promote good practices to address the human-health, socio-economic, and environmental impacts of solid wastes. Lastly, recommendations are provided by the researcher to promote ecological solid waste management within the identified area.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Solid Waste Management in Urban Cities

The world is getting more and more urbanized each day and the rate of increase in urbanization is already at a disturbing degree. This likewise contribute to the increase in hazardous waste generation causing several health problems and environmental deterioration which greatly affects the community living below the poverty line and those marginalized population without equal access to public health and sanitary services in the city. They are extremely susceptible to disease outbreaks and epidemics.

The increase in solid waste generation is an impending effect of prevalent economic production and consumption which are influenced by the rate of urbanization and the income of the people living in the area. It shows that there is a direct relationship between the (1) level of income of an individual and economic prosperity of the country and the (2) rate of waste generation per capita. As such, the wastes generated is an indicator of how the people's lifestyles alter as an outcome of the economic development.

Moreover, the degree of urbanization reflects the distribution of waste generation within the various regions. For instance, the higher standard of living in cities generates higher waste outputs compared to suburban and rural areas. In the Philippines, its urban areas produce almost $\frac{1}{4}$ of the country's total waste generation. This is shown by the data collected last 2000 resulting to an average of 0.3 kg/person/day and 0.5 kg/person/day for rural and urban areas, respectively (San Juan, November 2019).

Legal Bases in Promoting Ecological Solid Waste Management

Several interventions are being implemented by the Philippine government in order to protect the human health and the environment against the hazards caused by negligent waste disposal. An emphasis was put on the proper collection and disposal of wastes as well as the imposition of fines and penalties for non-compliance even in the earlier regulations.

The Section 16, Article II of the Philippine Constitution states that “the State shall protect and advance the right of the people to a balanced and healthful ecology in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature”. Moreover, it further stipulates under Section 15, Article II that the “State shall protect and promote the right to health of the people and in still health consciousness among them”. These provisions gave rise to the crafting of Republic Act (RA) No. 9003, otherwise known as *Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000* and was approved on January 26, 2001. Furthermore, Section 10 of RA No. 9003 stated that in accordance with the relevant provisions of RA No. 7160, otherwise known as the *Local Government Code of the Philippines*, the functions on solid waste management is already devolved at the LGU level. Thus, they shall spearhead the implementation and enforcement of the provisions of the Act in their respective jurisdictions. Both Presidential Decree (PD) No. 856 or the Code of Sanitation and PD 1152 or the Philippine Environmental Code mandate the locals to provide efficient system from the collection up to the waste disposal. However, there is a need to improve the behavior at the ground level where the program on solid waste is being implemented to ensure its effectivity (San Juan, 2019).

In terms of compliance with RA No. 9003, Quezon City was the first city in Metro Manila to have its own 10 – Year Solid Waste Management Plan approved by the National Solid Waste Management Commission. The thrust of the plan is waste

reduction/diversion through recycling and composting activities in the barangay (local community) level. Waste reduction and diversion will be focused on the residential areas because they contribute the bulk of the solid waste generated by the City. The City shall require all barangays or cluster of barangays to set up their own Eco-Centers/MRFs. Waste Management Committees shall also be activated in every barangay. The Committee may form Cooperatives for the program to be self-sustaining. Incentives and awards program shall also be part of the approaches to encourage stakeholders, particularly the barangays, to implement waste segregation and waste reduction strategies. This plan is now in the process of being updated to include a long term and sustainable solution to the growing waste generation by considering modern technologies that are both environmentally – friendly and socially acceptable.

The City has also been recognized as the first local government unit to implement a successful and effective package clean up system on garbage collection and disposal. In a Package Clean Up System, the private sector is given full responsibility to administer and directly carry-out the management of solid wastes from various sources and the total environmental upkeep of the assigned service area. This system has made the city's garbage collection consistently more than 99% efficient through the years. Waste segregation at source has been the core strategy in all our waste reduction initiatives. Incentives and awards are given to the local communities, schools and the private sector for actively participating in the City's solid waste management program. To show moral ascendancy, even the City Hall officials and employees strictly follow the waste management policies enforced by the City.

The City Government is also very active in promoting environmental protection and management through various social marketing and advocacy projects that

encourage our constituents to be advocates and stewards of the environment. IEC campaign activities range from the implementation and/or participation in special events to the actual conduct of trainings and seminars, and production of various information materials.

The informal waste sector also plays a big role in the city’s waste reduction efforts. The integration of junk traders/junkshops to the formal waste management system has been the overarching goal in the enactment of City Ordinance No. SP-1711, S-2006, or “An Ordinance Regulating the Operation of Junkshops in Quezon City.” Various projects and capacity-building activities have been implemented since then not only to protect the environment, but also to improve the well-being of the members of this sector who are mostly indigent and lacking in livelihood opportunity.

Hereunder are the following solid waste management ordinances that are being locally implemented:

Table 1

City-Level Legislation Governing MSW Management from Integrated Solid Waste Management Plan Quezon City, 2016

Ordinance No.	Title
SP-2235, S-2013	An Ordinance Imposing an Annual Garbage Fee on All Domestic Households and Providing Penalty for Non-Compliance Thereof
SP-2202, S-2013	An Ordinance Prohibiting the Use of Polyethylene (Plastic) Advertisement and Propaganda Materials Within the Territorial Jurisdiction of Quezon City
SP-2140, S-2012	An Ordinance Regulating the Use of Plastic Bags and Establishing an Environmental Fee for Its Use, Providing Mechanism for Its Recovery and Recycling and Providing Penalties for Violation Thereof
SP-2127, S-2012	An Ordinance Prohibiting the Use of Plastic and Styrofoam in Quezon City

Ordinance No.	Title
	Hall Complex, Novaliches District Center, Quezon City General Hospital and Novaliches District Hospital for Efficient Garbage Disposal and to Reduce Risk to Health and Well-Being
SP-2122, S-2011	An Ordinance Prohibiting the Open Burning of Garbage, Trash or Any Other Refuse Materials Within the Territorial Jurisdiction of Quezon City and For Other Purposes
SP-1711, S-2006	An Ordinance Regulating the Operation of Junkshops in Quezon City and Imposing Penalty for Violation Thereof and For Other Purposes
SP-1707, S-2006	An Ordinance Requiring the Segregation at the Source of All Household, Institutional, Industrial, and Commercial Waste and/or Garbage into Wet or Biodegradable and Dry or Non-Biodegradable, Pursuant to Republic Act No. 9003
SP-1512, S-2005	An Ordinance Creating the Quezon City Solid Waste Management Board
SP-1630, S-2005	An Ordinance Amending Section 4 of Ordinance No. SP-1501, S-2005 "Requiring Subdivision Developers and/or Subdivision Owners in Quezon City to Provide Sufficient Space for the Installation of Compositing Facilities to Accommodate the Disposal of Recyclable or Biodegradable Waste", Authorizing the Environmental Protection and Waste Management Department (EPWMD) in Coordination with the Subdivision Unit to Undertake the Implementation and Enforcement of this Ordinance
SP-1530, S-2005	An Ordinance Mandating Residents, Owners and Operators of Institutions to Clean Their Own Surroundings Including Canals, Streets or Roads in Their Immediate Premises to Make Quezon City a Cleaner and Healthier Place to Live In, and Providing Penalties for Violation Thereof
SP-1506, S-2005	An Ordinance Amending Ordinance No. 6305, S-65, Prohibiting the Throwing of Any Kind of Garbage, Waste Matters, or Refuse in Any Drainage Outlets such as

Ordinance No.	Title
	Rivers, Creeks, or Any Tributaries in Quezon City
SP-1501, S-2005	An Ordinance Requiring Subdivision Developers and/or Subdivision Owners in Quezon City to Provide Space for the Installation of Composting Facilities to Accommodate the Disposal of Recyclables or Biodegradable Waste Generated by Homeowners and Providing for Penalties and Administrative Sanctions in Violation Thereof
SP-1483, S-2005	An Ordinance Requiring All Residents and Business Establishments in Quezon City to Segregate Spent Fluorescent Bulbs from Common Garbage as to Eliminate Exposure from Mercury, Declaring the Same as Hazardous Waste and Directing the Environmental Protection and Waste Management Department (EPWMD) to Prepare Implementing Rules and Regulations Regarding the Disposal of the Same
SP-1323, S-2003	An Ordinance Adopting Guidelines and Procedures for a Unified Approach on Solid Waste Management
SP-1203, S-2002	An Ordinance Granting Incentives to Barangays Practicing Best Solid Waste Management
SP-1191, S-2002	An Ordinance Providing Incentives to All Barangays Utilizing Their Own Trucks for Solid Waste Collection Service in Their Respective Barangays
SP-1072, S-2001	An Ordinance Mandating All Drivers of Public Utility Vehicles Plying the Streets of Quezon City to Provide a Receptacle Conspicuously Inside Their Respective Vehicles for the Proper Disposal of Trash/Rubbish of their Passengers and Providing Penalties for Violation Thereof
SP-941, S-2000	An Ordinance Regulating the Operation of Ambulant/Push Cart Junk Dealers and Providing Penalties for Violation Therefore
SP-856, S-2000	An Ordinance Amending the Penal Provisions of All Ordinances Relating to Waste and Garbage Collection and Disposal and Littering such as, but not Limited to Ordinance No. NC-106, S-89;

Ordinance No.	Title
	Ordinance No. NC-118, S-89; Ordinance No. NC-172, S-90; Ordinance No. SP-111, S-93, Prescribing a Uniform and Graduated Penalties Therefore, and Deputizing the Elected Barangay Officials to Help in the Implementation Thereof
SP-813, S-99	An Ordinance Imposing a City Garbage Collection Service Charge on All Persons Engaged in All Forms of Business Activities/Calling or Undertaking
SP-111, S-93	An Ordinance Requiring All Industrial and Commercial Establishments to Put Adequate, Sufficient and Covered Trash Receptacles and Its Implements and Accessories Within the Vicinity of Their Establishments and Providing Penalty and/or Fine for Violation Thereof
NC-172, S-90	Prohibiting Urinating, Defecating, and Indiscriminate Disposal of Waste, Trash and Any Form of Garbage in Public Places, Except in Any Designated, Allowable Areas or Places of Quezon City and Providing Penalties for Violation Thereof
9820, S-73	Regulating Solid Waste Disposal Practices, Including the Prohibition of Open Dumping in Vacant Lots, in Esteros and In Other Water Courses
6305, S-65	Prohibiting the Throwing of Any Kind of Garbage, Waste Matters, Or Refuse in Any Drainage Outlets Such as Canals, Rivers, Creeks, or Any Tributaries in Quezon City, and Providing Penalties for Violation Thereof

Challenges in Solid Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic

The solid wastes that are being produced daily have to be well-managed especially in an urban system. This is considered a fundamental practice that is implemented by the local authorities in order to sustain the cleanliness and hygienic environment within the residential areas. Their role is very significant to reduce the negative impacts of the natural disasters such as earthquakes, floods, pandemic, etc.

since the wastes aggregation contributes to the increase in multiple risks associated with the pervasiveness of pathogens caused by improper disposal of wastes. As such, sweepers and healthcare staff who are directly exposed to wastes may become infected, which in turn can also affect the sanitation of the area.

The abrupt increase in pneumonia cases was detected in Wuhan City, China in December 2019 and was reported to the World Health Organization (WHO) China Headquarter at the end of the said month. After a few months, WHO declared COVID-19 as a pandemic last 11 March 2020. This has greatly impacted the various sectors which resulted to restriction in movement and transportation, limited contact with other people, and worsened economic downturn. The respiratory droplets from an infected individual is considered the primary source of transmission but secondary source also includes indirect contact where the metallic surface is being touched by an infected person which transmits the virus. As a result, the type and amount of wastes generated drastically changed during the pandemic period. A huge portion of the wastes are made up of food packaging, masks, personal protective equipment (PPE), hand sanitizers and alcohol containers, and other plastic wastes since these have form part of our daily lives. These have added to the voluminous loads which are transported and processed in the waste treatment systems.

One of the causes in the increment in waste generation is the implementation of lockdown and work-from-home setup by most communities in order to avoid the spread of COVID-19. Also, higher food consumption at home and increased online shopping have greatly contributed to household wastes. Further, because of the surge in positive cases compared to the existing medical facilities, those patients that are considered asymptomatic (showing moderate symptoms) are recommended to do home quarantine. Their wastes should be disposed attentively to avoid the

transmission of disease among the family members and even waste collectors. Poor handling of infectious solid wastes may be an underlying contributor to the spread of disease that may also derail the regular operations of waste collection and processing.

Currently, the demand for single-use plastics has reached a very alarming rate where the act of recycling is not recommended because of the viral retention. Each person is required to wear a facemask in order to address the aerial spread of the disease which has added to the amount of wastes being produced. Moreover, the cafe and restaurants are not allowing their customers to use reusable containers. Instead, they provide the single-use plastic packaging materials to minimize the viral transmission.

Improper disposal of plastic-based waste materials also contributes to marine pollution. These contaminants may impact the natural habitat of the sea creatures and negatively affect them. In addition, the virus that can be found in the mask's surface may be transmitted through the bodies of water and infect those in contact with it. In fact, ten (10) million masks have been dispersed in the surroundings in just a month, according to the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) in Italy.

The figure below shows the Solid Waste exposure pathway according to the Cost Sharing Framework for SWM, 2010.

Figure 2. Solid waste exposure pathway from cost sharing framework for SWM, 2010.

As previously discussed, the commercial, residential, industrial, and institutional sources make up the municipal solid wastes generated. Other sources not falling on the aforesaid categories are street sweepings, illegal dumpings, open spaces, road litters and rubbish, and those coming from the water bodies. Thus, families who live near the dumpsite vicinities are greatly exposed to various diseases. This is aggravated by the presence of leachate and methane gases coming from the solid wastes which have been disposed and left in dumpsites for quite some time. These may contaminate the nearby groundwater and surface waters. Likewise, insects and pests will serve as disease vectors. As a result, this will have repercussions on the health of the exposed population, cause environmental pollution, clog the waterways and increase the flooding incidents, affect aesthetics, and contribute to the global warming.

The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Waste Sector

Hereunder are some of the pandemic's impact on the waste sector:

1. Health and safety of solid waste management workers. Lockdown greatly affected the livelihood of the informal workers which heavily relies on the solid waste management sector. This provides emphasis on the vulnerable condition of which they work under even prior to pandemic.
2. Reapportionment of the waste generation. There is a shift in the number of wastes generated from the commercial establishments and industries to residential communities, such as the following:
 - 2.1. There is an increase by 40% in the volume of the medical wastes produced;
 - 2.2. There is a drastic decrease in the commercial and industrial wastes production due to the decline in manufacturing activity;
 - 2.3. The existing hazardous waste treatment in developing countries is likely to be overloaded with the increased waste production coming from the medical sector, such as hospitals and pharmaceuticals. This may result to stockpiling and inadequate areas designated for disposal; and
 - 2.4. The resurgence in the use of single-use plastics such as food packaging materials and limited recycling activities contributed to the increase in the number of municipal wastes generated. This has resulted to:
 - 2.4.1. Various municipalities found it financially and physically challenging to cope;
 - 2.4.2. There are substantial impacts on municipal revenues which also strained municipal budgets due to high costs of healthcare and social protection;

2.4.3. There have been disruptions due to the containment measures being implemented, resulting in job deficit and fiscal deterioration across all sectors; and

2.4.4. Increased competition for public funds which will be allotted to address COVID-19, such as procurement of PPEs that will strain the budget which should be utilized in other solid waste management initiatives.

3. Alteration in waste treatment-related activities. There has been changes in the government focus in terms of solid waste management – from waste diversion and recycling into collection and transportation of wastes acquired from population centers:

3.1. Other key factors identified such as disruptions in supply chain and decrease in commercial enterprises aside from the anticipated risks of COVID-19 contributed in the reduction of recycling activities. This may cause the upturn of raw material independency instead of recycled materials; and

3.2. There is an increase in disposed wastes that are being thrown at landfills which are made up of more recyclable materials that are being received at the municipal waste channels. Most of the collected wastes are accumulated in temporary dumpsites.

4. The small and medium enterprises are being pressured since most of the waste collection and transport companies belong to this sector. According to the World Bank Group (2020), most of these SMEs are unable to sustain the provision of essential services caused by the huge costs derived from hourly labor and fuel, resulting to discontinued payment.

Solid Waste Management During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Solid waste management needs to be given prior consideration where the local government units shall continuously review and evaluate the existing data in order to come up with short - and long - term solutions to efficiently address the issues. The environmental experts perceived that there is no simple solution to the waste problem because of the existing economic and physical discrepancies among various communities. However, it is also being emphasized that in terms of gender roles, women are considered to be the major players in household waste management; thus, they can greatly contribute to the waste segregation practices within their respective families, and eventually within the community.

The abovestated role of women is an example of community participation as a process where the influence of the stakeholders share control over identification of priorities which may affect the access to public goods and services, policy making, and allocation of resources. It has been stressed in numerous cases that self-help and community participation may contribute to address the waste collection problems, especially in low-income areas. The crafting of an implementation project should incorporate the enhancement of community awareness and willingness to participate in its key aspects.

In this regard, ISWA proposed the following priorities that will contribute to proper waste management implementation during the COVID-19 pandemic:

1. Countries, states/provinces and cities should ensure that waste management, recycling services, treatment and disposal facilities will not be disrupted and no extra risks for public health will be created by improper waste management. Waste management workers, especially those in waste collection, should take additional precautions and ensure health and safety

procedures to be protected from any potential infection by the waste streams and/or the equipment.

2. Recycling activities should be re-adjusted to avoid cross-contamination and infections.

3. The increased quantities of healthcare and medical waste should be safely treated and disposed of, making sure that they pose no risk for further infections and pollution.

Priority I: Sustainability of the provision of waste management services

One of the most significant ways to address the health-related issues and spread of disease is the implementation of the proper waste management. It should be emphasized that this also covers the hazardous and healthcare wastes, in addition to the municipal wastes being generated by the communities. The practices which promote lesser wastes being thrown to dumpsites such as recycling and waste diversion should be implemented after the COVID-19 crisis passed.

In light of the above, the recognition of the responsibilities being carried out by the waste workers plays a vital role especially during pandemic. In order to avoid the accumulation of wastes and to maintain the areas free from vector of diseases, the waste collection should be done regularly. As such, the local authorities must come up their respective contingency plans to ensure that the primary wastes services will not be affected so that no additional health hazards will occur in addition to the COVID-19 crisis. This should include proposed recommendations pertaining to the available workforces, automobiles, disinfection, and other related services.

Priority II: Modification of the recycling activities

It is not considered precarious when each of the households will conduct their own recycling activities at home. The origin of cross-contamination is the transition between the generator and handler – the person who is producing their own wastes outward into the public system, and those individuals who address the issues on residual wastes, respectively.

In line with this, all factors are considered to ensure the safety of the recycling activities which will be carried out, such as: (1) recycling systems; (2) formal wastes; and (3) various processes including the machines, centers, and practices within the low-income communities. The government institutions and/or private entities have direct and indirect control on the aforesaid processes. This can be through the regulations being implemented and influence of the concerned agencies.

Priority III: Establish the secured processing of healthcare wastes

It is the utmost responsibility of all the national and local authorities to assure the maximum protection within their respective jurisdiction by amplifying their plans to implement the sustainable waste management. Extra effort is needed in case there is an increased amount of wastes that exceed the existing capacity in place. Some of these examples are the following: (1) Disseminate IEC materials for the communities to thoroughly understand that handwashing with antibacterial soap and water for more than twenty (20) seconds is far more effective than the use of alcohol. Those in leadership positions should also act as a role model to promote this practice against the spread of diseases.

The wastes that are transported off-site should be tracked, registered, and treated accordingly to ensure that these will not cause health hazards upon arrival at the intended destination. The persons designated to handle healthcare wastes should

be equipped with PPEs and wash hands after removing it. However, many developing countries still need more infrastructures to treat these wastes. In order to temporarily address this, wastes produced during pandemic are being stored in sanitary landfills located in an isolated area and away from the regular wastes generated.

Sanitary landfills, in the absence of thermal treatment, shall serve as final sink for the increased amount of healthcare wastes produced. Hence, these are considered to be crucial part of the waste management system especially during the pandemic period, since these landfills will accommodate wastes for safer disposal (International Solid Waste Association, 2020).

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

This research used a descriptive-qualitative method which includes semi-structured interviews among the barangay officials and other identified stakeholders within Barangay Alicia, Quezon City.

Field observations during the collection and conveyance of solid wastes were also conducted. The study went through three (3) phases as follows:

1. The researcher gathered and studied the related literatures;
2. The researcher gathered primary data through semi-structured interviews, field work and observations; and
3. The researcher analyzed the data and information gathered through comparative and thematic analysis in order to obtain the conclusion and recommendations of this study.

Respondents

The stakeholders determined in this research through purposive sampling are considered to be the key informants of the researcher in gathering the primary data. The researcher has chosen this sampling technique due to limiting circumstances of the ongoing pandemic; thus, the participants that are directly affected were the ones consulted:

1. Concerned Brgy. Official/s on the Committee on Environment and Health of Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City: Mr. “Alvin” and Kagawad Enriquez were interviewed regarding the existing policies and activities pertaining to solid

waste management, waste management options before and during COVID-19 pandemic, challenges and good practices in solid waste management, and their proposed recommendations to address the said issues/challenges.

Figure 3. Field visit at the barangay hall for the conduct of interview with Kag. Enriquez.

2. Respondents from the household communities: Two (2) respondents, Ms. “Amy” and Ms. Elvie Razo were interviewed regarding their awareness on the existing solid waste management policies and activities which are being implemented within the barangay, waste management options at the household level before and during COVID-19 pandemic, challenges encountered and good practices being implemented at the household level, and their proposed recommendations to address the challenges they experienced at the household level.

Figure 4. Interview with Ms. “Amy” (left) and Ms. Elvie Razo (right).

3. Waste/Garbage collector: Mr. Enrique Boco under National Solid Waste Task Force was interviewed regarding his awareness on the existing policies and activities pertaining to solid waste management, waste management options in terms of waste transportation before and during pandemic, challenges and his proposed recommendations as waste collector who has direct experiences of the issues related to solid waste management.

Figure 5. Field observation and interview with Mr. Enrique Boco.

4. Small business enterprise owners: Ms. Allodia Enriquez and Ms. Raquel Moreno, both small enterprise owners, were interviewed regarding their awareness on the existing solid waste management policies and activities, waste management options before and during pandemic as sari-sari store owners, challenges and good practices in promoting proper solid waste management, and proposed recommendations to address such issues.

Figure 6. Interview with Ms. Allodia Enriquez (left) and Ms. Raquel Moreno (right).

Research Instruments

Primary and Secondary Data Collection

The researcher conducted online desk reviews on documents that served as sources of secondary data, majority of which are related literatures prior to and during the occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, as previously mentioned, semi-structured interviews with the abovestated key informants were also conducted. The interview schedule consisting of five (5) parts contained questions on the following aspects:

Demographic profile of the informants

1. Waste management options and the existing policies being implemented
 - a. Source separation
 - b. Waste storage
 - c. Waste transport
2. Challenges encountered in solid waste management before and during COVID-19 pandemic
 1. Human health
 2. Socio-economic
 3. Environment
3. Good practices in promoting proper solid waste management during COVID-19 pandemic
4. Proposed Recommendations to address the identified issues/challenges

Data Analysis

The secondary references and materials acquired during the visit at the barangay hall provided the data on waste generation and characterization in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City. In addition, their office consolidated the documentation regarding their good practices and corresponding solid waste management – related policies and/or ordinances being implemented within the said barangay.

In support to this, the results gathered from the conducted semi-structured interviews were fully transcribed by the researcher from which the relevant data and information were studied and assigned into preliminary codes to describe the corresponding content. The identified thematic patterns were analyzed and reviewed and formed part of the research findings.

Thematic analysis was used in order to allow flexibility in determining the meaning of the data through the assigned “themes”. In this study, the researcher was able to identify nine (9) codes to which the responses were mainly categorized into: (1) Waste Management; (2) Implementation; (3) Collection; (4) Types of Wastes; (5) Political Intervention; (6) Majority of Land Use/Landscape Structure; (7) Challenges; (8) Social Responsibility; and (9) Recommendations.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

History and Profile of Barangay Alicia, Quezon City

The barangay was established on 09 January 1961 through the Ordinance No. 61-4621. The geographic location and description are the following:

1. Territorial Boundaries: Culiat River (North), Samar and Ilocos Sur Sr. (East), Antique and Camarines St. (West), Ilocos Norte St. (South)
2. Total land area: 9.7746 hectares
3. Road Network: 12 (number of streets); 6 (number of puroks); Cemented and Asphalted (type of roads), 1 (number of bridge)

Depressed areas are located in the interior portion of Cotabato/Tacloban St. with more or less 150 families. Hereunder are the maps showing the geographic areas within the barangay:

Figure 7. Barangay Alicia streetscape problem map from Brgy. Alicia, 1961.

Figure 8. Barangay Alicia streetscape problem map from Brgy. Alicia, 1961.

Table 2

Population Projection by Barangay for 10 Years (2005-2014) from Quezon City 10 Year – SWM Plan, 2005-2014

Year	Population
2005	6,602
2006	6,729
2007	6,858
2008	6,989
2009	7,124
2010	7,261
2011	7,400
2012	7,542
2013	7,687
2014	7,835

Table 3

Total Population per Barangay from Quezon City 10 Year – SWM Plan, 2005-2014

City/Barangay	Total Population	Household Population	No. of Households
Quezon City	2,173,831	2,158,367	480,624
Alicia	6,003	5,997	1,273

The tables above show the total population per barangay and the population projection of Brgy. Alicia for ten (10) years, from 2005 to 2014 with the computed annual rate of increase of 1.9% as seen below:

Table 4

Rate of Annual Population Growth based on Population Projection

Year	Population Projection	Rate of Annual Population Growth
2005	6602	1.9
2006	6729	1.9
2007	6858	1.9
2008	6989	1.9
2009	7124	1.9
2010	7261	1.9
2011	7400	1.9
2012	7542	1.9
2013	7687	1.9
2014	7835	-

The projected increase in the population is 0.69% higher than the average annual growth rate of 1.21%, according to the Philippine Statistics Authority, 2015. This means that the higher the rate of increase in population, the higher the amount of wastes generated in the identified area.

Waste Generation and Characterization Before and During COVID-19 Pandemic

The Systems Dynamics Model was used to assess the movement of solid waste material and as such, four (4) final destinations will be considered: unmanaged wastes, waste diversion, informal sectors' collection, and waste disposal practices (Tinio et al, 2019). The practice of segregation is assumed to be undertaken by the households to manage their generated wastes based on the composition: residuals, compostables, recyclables, and special wastes. If the local barangay unit failed to properly manage their solid wastes, the City government is relayed with the task to

collect and properly dispose all generated wastes. The special wastes such as the infectious medical wastes need special handling while the rest are being processed in the whole waste management system. The remaining materials after the city waste collection can either end up as additional unmanaged wastes as litters or managed when these waste generators carry out their duties in terms of proper solid waste management through recycling, waste diversion, and other waste interventions. Moreover, the efficiency of the collection and participation by the public largely affects the whole management system.

The data provided by the barangay LGU with regard to the compliance to the waste segregation at source for the year 2019 is shown below:

Figure 9. Barangay waste segregation at source compliance from Brgy. Alicia, 2019.

Name of Street	Total No. of Households	No. of Non-Compliant Households	Remarks
ILOCOS SUR	26	11	
SAMAR	36	-	
PANGASINAN	162	27	
ILOCOS NORTE	294	169	
FORT SANTIAGO	120	32	
TAAL	10	1	
ANTIQUE	62	11	
BATANGAS	42	14	
DAVAO	175	118	
COTABATO	311	20	
BALAYAN	57	20	

The total number of households is 1245 which were collected with wastes and 403 of these were considered non-compliant, resulting to only 63% compliance to their local ordinance and barangay Solid Waste Management Plan regarding the implementation of segregation at source.

The researcher was also provided by the barangay LGU with the Environmental Compliance Audit (ECA) Reports from 2017-2021. Hereunder is the summary of the said reports:

Figure 10. Processed data from household compliance to segregation at source from Brgy. Alicia, 2017-2021.

Table 5

Generated Environmental Compliance Audit from Brgy. Alicia, 2017-2021

Environmental Compliance Audit								
Year	Total number of households	Total number of compliant households	Types of wastes generated				Waste generated per quarter	Waste diverted
			Recyclables (kg)	Compost biodegradables	Residuals	Others		
2017	3853	3756	-	-	-	-	-	-
2018	2041	1567	20,980	-	-	-	520088.135	4.03
2019	1533	1130	27,130	-	-	-	792881.1775	3.42
2020	1533	1256	15,649	-	-	-	644385.8098	2.428
2021	1533	1256	15649	-	-	-	644385.8098	2.428

Based on the data provided above, there is 97% from the total number of households that are compliant to the segregation at source last 2017, 76.77% compliance for 2018, 73.71% for 2019, 81.93% for 2020 and 2021. The highest and

lowest amounts of recyclables (in kg) generated were 27,130 in 2019 and 15,649 in 2020 up to the 1st quarter of 2021, respectively. In terms of waste generation and diversion, the highest and lowest amounts of wastes generated were 792881.1775 for 2019 and 520088.135 for 2018, whereas for the waste diversion, the highest average diversion rate quarterly was during 2018 with the rate of 4.03 and the lowest diversion rate of wastes generated was during 2020 to 1st quarter of 2021 with the rate of 2.428.

On the table above, no data was provided for the other types of wastes because the barangay LGU is only documenting those that are recyclables. Other types of wastes generated were reflected in the thematic analysis of the responses gathered from the semi-structured interviews conducted.

Pertinent Laws and Policies Governing the Solid Waste Management Within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City

Salient Features and Status of Implementation of RA 9003: Ecological Solid Waste Management Act

The hierarchy of practices is being shown as an inverted triangle in terms of solid waste management implementation. Based on the model shown below, the waste avoidance and reduction are two of the most opted practices for the scaling down of the amount of wastes that is entering the waste system. In addition, this goal can also be achieved through manufacturing durable products that are feasible for reuse and recycling, reduction in the use of raw materials for production and declined amount in consumption. Further, all these practices require behavioral change as the lifestyle exigencies usually support convenience over preservation and conservation of resources with the slightest regard for the welfare of the environment and its long-term consequences.

Figure 11. Overall policy of RA 9003 based on waste management hierarchy.

The LGUs are considered to be the primary unit responsible for the implementation of the Ecological Solid Waste Management Law, specifically Section 10 of the said Act. They must create the city/municipal and provincial Solid Waste Management Boards and shall draft a 10-Year Solid Waste Management Plan that will be implemented in the community. Moreover, the LGUs are mandated to divert 25% of the wastes generated within five (5) years after the effectivity of the law through reuse, recycling, and composting activities. Section 20 of the said law further stipulates that there should be an increase in the target percentage of waste reduction every three (3) years. This can be done through segregation at source and creation of MRF in every barangay or cluster of barangays, according to Section 21 and 32, respectively. In line with this, the private sectors, communities, and other stakeholders play vital role for the implementation of the Act.

DENR Administrative Order (DAO) No. 2001-34 or the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act 9003

1. Section 6, Rule VI: Creation of a Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee

The establishment of the Barangay Solid Waste Management Committees is included in the strategy of the Quezon City LGU. They are tasked to manage the solid wastes, in coordination with the Environmental Protection and Waste Management Department (EPWMD). Hence, the said board shall have the following duties and responsibilities:

1. Create a management program for solid wastes in accordance with the city or municipality plan;
2. Practice segregation prior to the collection of all types of wastes, such as compostables, biodegradables, and reusables wastes. The Resolution No. 60 was approved by NSWMC in 2013 which aims to provide various measures for the conduct of the mandated solid waste segregation at source, segregated collection up to the recovery stage in order to aid the waste generators on the onsite separation as well as to express support to the LGUs in implementing their solid waste - related campaigns;
3. The law requires the establishment of the materials recovery facility for every barangay or cluster of barangays. This shall be modified to serve as receiver, storage, and processor for the recyclable materials effectively and efficiently. Other residual wastes shall be collected and transferred to other disposal facilities;
4. Allocate barangay funds;

5. Organize core coordinators; and
6. Submit monthly report to city or municipality.

2. Section 7, Rule VI: Membership of the Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee

The Barangay Solid Waste Management Board shall be composed of the barangay captain with the following as members:

1. One (1) kagawad
2. Sangguniang Kabataan chairperson
3. Home Owners Association Head/President
4. Private/public school head/principal/representative
5. One (1) Parent and Teachers Association (PTA) president/representative
6. One (1) religious organization representative
7. One (1) transportation community representative
8. One (1) environmental non-governmental organization representative
9. One (1) representative from junkshop owner's association or the Head of Market Vendors Association

On the collection and transfer, the barangay should ensure the following:

1. Provision of waste containers located in the identified collection points for temporary storage while waiting for collection;
2. Household segregation of wastes for the purpose of composting, recycling, and reuse;
3. Availability of transport vehicles for the regular hauling of wastes from the collection points up to the final disposal; and

4. Issuance and effective implementation of the local ordinances for an efficient collection system in the barangay.

3. Section 1, Rule IX: Operations of a Materials Recovery Facility

Barangays shall be liable for the following waste-related activities: recycling, collection, and segregation at source. Since it is mandated to establish MRFs, it is also the responsible of LGUs to allocate a small land area which will be determined through its Sanggunian.

4. Section 5, Rule XV: Establishment of Local Solid Waste Management Fund

Barangay councils may issue resolutions to establish the local ordinances for the establishment of a Local Solid Waste Management Fund, pursuant to the relevant provisions of RA 7160. This will be sourced from the collected fines, donations, endowments, grants, sub-contracting fees, 20% Development fund for waste management.

Memorandum Circular No. 2020-147 dated 29 October 2020: Guidelines on the Management of COVID-19 Related Health Care Wastes

The main objective of the Circular is to provide extensive guidance on the duties and responsibilities for the LGUs regarding the safety management of all COVID -19 – related waste products. All cities and municipalities are directed to comply and to harmonize the efforts of the barangays within their respective jurisdiction. The salient features of the policy are the following:

1. The proper way to segregate the wastes at source at the household and community level must be strictly enforced in all cities and municipalities in order to ensure that COVID-19 – related wastes are separated from other types of wastes.
2. The barangays shall provide households with adequately labeled storage bags or bins where the same can temporarily store their COVID-19 – related wastes.
3. Personnel directly engaged with the whole waste management process from the point of collection up to the disposal of COVID-19 – related wastes must be provided with and ensure the use of PPEs.
4. Empower the Barangay Ecological Solid Waste Management Committees (BESWMC) to support the strategies and measures of the city/municipality on proper management of COVID-19 – related wastes.
5. Barangays, through BESWMC, shall prepare compliance plans to the measures of COVID-19 Waste Management Plan which shall be incorporated as addendum to 10-Year Solid Waste Management Plan.
6. A portion of fund shall be allocated or realigned to adequately support the proper implementation of their COVID-19 Waste Management Plan.

Barangay Resolution No. 062, s. 2014: A Resolution Creating the Barangay Alicia Solid Waste Management Committee, Its Functions and Responsibilities and Executive Order No. 03-A, s. 2020: An Order Organizing/Reorganizing the Barangay Alicia Ecological Solid Waste Management Committee (BESWMC), Its Functions and Responsibilities

The functions of the members of the created Solid Waste Management Committee include the following:

1. Formulation of the Barangay Solid Waste Management Plan consistent with the City's SWMP;
2. Organize Core Coordinators;
3. Conduct of Information and Education Campaign;
4. Allocation of barangay funds or look for alternative resources of funds;
5. Submit monthly report to the City's Solid Waste Management Committee;
and
6. Conduct of regular meetings.

Environmental Governance Towards Locally Sustainable Waste Management

Environmental governance is the process which incorporates the various fundamentals of solid waste management such as managers, different organizations, the communities, and the required mechanisms for the operation of a sustainable solid waste management, especially among the developing areas (Atienza, 2008).

Among the indicators of a good governance are accountability, transparency, and participation by the concerned stakeholders and their contribution in addressing the problems. The quality of an effective solid waste management are replicability,

effectivity, and sustainability. The rate of participation of the stakeholders involved greatly affects the progress of the implemented solid waste management programs. Hereunder is the illustration showing the flow of the environmental governance towards sound solid waste management (Atienza, 2009).

Figure 12. Environmental governance towards sound SWM from Atienza, 2009.

Fig. 5. Environmental Governance Towards Sound Solid Waste Management

Figure 13. Institutional arrangements mandated by ESWMA by Atienza, 2011.

Institutional Arrangements Mandated by the ESWMA

Good Solid Waste Management Practices Implemented in Brgy. Alicia Before and During COVID-19 Pandemic

1. *Solid Waste Management Plan Implementation*

The Barangay Solid Waste Management Plan shall apply to all types of establishments including the commercial and residential houses, industrial establishments, various institutions such as churches, schools, hospitals, and both public and/or private markets established and operated within the barangay.

Hereunder are seven (7) phases of this plan:

1. Establishment of Barangay Solid Waste Management Core Group: the BSWM Board shall assign personnel which will form the core group and responsible for the monitoring and reporting of the project. It is also their duty to conduct a regular meeting to update information on the project.
2. Waste Characterization: a study used to determine the volume of daily waste generated and its composition.
3. Information and Education Campaign: this shall be composed of house-to-house campaign, public address system, and meetings and public forum.
4. Segregation at Source: every household, institution, and commercial establishments must segregate at source provided that there is an allotted storage for each type emanating from various sources with proper marks/labels as *nabubulok* and *di-nabubulok*.
5. Dedicated Collection: effective implementation of “No segregation, No Collection” ordinance.
6. Establishment of Materials Recovery System: assign and designate an eco-aide to collect the recyclables within the barangay through the established

MRFs and creation of a Memorandum of Agreement with the junkshop for the efficient collection of the recyclables.

7. Implementation: the city, in coordination with EPWMD, contracted trucks which collect solid wastes per schedule of waste collection.

2. *Sinop Basura sa Barangay*

A Community-Based Solid Waste Management Program aims to reduce the volume of solid wastes from source by waste segregation and the implementation of separate collection or the “No Segregation, No Collection” scheme.

3. *Collection and Transfer at the Barangay Level*

Macro-micro Cell Route Collection Scheme is the system of waste collection dividing the city into districts and the districts by barangays, further subdividing the barangays into cells where one (1) cell route is equivalent to one (1) unit collection vehicle.

Barangay Base Solid Waste Management Collection Operations. The barangay is subdivided into cell or route and by identified main roads.

Issues, Challenges, and Policy Gaps Pertaining to Solid Waste Management in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City

Based on the conducted semi-structured interviews among the respondents and review of the related literature, hereunder are the identified issues on solid waste management:

1. Expensive cost of delivering the solid waste management services;

2. Limited incentive to reduce waste at the household level. A provision of the incentive is needed in order to encourage the people to minimize their generated wastes. On the other hand, placing charges/sanctions on improper waste disposal will serve as a reminder for the local communities regarding their responsibility to make the whole solid waste management system work;
3. Lack of manpower to address technical concerns;
4. Lack of personnel having permanent position in the barangay who shall handle the solid waste management concerns;
5. Land scarcity for the mandated establishment of the MRFs;
6. Inadequate activities such as promotion on waste recycling. Effective promotion and collection services are very important since people will be encouraged to separate their wastes if they are informed that an entity will utilize the waste materials and that the schedule for collection is reliable and consistent;
7. Lack of social accountability among the members of the community. All the people play vital role in waste reduction in their respective communities. It is considered imperative that they are well-informed, educated, supported, and motivated to maximize their participation; and
8. Uncertainty or absence of markets for compost products.

Several elements can be considered as causes for the failure of the effective implementation of solid waste management - related policies. The objectives of the said policies aim to achieve an improved health and a clean environment, however, these failed to gain the cooperation and full attention of the community and other

stakeholders because the laws were focusing more on providing sanctions to express control and command within their jurisdictions.

In terms of RA 9003, hereunder are the identified policy gaps according to Vella Atienza (2011) subject to further study:

1. Lack of support for the LGUs: The law requires the LGUs to comply with the responsibility of managing the generated solid wastes within their respective areas but provides little support for their effective compliance.
2. Financial constraints: The national government does not allocate and provide for the adequate funds to finance the cost of activities to be undertaken by the LGUs as required by the law. The fees for the provision of solid waste management services that are being collected by the LGUs are not sufficient, especially for the lower-class municipalities. As such, the DENR set various categories of SLF through the issued DAO No. 2006-10. Said categories are based on the net residual wastes that are being produced by the municipalities which pertain to the difference between the amount of wastes generated and diverted or recovered through different methods such as composting and recycling. This also accounts for the estimated increases in waste generation within the 10-year period. However, finding the suitable sites for the construction of landfill is considered challenging due to issues related to social acceptability and not-in-my-backyard (NIMBY) syndrome. The public is still wary of the possible environmental and health problems that may be caused by leachates which contaminate the bodies of water, despite the efforts of the NSWMC and DENR to issue guidelines for the safe and secured landfill establishment and operation.

3. Setting idealistic deadlines: The amount of time required by the law is insufficient in order to close all the open dumpsites. It was clearly stated under the law that there should be no dumpsites after five (5) years upon the effectivity of the Act. Therefore, there should be no single dumpsites operating at the present time. Realistically, the set deadline is challenging to achieve because there are lot of considerations pertaining to financial, health, environmental, and technical aspects for the safe and proper termination of open dumpsites and sanitary landfills construction.

Behavioral Change for the Better Waste Management

One of the primary cultural aspect that influences the people's way of life is the person's behavior. An intensive and creative social marketing is needed to conduct a study on the community's behavior and to be able to introduce and incorporate new ones. This can be undertaken by studying the demographic trends and cultural patterns within the community through actual engagements and trainings.

A 2022 study conducted by the Resources, Environment and Economics Center for Studies, Inc.'s (REECS) on household waste management systems and its linkages to the human behavior indicated that:

1. The responsibility of undertaking the proper waste management is still viewed as the sole accountability of the government;
2. There is an insufficient public participation in terms of segregation at source towards sustainable waste management;
3. Raising awareness through the conduct of IEC and training activities and stricter law enforcement and local ordinances are needed to achieve ecological solid waste management; and

4. Empowerment within the community and political will are needed to resolve the waste management - related issues.

The people's behavior and perspective towards solid waste will change if they will be able to recognize and appreciate the significance of the environment and the effects of improper waste management to health and safety. While it is important to follow what the law requires, the community should gear towards sustainable solutions and fully understand why composting, recycling, segregation, and other related activities must be carried out. Moreover, there should be a long-term and intensive social marketing program to be implemented within the small unit of the local government.

In the case of Brgy. Alicia, imposing sanctions and conducting IEC are inadequate based on the issues and gaps which were gathered during the interviews. It is also significant to provide the communities with positive reinforcement to comply with the rules and regulations such as provision of incentives depending on how they are practicing the proper solid waste management. For the concern on funding, this is very crucial that the LGUs, in coordination with other relevant stakeholders, should be able to determine income-generating activities that will sustain the solid waste management -related programs being implemented. It is also worth emphasizing that raising the awareness among the household communities is insufficient; they should be able to realize the consequences if proper solid waste management practices will not be carried out. Thus, social accountability should be strongly put in place.

Thematic Analysis on the Responses Gathered during the Semi-Structured Interviews

After the conduct of the review of the literature, the researcher proceeded with the fieldwork and semi-structured interviews among the identified respondents. The gathered data and information during the interview were processed using thematic analysis to allow flexibility in interpretation and approach through assigning broader codes which covers the main points of the discussion. Hereunder is the table of summary containing their respective responses according to “themes”:

Table 6

Thematic Analysis on the Responses Gathered during the Semi-Structured Interviews

Assigned Codes	Small Enterprise Owners	Household Members	Garbage Collector	Barangay Official
Waste management	Waste segregation Biodegradable and non-biodegradable Waste separation Composting Recycling	Waste segregation Composting	Waste segregation	Waste segregation
Implementation	Strict Scheduled collection		Efficient waste collection No downtime	Ensure on – time waste collection Submission of report (ECA) to EPWMD for environmental certificate of the barangay
Collection	Before pandemic: Monday Wednesday Friday During pandemic: Everyday Truck Person-in-charge	Before pandemic: Monday Wednesday (non-biodegradables) Friday During pandemic: Everyday	Before pandemic: Monday Wednesday (non-biodegradables) Friday 6:00 am - 10:00 or 11:00 am During pandemic: Everyday, except Sunday	Before pandemic: Monday Wednesday (non-biodegradables) Friday During pandemic: Everyday Wastes should not be left along the streets if the

Assigned Codes	Small Enterprise Owners	Household Members	Garbage Collector	Barangay Official
			No holidays	trucks have not arrived yet
			Garbage should already be out on the street by the time the truck arrives	
			Waste segregation is barely done	
Type of Wastes	Masks PET bottles Vegetable peelings Leftover food Plastics (cellophane, plastic bags) Papers and <i>kartons</i>	Food wastes Bottles Boxes Leftover food Plastics Empty gallons		Household wastes Commercial wastes Bulky wastes Concrete debris from construction site
Political Intervention	Barangay Captain City hall Assistance	Lack of IEC for households Provision of streetsweepers Lack of coordination with the households Lack of penalty/ies implemented for the violators	Everyday garbage collection per directive of Mayor Joy Belmonte House-house visit for IEC materials	Conduct of IEC Campaign such as distribution of flyers and solid waste management advocacy Continuous river clean-up activities at least once a month Implementation of TUPAD Project of DOLE for displaced workers with submitted accomplishment reports DENR directive for small restaurants to put up grease trap Hiring of 6 street sweepers
Majority of Land Use/Landscape Structure	Majority of which are residential lands compared		Narrow streets where the trucks cannot pass through	Majority of which are residential lands compared

Assigned Codes	Small Enterprise Owners	Household Members	Garbage Collector	Barangay Official
	to commercial areas.			to commercial areas.
Challenges	Segregation	Limited awareness on the programs	Health hazards among the garbage collectors	No space for establishment of MRF, only MRS because of the small land area. Lack of cooperation from the community
	No provision of container	<i>Ningas Cogon</i> Mentality (lack of consistency on implementing	No insurance provided	Lack of discipline among the community members
	No initiative from all the households	solid waste management efforts)	Limited access to some areas affected by COVID-19 lockdown	Implementation of segregation at source
	No compost area	Lack of discipline among the community members	After the waste collection, these are transported to Montalban, Rizal where all the wastes are no longer segregated	Implementation of "no plastic" policy
	Urbanized area		Some of the uncollected wastes are being thrown to the nearby river	"Pakikisama" mentality rather than strict implementation of rules and regulations
				Restriction on the solid waste management activities carried out during pandemic (no seminars and meetings conducted)
				Lack on the number of dump trucks deployed (only 1 provided)
				Presence of informal settlers near the river (along Tacloban St. exit)
				Perception that there will be no segregation in the landfill

Assigned Codes	Small Enterprise Owners	Household Members	Garbage Collector	Barangay Official
				Conflict on political jurisdiction of the creek between Brgy. Alicia, Brgy. Sto. Cristo, and Ramon Magsaysay
Social Responsibility	Helping the community Providing recyclable waste materials for free	Providing recyclable waste materials for free		Lack of "police power" to relocate the informal settlers Some individuals are allowed to sell recyclable materials to earn money before pandemic
Recommendations	Provision of trucks that crushes the wastes Project livelihood program Educating the community and the young ones Segregation Role model River clean-up	Segregation Recycling Proper waste disposal Educating the young ones Maintaining the cleanliness in and outside of the house	Salary increase and provision of benefits to waste collectors and driver	Additional garbage trucks for collection Continuation of stakeholders' meeting every 3 rd month of the quarter with RTD junkshop, apartments, and townhouse owners Request for additional waste containers from EPWMD Conduct of clean up drive every 15 th of every month Need for stricter implementation (issuance of Notice of Violation instead of a warning)

All of the respondents identified waste segregation as the major waste management technique implemented in Brgy. Alicia. Both the small group enterprise

owners and the household members mentioned about “composting” of their leftover food and other types of biodegradable wastes.

In terms of implementation, the small enterprise owners, garbage collectors, and brgy. official stated that there is a strict implementation of efficient and on-time waste collection. As for the local government, they are required to submit a report or the Environmental Compliance Audit to EPWMD prior to the granting of the barangay environmental certificate.

The responses in terms of waste collection have also been consistent. It was stated that prior to pandemic, the schedule was Monday-Wednesday-Friday where non-biodegradables are usually collected during Wednesday. But since the start of the pandemic, the waste collection has already been scheduled everyday, from 6:00 am to 10 or 11:00 am. The garbage collector stated that there is no holiday break for them because the waste generation is continuous, hence, there must be a daily schedule for garbage collection in order to avoid waste accumulation in the streets. The barangay official also stated that wastes should not be left on the road if the truck has not arrived yet in order to maintain cleanliness and orderliness in the streets.

For the types of wastes being generated, the small enterprise owners and household members mentioned about biodegradable and non-biodegradable wastes such as masks, vegetable peelings, food wastes, etc. However, the barangay officials mentioned about the overall types of wastes being generated by the community: household wastes, commercial wastes, bulky wastes, as well as the concrete debris from the construction sites.

Since the barangay officials and waste collectors hired by the LGU are included in the study, political intervention theme was also identified by the researcher. For the small enterprise group, they mentioned that there is an assistance provided by the

local government, however, for the household members, they stated that there is lacking IEC among the households regarding proper solid waste management, there is also an inadequate coordination on the part of barangay LGU, and less stringent penalties being implemented for the violators. The garbage collector mentioned that the new schedule for the waste collection was a directive coming from Mayor Joy Belmonte, head of the Quezon City LGU. The barangay officials provided a list of some of the activities being locally implemented such as the conduct of IEC, continuous river clean-up, implementation of TUPAD project, hiring of street sweepers, etc.

The researcher also included the theme on land use/landscape structure because this also affects the effective solid waste management within the barangay. For small enterprise owners and barangay official, they have mentioned majority of the land use is residential areas unlike Brgy. Sto. Cristo which has a lot of commercial establishments. The garbage collectors also mentioned that there are some narrow streets which impede the efficient collection of wastes. In support to this, because of the small land area, the barangay official also mentioned about the insufficient space for the establishment of MRF, only MRS or a small cage where the non-biodegradables are being stored before being delivered to nearby junkshop for additional income.

In terms of the challenges raised by the respondents, the common problems mentioned are the effective implementation of segregation at source, lack of self-discipline, cooperation, and initiatives among the community members. Most issues faced with regards to informal settlers residing in the nearby river are relative to the lack of “police power” of the barangay officials to identify sites and to implement their relocation. In addition, the activities that were being carried out such as the conduct of seminars, IECs, clean-up drive were put on hold because of the pandemic situation.

The solid waste management within the barangay also created the social responsibility and bond for the community members. For the small enterprise group and household members, they stated that they are willing to help the community such that they provide recyclable waste materials to those who are poor and needy for free. For the barangay official, they stated that prior to the pandemic, they were allowing some individuals to sell recyclable materials and earn money for themselves.

Lastly, the respondents provided valuable inputs for their respective recommendations which include the provision of the livelihood programs, conduct of IEC, strict implementation of segregation at source, conduct of river clean-up, proper waste disposal, and stricter implementation of laws and policies with regard to proper solid waste management.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Solid waste management is considered to be a multifaceted concern that was exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. In general, localities seek for the appropriate ways to address such pressing issue. This research showed that various factors play vital role in order to achieve an effective waste management system such as socio-cultural, environmental, institutional, legal, and technological aspects for the whole waste strategy to work.

Waste collectors are not the only ones who must be liable in promoting proper waste management but also the community members who need to be vigilant about the environmental and health safety. Thus, the directive based on laws and policies to minimize waste generation at source should be followed.

The laws and policies that are being implemented are the important elements in terms of governance aspect in dealing with issues related to solid wastes generated. According to Ocenar (2011), policies are needed for the strategic planning and operation of the solid waste management programs. The policy gaps can affect the efficiency of the waste collection and disposal. Likewise, the weak compliance to these regulations proves that no “best policy” can be enforced without considering the aforestated factors to make the whole system function.

Another concern that must be taken into account is the insufficient social acceptability which may cause the lack of comprehensive and localized solid waste management policy that involves the informal waste sectors and acknowledges their roles and responsibilities. This is a significant step towards crafting of a localized solid

waste management policy where the primary stakeholders are taking part. This type of commitment will eventually create a relevant discourse on COVID-19 waste-related issues and to aid in livelihood recovery of those communities affected during the post-COVID period.

In addition to the informal settlers, there are also other primary and secondary stakeholders from various fields of interest who play a role in shaping the whole community. A thorough understanding of who these stakeholders are and their responsibilities will aid in establishing a functioning waste management system. As such, the communication transfer among these stakeholders is considered relevant, especially in developing countries.

Moreover, the conduct of IEC and awareness campaigns in order to help the people grasp what these regulations are and what this aim to achieve is important for them to realize the weight of this environmental issue. Hence, the issues on solid waste management do not only include the wastes per se, but focus more on the lavish lifestyle of the people which develops over time and the endless search for a better life.

Recommendations

In order to address the pressing solid waste management situation during COVID-19 pandemic, local government and communities have to ensure that the optimal waste management services will be delivered in order to avoid the possible risks to public health and safety as well as the pollution associated with waste accumulation.

Proposed Policy Actions to Enhance the Solid Waste Management Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic

An appropriate and timely barangay resolutions towards effective implementation of solid waste programs should be passed, taking into consideration the following:

1. Integration of sustainable consumption into local policies where the use of products and services shall have minimized environmental effects to sustain the needs within the carrying capacity;
2. Active involvement of the informed stakeholders such as residents, small-scale business owners, and educational sector;
3. Improve public awareness and social accountability campaigns on sustainable consumption;
4. Shifting the social context by making the more sustainable choice the default option (continuous banning on the use of plastics within the community); and
5. Implementation of circular economy (CE) - based solutions, where the life cycle of the product is being extended. In this way, the product is being kept and used as long as possible in order to reduce the amount of wastes generated.

In general, three (3) major factors contribute to the successful solid waste management implementation. These include (1) Strong political leadership; (2) Coordination among various sectors and stakeholders in the community; and (3) Networking and partnerships with different agencies, entities, and organizations.

Figure 14. Critical waste management areas requiring attention with COVID-19 from UN Habitat SWM Response to COVID-19.

Critical waste management areas requiring attention with COVID-19

In relation to the illustration above, hereunder are some of the ways to properly manage the waste while protecting the community against COVID-19:

1. Separate the infectious wastes in the households. It is recommended to distribute the containers among the households, focusing on low income and informal settlements.
2. Waste reduction should be promoted through the 5Rs (rethink, refuse, reuse, reduce, and recycle).
3. Maintain and expand waste collection services. Close contact between people must be reduced during waste collection.
4. Practice composting at the household level within their respective backyards or using big pot containers.

5. Strict enforcement of RA 9003 and the economic benefits of practicing waste diversion, recycling, and segregation must be emphasized.
6. It is of utmost importance to strictly implement the “No segregation, no collection” policy to inculcate discipline among the households and communities.

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**ANNEX I: LETTER OF REQUEST ADDRESSED TO HON. ENRIQUE C. ENRIQUEZ,
COMMITTEE ON ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH, BRGY. ALICIA, QUEZON CITY**

14 April 2021

Hon. Enrique C. Enriquez
Committee on Environment and Health
Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City

Dear **Hon. Councilor Enriquez**,

I am Cherry Winsom F. Holgado, graduate student from the University of the Philippines Open University and residing at #81-D Cotabato St. Bago Bantay, Quezon City. As part of our course requirement, we are tasked to write a Special Problem (thesis) on the area of our interest. Being one of the residents here in Brgy. Alicia, I have chosen this barangay as the focal area of my study.

My research study focuses on the ecological solid waste management in Brgy. Alicia amidst COVID-19 pandemic. This aims to (1) conduct comparative analysis on the solid wastes generated before and after COVID-19 pandemic within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City; (2) identify the good practices being implemented as regards to solid waste management at the barangay level during COVID-19 pandemic; (3) assess the policies implemented at the barangay/local level related to proper solid waste management in response to the COVID-19 pandemic; and (4) formulate the recommendations for the ecological management of solid waste in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City.

In this regard, may I request to set an appointment with you to conduct the semi-structured interview on **23 April 2021** at your most convenient time. In addition, I would also like to request for the copies of the following documents: (1) types and volume of solid wastes generated before and during COVID-19 pandemic; (2) local policies being implemented in the community to ensure proper waste management; (3) disseminated information, education and communication (IEC) materials on proper solid waste management; and (4) other materials and references as regards to solid waste management in the barangay. Rest assured all data that will be gathered shall be treated with **utmost confidentiality** and shall only be used for the sole purpose of conducting this study.

With this, I am hoping for your kind consideration on this matter and I am looking forward to share the output of this research with your office.

Thank you.

Sincerely,

Cherry Winsom F. Holgado
UPOU MENRM Student
Brgy. Alicia Resident

ANNEX II: LETTER OF REQUEST ADDRESSED TO MR. RICHARD S. SANTUILE, ACTION OFFICER, QC TASKFORCE SOLID WASTE COLLECTION, CLEANING AND DISPOSAL SERVICES MANAGEMENT, QUEZON CITY HALL

14 April 2021

Mr. Richard S. Santuile

Action Officer
QC Task Force Solid Waste Collection
Cleaning and Disposal Services Management
Quezon City Hall

Dear **Mr. Santuile**,

I am Cherry Winsom F. Holgado, graduate student from the University of the Philippines Open University and residing at #81-D Cotabato St. Bago Bantay, Quezon City. As part of our course requirement, we are tasked to write a Special Problem (thesis) on the area of our interest. Being one of the residents here in Brgy. Alicia, I have chosen this barangay as the focal area of my study.

My research study focuses on the ecological solid waste management in Brgy. Alicia amidst COVID-19 pandemic. This aims to (1) conduct comparative analysis on the solid wastes generated before and after COVID-19 pandemic within Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City; (2) identify the good practices being implemented as regards to solid waste management at the barangay level during COVID-19 pandemic; (3) assess the policies implemented at the barangay/local level related to proper solid waste management in response to the COVID-19 pandemic; and (4) formulate the recommendations for the ecological management of solid waste in Brgy. Alicia, Quezon City.

In this regard, may I request for the copies of the following documents: (1) types and volume of solid wastes generated before and during COVID-19 pandemic within Brgy. Alicia; (2) local policies being implemented in the community to ensure proper waste management; (3) disseminated information, education and communication (IEC) materials on proper solid waste management; and (4) other materials and references as regards to solid waste management. Rest assured all data that will be gathered shall be treated with **utmost confidentiality** and shall only be used for the sole purpose of conducting this study.

With this, I am hoping for your kind consideration on this matter and I am looking forward to share the output of this research with your office.

Thank you.

Sincerely,

Cherry Winsom F. Holgado
UPOU MENRM Student
Brgy. Alicia Resident

ANNEX III: PROPOSED FLOW OF THE DISCUSSION/GUIDE QUESTIONS FOR THE SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS TO BE CONDUCTED AMONG THE IDENTIFIED KEY INFORMANTS

1. Interview with the Brgy. Official

- I. Demographic profile of the respondent
 - Name
 - Age
 - Address
 - Position/designation
- II. Existing policies and activities pertaining to solid waste management
- III. Waste management options before and during COVID-19 pandemic
 - Source separation
 - Waste characterization
 - Waste storage
 - Location of storage facilities
 - Waste transport
 - Vehicles used in transporting solid wastes
- IV. Challenges encountered in solid waste management before and during COVID-19 pandemic
 - Human health
 - Socio-economic
 - Environment
- V. Good practices in promoting proper solid waste management during COVID-19 pandemic
- VI. Proposed Recommendations to address the issues/challenges

2. Respondents from the Household Communities

- I. Demographic profile of the respondent
 - Name
 - Age
 - Address
- II. Awareness on the existing policies and activities pertaining to solid waste management
- III. Waste management options at the household level before and during COVID-19 pandemic
 - Source separation
 - Waste characterization
 - Waste storage
- IV. Challenges encountered at the household level in terms of solid waste management before and during COVID-19 pandemic
- V. Good practices in promoting proper solid waste management during COVID-19 pandemic
- VI. Proposed recommendations to address the issues/challenges

3. Waste/Garbage Collectors

- I. Demographic profile of the respondent
 - Name
 - Age
 - Address

- II. Awareness on the existing policies and activities pertaining to solid waste management
- III. Waste management options before and during COVID-19 pandemic
 - Waste transport
 - Frequency and vehicles used in transporting solid wastes
- IV. Challenges encountered in solid waste management before and during COVID-19 pandemic
- V. Proposed recommendations to address the issues/challenges

4. Small Business Enterprise Owners

- I. Demographic profile of the respondent
 - Name
 - Age
 - Address
- II. Awareness on the existing policies and activities pertaining to solid waste management
- III. Waste management options before and during COVID-19 pandemic
 - Source separation
 - Waste characterization
 - Waste storage
- IV. Challenges encountered in terms of solid waste management before and during COVID-19 pandemic
- V. Good practices in promoting proper solid waste management during COVID-19 pandemic
- VI. Proposed recommendations to address the issues/challenges

ANNEX IV: TRANSCRIPTIONS OF THE CONDUCTED INTERVIEWS AMONG THE IDENTIFIED KEY INFORMANTS

1. Ms. Allodia Enriquez (Small Enterprise Owner)

CHE: So ano po siya itong ginagawa kong study eh thesis ko po sa masters. Sa OU po ako nag mamasters ngayon. Eh since Covid naman, dito na po ako magcoconduct ng study kasi mahirap naman bibiyahe pa po tapos di ba? Mas risky po sa Covid. Ang mga respondents ko sa study, meron ditong for small business enterprise owner. Ano po siya made of six parts. Unang una yung demographic profile of respondents. Pwede ko po ba makuha name nila?

AE: Allodia Enriquez

CHE: Yung age po nila?

AE: 46

CHE: Anong Number po ng bahay ninyo?

AE: 82 Cotabato St.

CHE: Bale sa second part po ng interview, gusto ko po mameasure yung awareness ng respondents ko with regards to solid waste management sa barangay. Itatanong ko lang po kung meron po ba kayong alam na mga resolution o ordinance sa barangay na inimplement po sa atin?

AE: yung ano lang waste segregation mga bio, non-bio.

CHE: Pero naimplement naman po siya sa dito sa store?

AE: Dito? Ah no. Hindi naimplement pero Pag kinollect din kasi sabay-sabay. As far as I remember may time na talagang sobrang strict.

CHE: mga kailan po kaya iyon?

AE: Before Covid. Parang may days na kinocollect ang nabubulok tapos may days na hindi nabubulok parang wait lang. Loves, yung dati anong araw na kinokolekta yung basura na nabubulok?

Husband: Monday at Friday

AE: tapos Wednesday yung hindi nabubulok

CHE: Ah ito po ay nabubulok Monday and Friday

AE: OO Before covid iyan

CHE: Wednesday, Thursday ay sorry po

AE: Wednesday lang yung hindi nabubulok. Before Covid ito tapos nung nagcovid back to zero. During Covid naman, though ano na siya naging everyday. Diba dito sa atin, MWF na nagkukuha tapos ngayon parang nagiging mga two weeks na parang daily. Oo, halos daily na ang collection.

Che: Actually noong Monday daw po kasi galing akong brgy kahapon then ngayon naman yung mga bahay bahay nga po. Nabanggit nga po kahapon na last Monday nga po nagstart. So para po sa inyo mas maluwag sila. Although everyday, hindi sila strictly nagsesegregate. Meron pa po ba iba na policies, activities na iniimplement sa atin?

AE: in relation to waste management? So far yun lang. Yun lang kasi yun yung policy na talagang pinapatupad nila. Nag-iikot sila tapos nagpapaalala sila na magsegregate ng waste. Tapos meron talaga from the city hall na kasama ng truck. May isang person silang in-charge na nagmamake sure na o ito ba ay nabubulok ay di namin yan kukunin. Meron siyang sumasama parang nakaassign siya talaga for collection. Ngayon nga siguro dahil nga sa pandemic ay hindi na nagagawa.

CHE: Pero di po ba mas delikado yun kung di nasesegregate yung mga ganito mga mask kasi infectious waste iyan.

AE: Kaya nga ako rin sa amin halimbawa **itong mask kinucut namin yung garter para hindi na magamit ng iba** kasi siyempre kahit na ano parang pinupublicize nila na washable siya pero siyempre ang hirap pa din lalo na kung ang makukuha yung mga cannot buy na mag aano na lang magrecycle siyempre kawawa din sila at risky nga.

CHE: Part three na po tayo waste management option before and during covid. So una po nabanggit ninyo ang waste segregation. Dito po sa store ninyo paano ninyo hinihiwalay yung mga waste? per bottle ba? Plastic ganun?

AE: **Ayun yung mga PET bottles hinihiwalay namin siya tapos ang nagcocollect naman niyan binibigay ko sa nangangalakal.** Kasi may matanda dito na nag-iikot siya eh siyempre nakikita ko naman na mahirap mangalakal tapos dala niya kariton niya. So ito talaga sabi ko di naman ginagamit safekeep na diyan namin nilalagay yung karton, yung PET bottles

CHE: yung mga recyclables po?

AE: **Pagka basura naman ay dyan din, pupunta na diyan si Nanay.** Kasi sabi ko sa **kanya sasave ko talaga iyan sa iyo kaya pagka ano kunin mo na lang.** Eh may one time na taga diyan kinukuha niya yung mga lata, sabi ko ay hindi, kay nanay iyan. Sabi niya wala na si nanay. Sabi ko eh wag mong pakialaman iyan kasi kay nanay iyan kasi kayo naman po malakas naman kayo hayaan niyo na sa matanda iyan.

CHE: So dito po ay pet bottles and karton so yun po ay under ng recyclables ano. May iba pa po ba kayong pagcategorize ng waste?

AE: Yung mga ano kapagka naghihiwa may mga peelings

CHE: Ito po sa nabubulok ano?

AE: **Yung mga peelings ng mga gulay, yung mga food nilalagay din namin siya sa isang plastic.**

CHE: So separate po siya

AE: **Separate naman po siya tapos yung mga plastic hinihiwalay yung mga cellophane ay yung mga lalagyan ng ulam, mga plastic bag, ganoon.**

CHE: Sa mga nabubulok may iba pa po kayo na poproduce na ano?

AE: **Yun lang. Yung left over food. Pero minsan yung mga leftover food pinapakain na lang namin sa stray dogs ganun**

CHE: So sa recyclables po meron kayong plastics, plastic waste, pet bottles tsaka kartons. Mga papers po?

AE: Wala kasi kami masyadong paper eh yung paper naman ginagamit din namin siya. Kasi may aso kami so ginagamit ko naman nirerecycle ko lang siya pambalot ng mga waste din.

CHE: How about sa waste storage po ito po ay waste separation ano, waste segregation. Pagdating naman po sa waste storage, saan po kayo nag-iimbak? Dito ang mga kartons and pet bottles

AE: **Pero kasi nga regular naman ang collection, pinapadala namin siya sa ano truck.** Eto kasi si nanay pag kinuha na niya yan binebenta niya tapos yung mga kartons din. Actually yung mga karton namin.

CHE: So mga recyclables lang po tumatagal pag mga food waste sinasabay po siya sa truck.

CHE: Part four naman po ng interview na ito ay ang challenges when it comes to Solid Waste Management. Sa tingin niyo po, anong mga challenges encountered in terms of solid waste management before and during covid pandemic.

AE: **Siguro ang challenge lang kasi even kung gusto mo magsegregate mahirap talagang gawin.**

CHE: Before pandemic po ito?

AE: Ang hirap wala kasing container na pinoprovide. Sana may pinoprovide din yung barangay or yung meron din parang for community kung saan pwedeng ilagay ang basura kung walang collection pa. Kaso yun nga ang mahirap kasi siyempre ang hirap din halimbawa may iprovide na tatlong basket. Minsan hindi naman ikaw nagdadamot pero yung waste mo magugulat ka na lang nadadagdagan kasi halimbawa eto diba everyday kumukuha ng basura so empty ito ngayon. Bukas iyan puno na iyan. So magugulat ka hindi mo naman siya mapupuno kung isang household lang. Eh ang hirap din naman na sabihin mo na "Hoy basurahan namin iyan". Sana din may initiative din bawat household. That is our responsibility.

CHE: Ibig sabihin po ba, no accountability sa mga household?

AE: Kasi 'di ba halimbawa ikaw nagsesegregate pero iba di naman nagsesegregate. Kaya labo labo pa rin sila pagdating sa tao.

Che: How about during pandemic po?

AE: So during pandemic, sa tingin ko na-lessen yung challenge, kasi everyday na sila halos nangongolekta ng basura. Pero yun nga sana strict implementation pa rin ng waste segregation. Siyempre wala na tayong landfill pero kahit gusto natin din gumawa ng fertilizer at mag compost, wala?

CHE: May ganun din po bang activity ang barangay? Kasi sayang naman ang mga compostables

AE: Kasi wala din siyang compost area, 'di ba? Parang kasi talagang mag-uumpisa sa barangay pero dahil kasi napakaurbanized ng area, hindi din talaga though from the barangay naman, di naman din ano para idiscredit yung ginagawa. Meron din mga initiatives ang barangay. Pag may truck ng basura may nag-aassist lagi from the barangay. Minemake sure nila yung community naman ay clean. Nagagalit din si kapitan kapag nakita niya na basura day tapos hindi nakuha yung basura dito so naalarm din siya. So bukod din sa city hall na nag-aassist before, meron ding tanod na nag-aassist. To make sure na every bahay nakukuha ang basura.

Che: So challenge mas nalessen during pandemic kasi mas madalas ang collection. Siguro kulang lang ng strict implementation pagdating sa waste segregation tapos yung mga composting ng mga nabubulok di rin po nagagawa kasi siguro sa kulang po yung sa area. May dadagdag pa po kayo na challenges?

AE: Yung nakita ako lang magiging challenge pa rin sana siya kung di siya nagdadaily na pagkuha ng basura. Nasanay na din yung mga mga tao na kapag hindi siya yung usual day like Thursday tapos biglang dadating yung truck. Tulad kanina, may truck ng basurang dumaan.

CHE: Naalarma din yung tao kapag si ateng nagwawalis sa labas ay sumisigaw na nandyan na ang truck.

AE: Si Sally kasi ano siya ng barangay ng dating kapitan. Ano siya parang street sweeper siya. Pero ngayon kasi si kap kagawad na siya nagpalitan na pero nandyan pa rin si Kap Ding. Ngayon kapitan natin si Kap Koro. Pero sanay kasi yung mga tao kahit si Brgy Kap Koro ang nakaupo, tinatawag namin si Kap Ding kasi siya yung pinakamalapit kasi pag may mga problema kaming pambarangay, sa kanya talaga. Eh since number one kagawad din siya though di siya sa waste management but at least maganda din yung meron kang kakilala nafoforward mo yung concerns tapos nagagawan ng paraan. So buti na lang everyday na rin yung kahit wala siyang strict implementation for solid waste management, hindi naiistuck sa bahay o sa community na pwedeng magcause ng health problems or health concerns.

Che: May mga good practices po ba kayong iniimplement in terms of solid waste?

AE: Yun pa rin kasi everyday nagluluto si Olan yung peelings nasa isang plastic bag yun ako din automatic practice ko din yung empty bottle ng mga toyo diyan talaga nilalagay sa iisang lagayan. Ano yun parang hitting two birds with one stone. You help community, you help din yung mga tao na nangangailangan iyan. Iniisip namin ibebenta pa ba natin eh kailangan naman. Tayo naman ididisperse naman iyan. Ba't mo pa pagkakakitaan eh makakatulong naman.

Che: So waste segregation. May gusto pa po kayo idagdag sa mga plano sa future na halimbawa pag natapos na ang pandemic?

AE: Gusto ko lang magmungkahi lang ng mga aksyon na siyempre wala namang akong capacity to do.

Che; Dito na po siguro tayo sa recommendation ano, para kahit hindi po sa household. Ano po recommendation niyo to promote ecological solid waste management sa barangay natin?

AE: Ako talaga ang dream ko para sa barangay, gusto ko magkaroon din tayo ng alam mo yung truck ng basura na nagccrush na siya talaga ng wastes. Kasi ano lang siya ang nakita ko na may ganyan Marikina, Cogeo, parang mga Rizal Area.

Che: Habang nagcocollect ay nagccrush ng basura, di po ba?

AE: Parang nainggit ako, sabi ko may ganon naman palang truck sana may ilang trucks na ganyan din dito sa barangay. Sa totoo lang, ang dami din kasing mga residente na walang ginagawa. Sana din kahit na parang masyado nang busy yung place dahil maraming commercial areas, sana meron pa din yung mga nanay na walang work diba yung parang they can also help doon sa recycling. Parang isang project livelihood program di ba? Eh dito naman kasi sa atin, wala namang mga lupa na kahit na gusto mong magtanim, wala talagang mapagtatamnan.

CHE: Kaya dapat either irecycle o kumbaga gumawa ng panibagong product out of waste kasi sayang din naman yung mga materyales na ginamit.

AE: Tapos ayun for livelihood talaga after you educate the community. Ano lang yung parang when you help yung mga tao sa barangay in implementing solid waste management, you also teach the people how to fish kumbaga. Hindi lang sila is spoonfeed ng mga needs pero yun nga siyempre dapat may gawin din kesa naman idle lang sila.

CHE: Balak ko nga po sana mag-interview sa area malapit sa creek kung saan may informal settlers. Kaso natatakot po ako dahil sa covid and for safety purposes na rin kaya hindi na muna.

AE: Hindi rin natin sure kasi maraming pwedeng asymptomatic lang pero so far sa lahat ng barangays dito sa atin kahit nung naglockdown, dito sa Alicia yung wala masyadong case, parang isa lang nung total lockdown from March to June. Sandwich tayo ng Sto Cristo, Ramon Magsaysay sila yung marami. Tapos noong mayroong nag loose ng quarantine doon tayo nagkaroon ng mga possible cases pero di naman kumalat dahil WFH ang mga tao.

CHE: Mayroon pa po ba kayong gustong maidagdag sa recommendation? Kumbaga sa community...

AE: Yun lang. Dream ko lang talaga yun.

CHE: Okay po yun kasi at least malobby po natin sa barangay. Ito yung mga mungkahi ng mga resident kasi may mga pondo naman sila para dito.

AE: Tayo din kasi yung mga pinakamahirap na barangay kasi lahat ng commercial establishments nasa Sto Cristo at Ramon Magsaysay. Dito talaga ay purely residential. Parang ang hatian pa kasi nito di ba pag kumaliwa ka diyan yung simbahan yung side ng simbahan tapos yung kabilang side Ramon Magsaysay so sa kanila yung 7-11, Jollibee, etc. Ganun yung hatian. So parang hmm? Bakit sila

mayaman tayo mahirap parang ano lang... You can only do so much. Ang maganda lang kasi sa street natin hindi siya yung magulong street.

2. Interview with Ms. Raquel Moreno (Small Enterprise Owner)

CHE: Magandang araw po! Ako po si Cherry Holgado at nandito po ako para magconduct ng interview tungkol sa solid waste management dito sa ating barangay. Bale thesis ko po siya sa masteral ko sa UP. Ang area ko po kasi ay dito nakafocus sa Barangay Alicia tapos ang topic ko po ay tungkol sa solid waste management. Napili ko po kayo bilang isa sa mga respondents ko dahil small enterprise owner po kayo at nalalapit din in terms of location kesa lalabas po ako sa malayo ay mahirap na po gawa ng Covid pandemic. Mga simple question lang naman po ito regarding solid waste management. Confidential po lahat ng data na makukuha. So unang una po muna ay ang inyong profile. Pwede po makuha ang inyong pangalan?

RM: Raquel Moreno

CHE: Ilang taon na po kayo?

RM: 40 years old.

CHE: ano po yung address dito?

RM: 85 Cotabato St.

CHE: Part two po ng interview ay nakafocus sa awareness pagdating sa solid waste management dito sa barangay. May mga alam po ba kayong mga policies or ordinances tungkol sa solid waste management?

RM: Ang alam ko ay yung separation ng wastes. Ilang years na iyon di ba pinapagawa sa atin?

CHE: Sa palagay niyo po ay nagagawa naman po kaya?

RM: So far naman, ngayon ay nagagawa namin yan kasi ginagamit namin yung mga na nabubulok doon sa halaman bilang pataba.

CHE: Ah kayo po pala ay nagcocomposting.

RM: Oo, iniipon namin.

CHE: Pero ano po yung separation ng waste? Anong label? Paano ninyo hinihiwalay ang inyong mga basura?

RM: Yung nabubulok sa hindi nabubulok. Tapos yung iba yung mga katulad ng mga bottles na ganyan, yung mga pang recycle tulad ng mga bote at karton. O kasi marami naman akong mga karton.

CHE: Saan nyo po pansalamantalang tinatago?

RM: Ah pinamimigay ko na lang.

CHE: Pinamimigay nyo lang po, hindi binebenta?

RM: Yung mga may pambayad o sige go. Pero mga dos lang naman yun, tres. Pero yung iba hinihingi lang usually.

CHE: Bukod sa waste separation, meron pa po ba kayong gustong idagdag? Mga activities po kaya ng barangay may alam po kayo? Mga kinonduct nila before dito sa barangay natin?

RM: Wala na akong maisip. Pero diyan lang yung alam ko sa separation na nagdistribute sila ng mga materials. Katuwang doon yung city hall. Alam ko yun yung ordinance natin dito sa barangay.

CHE: Kailan po kaya sila nagdistribute ng IEC materials?

RM: Mga one year ago.

CHE: Tapos sa mga recyclables, ano po yung napoproduce ninyo? Mga plastic...

RM: Yan mga ganyan o yung mga plastic bottles

CHE: May paper po kayo? Boxes?

RM: **May mga papers din.** Ginagawa ng iba, ginagamit as scratch papers.

CHE: Tapos iniistore niyo po sila dito rin sa ano...?

RM: Kapag po naulan tsaka po pag may nanghingi. Usually marami ring nanghihingi niyan eh. Kasi yung iba, yung mga malalaki. Ginagamit nila sa halaman. **Kami nagagamit din naman namin sa mga halaman yung malalaki.**

CHE: Ang susunod naman pong part ay nakatuon sa mga challenges po na encountered in terms of solid waste management before and during pandemic. So before po muna noong wala pang pandemic, may mga problems/issues po ba kayong naranasan as regards doon sa solid waste?

RM: **Sa solid waste, parang wala naman.**

CHE: So wala po kayong naranasan halimbawa matagal ang pick up ng truck mga ganoong klaseng problema?

RM: **Noon, pag sa nabubulok kasi dati di kami nagcocompost. Sa mga nabubulok, pag di agad napick up, bumabaho.**

CHE: So during pandemic naman po.

RM: **Nitong pandemic wala naman so far.**

CHE: No problem kasi halos everyday ang collection. Parang one week na po ano?

RM: **Oo everyday yung pagkuha nila mas maganda.**

CHE: Next part naman po yung mga good practices. May mga good practices po ba kayong gustong i-share kung paano minamanage ang solid waste?

RM: **Best practice siguro yung pagseseparate. Dapat ano iyan talagang ginagawang kaugalian. Ituro mo rin sa mga bata.** Kasi yung mga bata halos wala ding pakialam so dapat ituro rin sa bahay at maging strict din na kailangan yung mga nabubulok ay nakahiwalay. **Kailangan magsisimula sa matatanda ang tamang gawain dahil makikita ng mga bata.** So ayun magtatanong muna sila, saan ito mommy? Saan ilalagay ito?

CHE: Pinapractice din nila?

RM: Alam naman nila kasi may responsibility din naman sila sa bahay, eh kaya alam nila.

CHE: Ilan po pala kayong members ng family?

RM: Apat. Dalawa yung anak ko.

CHE: Next po ayang yung nabanggit ninyong issue kanina yung matagal pong magpick up at kung may ibang challenge po kayo na maisip, ano po sa tingin ninyo ang dapat na solusyon o marerecommend ninyo? Hindi lang po para sa inyo kung hindi ay para rin sa barangay hall, yung mga dapat nilang gawin para sa community.

RM: **Sana kasi dapat sa kanila din magsisimula yung strict na pag implement ng mga batas nila eh.** Kasi kung minsan pababayaan mo, minsan yung iba di mo masasabi sa ibang bahay dahil malakas si ganito, si ganyan. Kailangan strict din sila. Kasi noon meron sila pag Monday and Friday, nabubulok tapos Wednesday di nabubulok. So before parang di naman yata ginagawa kahit may schedule. Parang ibang bahay kunin mo na ito bibigyan kita. Mga lagay lagay. So dapat hindi. Parang sa small things na ganoon makikita mo na may problema. Dapat strict pa rin sila sa pag implement.

CHE: Sa tingin nyo po may activities po ba silang dapat iimplement?

RM: **Oo, yung sa paglilinis ng ilog.** Kasi minsan maraming mga ano diyan mga pasaway.

CHE: Sabi po nila naglilinis sila kahapon diyan once a month.

RM: Ewan ko siguro hindi ko nakikita eh.

CHE: May daanan po diyan?

RM: Wala eh.

CHE: Ah sa inyo pa rin po iyang sa ibaba?

RM: Nagkahalalaman kami doon sa gate.

CHE: Mayroon pa po kayo gustong idagdag sa recommendation?

RM: Yun lang po.

3. Interview with Ms. “Amy” (Household Member)

CHE: Magandang araw po! Ako po si Ms. Cherry Holgado, residente rin po dito sa barangay Alicia. Nandito po ako ngayon para magconduct ng interview para sa aking research study tungkol sa Solid Waste Management. To start with the interview, okay lang po bang makuha ang name or nickname po ninyo?

AMY: Amy po.

CHE: Ganyan po spelling?

AMY: Oo

CHE: Age po niyo Maam?

AMY: 56

CHE: Ano pong address dito?

AMY: 86 po

CHE: Sa second part po ng ating interview gusto ko po sanang malaman yung level of awareness ng policies and activities within barangay. Ilan po kayo sa household ngayon?

AMY: Five po. Asawa ko tsaka anak.

CHE: Sino po yung dalawa?

AMY: Sister ko po tsaka yung anak niya.

CHE: Ah ok so family and relatives po kayo. May alam po ba kayong mga ordinances or policies na pinapatupad sa barangay Alicia as regards sa basura?

AMY: Opo.

CHE: Pwede po ba kayong magbigay ng halimbawa?

AMY: Like yung collection po ng basura. Ano po yung hindi nabubulok every Wednesday, pag nabubulok Monday-Friday.

CHE: Ah yung collection ng iba't ibang klase ng basura.

AMY: Oo. Kaya sinesegregate namin yung nabubulok tsaka di nabubulok.

CHE: So waste segregation. Nagagawa naman po kaya siya maam dito sa inyong household?

AMY: Kami po ay dalawa yung basurahan namin. Ang isa para sa nabubulok. Isa po para sa hindi nabubulok.

CHE: Okay po. Ok lang po kaya maam na mapicturan ko yung sample ng basurahan ninyo?

AMY: Nasa loob.

CHE: Kahit kayo na lang po. Ibigay ko na lang po yung phone ko sa inyo. For documentation purposes lang po. Sa third part po ng ating interview ay nakatuon naman po sa waste management option. Nabanggit niyo po yung waste separation po ano? So dinidivide nyo lang po yung basura into two? Nabubulok at di nabubulok?

AMY: Yes. Nakalagay sa dalawang basurahan.

CHE: Under nabubulok po usually mga anong type of waste po?

AMY: Food wastes.

CHE: Sa mga di nabubulok po?

AMY: Bottles. Boxes like yung mga ganito po yan, plastics.

CHE: May mga papers po kayo?

AMY: Mayroon din konti.

CHE: So itong mga di nabubulok, sama sama na po sila sa isang waste bin?

AMY: Kaya lang po yung malalaki kasi hinihiwalay ko na lang.

CHE: Nilalabas nyo po siya? Okay, how about waste storage po maam? Saan nyo po siya iniistore? Sa loob po ba ng bahay? Kung sakaling malalaki ay sa labas po?

AMY: Yung malalaki, mabigat siyempre medyo masikip na siya sa waste bin kaya dito ko nilalagay sa labas para mas madaling ilabas sa gate. Yung mga winawalis, ganoon din.

CHE: Waste bin inside and outside house. Ito pong mga recyclables, ano pong ginagawa niyo diyan? Binebenta? Tinatapon?

AMY: Binibigay na lang din kasi sayang eh. Kung kukunin ng basura iyon at least nakatulong pa ako. Nilalagay ko na lang diyan kung meron pa akong ilalaba at hinihiwalay ko na lang din para pag kaya pa pakinabangan magagamit pa dahil malinis.

CHE: So pinapamigay nyo po. Sinasama nyo po sa dumadaang truck? AMY: - ambulance noise-

CHE: Thank you. Next part po tayo ay challenges encountered. May mga problems po ba o issues na naencounter with regards sa mga solid waste?

AMY: Wala naman po. Ngayon nga ganito halos everyday may collection. Pero last time naalala ko kasi late dumating yung truck pero very seldom lang naman nangyayari.

CHE: So considered niyo po siya as challenge halimbawa kung medyo nadelay yung truck. Ano pong ginagawa niyo sa basura?

AMY: Nasa loob lang ng bahay. Di namin nilalabas. Kasi kami naglalabas pagka talagang halos nandiyan yung truck kasi may mga hayop din na pwedeng magkalat.

CHE: Before pandemic po ba ay wala naman silang naencounter na issues? Kasi before pandemic po di po ba thrice a week lang po sila nagcocollect?

AMY: Parang ganoon naman.

CHE: Okay lang naman po ba para sa inyo ang schedule nila sa paghakot ng basura?

AMY: Ok naman kasi yung di nabubulok minsan nagagamit ko. Mahirap lang yung nabubulok.

CHE: Next naman po yung mga good practices. May mga good practices po ba kayong pinopromote inside your household regarding sa solid waste?

AMY: Segregation lang

CHE: Na try nyo na po yung recycling? Yung mga materials na pwede pang gamitin

AMY: Opo, nagrerecycle naman.

CHE: Gusto ko po sana iyang picturan. So next part na po tayo maam. May recommendation ba kayo siyempre hindi lang para sa pamilya ninyo or within your own household pero para sa buong brgy alicia pagdating sa pagmanage ng basura. Kumbaga ano pong gusto nyong mangyari sa barangay natin?

AMY: Yung maayos na pagtatapon. Halimbawa yung schedule ay Wednesday. Kasi may nakikita din akong nagtatapon kahit hindi naman araw ng pagtatapon ng basura.

CHE: Paglalabas po ng basura. Follow schedule of garbage pick up. Meron pa po? Ok po thank you po. So yung mga programa po ng LGU natin, yung barangay, may gusto po ba kayong ipabago o idagdag?

AMY: Hindi kasi ako masyadong aware sa mga programs nila. Hindi ako masyadong updated kasi. Minsan tinitingnan ko lang ang FB nila.

CHE: FB po ng brgy Alicia? Finofollow nyo po sila?

AMY: Pag may time lang pero kasi **di naman sila nagpopost parati.**

CHE: Actually bago po ako magconduct ng interview ngayon sa household level galing po ako sa barangay. Nabanggit po nila na during pandemic, wala talaga silang activity na inimplement kasi nga siyempre social distancing at kapag nagclean-up drive, kumpulan yung tao. Naglilinis sabay-sabay.

AMY: **Pero kahit noon parang wala naman.** Kasi doon po ako dati nakatira sa Antique.

CHE: Ay ok tapos lumipat po kayo dito?

AMY: **21 years ako doon.** Malapit ako sa barangay pero wala naman akong nakitang ganoon.

CHE: 21 years?

AMY: Oo. Wala naman akong nakitang clean up ng brgy. May nakita ako yung mga nag iinject sa health center para sa mga bata. Yung nag iikot ikot, pero cleanup parang wala. Pero nandyan si Ate Sally, yung naglilinis every time.

CHE: **Street sweeper daw siya yung malakas yung boses.**

AMY: **May nagwawalis po everytime pag may basura sa labas.**

AMY: Oo nagwawalis siya pero di ko lang alam kung street sweeper ba talaga siya o baka parang kusang loob niyang ginagawa.

CHE: Kasi sabi po ng barangay may hinire daw po silang street sweeper. Eh **kasong pandemic parang kumonti daw.**

AMY: Parang hindi naman po. Kasi doon malapit ako sa barangay pero wala naman.

CHE: Ganoon din po ba ang problema kahit even before pandemic ay wala na po talaga?

AMY: 2 years ago pa yata.

CHE: Okay, maraming salamat po Maam. Yun lang po at thank you so much sa inputs ninyo. Kapag maapprove na po ito ay mabibigyan din kayo ng kopya. Thank you po!

4. Interview with Ms. Elvie Razo (Household Member)

CHE: Magandang umaga po Maam, Ako po si Ms. Cherry Holgado at currently po ay nagcoconduct po ako ng study on Solid Waste Management ngayong pandemic bilang thesis ko po sa masteral ko sa UPOU. Kaya po ako naparito ay upang magsagawa ng pag-iinterview kasama ang isang household member. Unang una po ay gusto ko po sanang malaman yung awareness niyo po kung may mga ordinances po o policy na inimplement ng barangay dito po sa inyo?

ER: **Oo pero di naman nagagawa di ba? Sa umpisa lang ganoon naman ang Pilipino ever since di ba?**

CHE: Tulad po ng anong policy?

ER: **Yung segregation lang.**

CHE: Sa tingin niyo po ay hindi po siya naiimplement ng maayos?

ER: **Hindi naman naiimplement nang maayos pero ako nagtatanim kami rito so yung mga balat balat ng mga prutas pwedeng gawing compost.**

CHE: How about po yung mga activities po ng barangay?

ER: **Hindi ako active kasi.**

CHE: Pero di po ba kung may activity po sila ay dapat umaabot po dito sa atin?

ER: **Meron kasi silang parang binabayaran na tagawalis sa kalsada.**

CHE: Street sweeper?

ER: Oo, pagdating sa allowance nila, di ganun kalakihan. Ang alam kong may activities yung sa mga senior pero yung sa mga katulad kong may bahay ay wala. Dito, wala akong alam.

CHE: Ang next part po ay waste management option before and during pandemic. Nabanggit niyo po na nagsesegregate po kayo ng waste. So before pandemic po ba, paano po kayo nagseseparate ng waste? Nabubulok sa di nabubulok?

ER: Kasi di ba nagtatanim kami so yung mga papel, hinahalo namin siya sa mga balat tsaka yung mga tira tirang pagkain so plastic lang bale yung nailalabas tapos yung bote tsaka yung plastic itinatabi din namin kasi binibigay namin sa nagbabasura.

CHE: Hindi nyo po binebenta? Binibigay nyo na lang po?

ER: Hindi. Iniipon din namin.

CHE: Before pandemic pa po yun?

ER: Oo, ganun na kami. Sa lahat ng mga plastics.

CHE: Paano naman yung waste separation ninyo during pandemic yung last year same pa rin po ba?

ER: Oo, pareho lang naman.

CHE: Sa waste storage naman po, saan nyo po iniimbak yung mga wastes ninyo?

ER: Sa mga empty na gallon na ginamit, mga bote ng mantika may nakalagay na recycled na mantika tapos yung malalaking lalagyan ng mineral water kahit yung mga softdrinks nandoon din yung mga nabubulok tapos nilalagyan ng lupa.

CHE: Nagcocompost po pala kayo?

ER: Oo.

CHE: Ang susunod naman po ay ano naman po sa tingin ninyo yung mga challenges sa household level pagdating sa solid waste management? Ano yung tingin niyong mahirap gawin dito sa barangay pagdating sa pagmamamane ng solid waste?

ER: Hindi naman dapat problemahin yan.

CHE: Halimbawa pag delayed yung truck na nangongolekta ng basura.

ER: So far naman mas maganda this year dahil nagsimula na everyday sila nangongolekta. Before kasi MWF lang, three times a week lang ngayon everyday na.

CHE: Mga good practices po sa HH ninyo pagdating sa SW. Halimbawa yung mga bata po ba ineencourage silang magcompost din?

ER: Oo, tinuturuan ko din sila kung saan ilalagay kasi sa kusina pa lang meron na para sa plastic tapos siyempre tinentrain ko yung mga bata kasi mga anak ko sila.

CHE: Mayroon pa po bang ibang mga good practices sa inyong bahay?

ER: Yung paglilinis sa loob at labas ng bahay.

CHE: Pero aware naman po sila kung saan nilalagay yung basura?

ER: Oo naman.

CHE: Next po, mga recommendations po ninyo hindi lang po sa HH level. Mga recommendations niyo po sa barangay kung anong dapat na gagawin sa mga basura or tingin nyo po ba anong dapat gawin ng barangay para maimprove ang solid waste management?

ER: Dapat kasi magmeeting kasi walang coordination eh. Magbibigay lang sila ng leaflet tapos di naman talaga nila actually naiimplement yung mga ganoon. Kung ano dapat bawal o ano. Sa umpisa lang yung efforts nila tapos wala na. Kasi dati nun schedule yung nabubulok at di nabubulok. Ngayon everyday naman nila kinukuha so sama sama na yung basura basta kami nabubulok ayun naiwan sa bahay namin.

CHE: So sa tingin nyo po sa umpisa lang lagi yung kanilang initiative tapos walang coordination sa mga tao hindi siguro dapat din magpatrain sila? Tingin niyo po, ano po bang dapat nila gawin?

ER: Hindi kasi nagbibigay naman sila ng mga leaflet. Alam mo naman tayong mga pinoy sa umpisa lang gumagawa.

CHE: So hindi po nasusustain kumbaga ng matagalan?

ER: Kasi kung halimbawa ako gumagawa eh yung iba naman hindi kasi wala namang penalty, wala ring mangyayari. Eh kumikilos lang yung Pilipino pag may penalty. Nagiging masunurin dahil takot magkapenalty.

CHE: May idadagdag pa po kayo?

ER: Uhh alam mo kasi sa ano sa Japan pwede magbigay ng sample lang? Sa Japan kapag kasi ischedule pagka basura alam mo pati lalagyan mo ng basura may coding eh kaya lang kasi bibilhin mo pa sa atin hindi. Halimbawa plastic ngayon tapos naglabas ka ng ibang wastes, hindi kinukuha. Oo, so dapat may schedule. Tsaka talagang segregated ang wastes doon. Ginagaya nila dito kaya lang di naiimplement. Pag nilabas yung ibang klase ng basura dito kahit hindi schedule, kinukuha din nila. So katulad noon halimbawa naglabas sila ng nabubulok, tapos marami pa siyempre mamamaho kaya kukunin na nila.

CHE: Mapipilitan silang sumunod talaga doon kasi di kukunin.

ER: Nag work kami doon. So maganda yung patakaran nila tsaka talagang istrikto. Meron silang pinamimigay kung ano yung schedule ng iba't bang uri ng basura tulad ng lata, bote, etc. Meron din silang plastic yung lalagyan ng basura. Pag bumili kami noon, dati bumili kami sa kabilang lugar, tapos ginamit namin sa lugar namin, hindi nila kinuha so parang may specification bawat lugar. Tsaka ganoon talaga sila kadisiplinado.

CHE: Sana ganoon din kadisiplina dito.

ER: Sana nga di ba kasi tayong mga Pilipino pag may kinain, soft drinks itatapon na lang. Kaya nga pag may nakikita ako sinasabihan kong huwag ka magtapon diyan kaso itatapon lang yun sa kalsada. So natutunan ko din yun doon sa Japan. Yung kanilang system. Tapos tinuturo ko na din sa mga anak ko yung mga candy kako pag may mga candy kayo huwag nyong itapon, ibulsa mo na lang kasi doon nagsisimula yung idea na "konti lang naman". Kung bawat isa gagawin yung pagtatapon ng balat ng candy kung saan saan, dadami talaga ultimo balot lang ng candy iyon candy wrapper lang iyon, ang dami kapag pinagsama-sama.

CHE: Kasi iniisip ng mga tao konti lang naman.

ER: Oo eh kung konti tsaka dapat talaga ineeducate mo ang mga bata dahil sa bahay magsisimula iyon. Ituturo mo pa lang sa bata. Malaking bagay yun na sa umpisa pa lang, nagsisimula pa lang ang bata nakasama mo sa park o kahit saan tapos may kinakain so itetraining mo na sila at an early age para matuto yun. Di naman kasi kailangan sa eskwelahan o ano kasi nagkakaisip na ang mga bata kaya tayo na magtrain.

CHE: Sige po. Maraming salamat sa inyong mga inputs. Pwede po magpacticure? (picture taking with the informant)

5. Interview with Mr. Enrique Boco (Garbage Collector under National Solid Waste Task Force)

CHE: Magandang araw po sir, ako po si Ms. Cherry Holgado. Nandito po ako ngayon para magconduct ng interview para sa aking masters. Ang topic ko po ay tungkol sa solid waste management sa gitna ng pandemya. Bago po tayo magsimula, nais ko po sanang malaman ang inyong pangalan.

EB: Ako po si Enrique Boco.

CHE: Kayo po ay isang garbage collector, tama po ba?

EB: Naghahakot kami ng truck sa barabarangay.

CHE: Ilang taon na po pala kayo?

EB: 44 na po.

CHE: Dito lang din po kayo nakatira?

EB: Taga Fairview po ako. Sa may likod ng batasan.

CHE: Ang layo po ninyo bakit di po kayo nakaassign doon?

EB: Ano po eh may mga nakaassign kada lugar.

--Recording was cut--

CHE: Sorry po sa panandaliang pagputol. Paano po yun? Rotation po ba kayo?

EB: Bale itong barangay niyo po araw araw po namin hinahakutan. Dati sa isang linggo, tatlong beses hinahakutan. MWF po.

CHE: Kailan po nagstart iyang araw araw?

EB: Bale dalawang linggo na po.

CHE: Bakit po everyday na yung collection?

EB: Yun po ang utos ng city hall ni Mayor Joy Belmonte.

CHE: Pero yung oras po ganun pa rin kumbaga once a day?

EB: Ganoon po araw araw po. Ang start po namin dito ay 6 ng umaga.

CHE: Buong brgy Alicia po ang iniikutan ninyo? Anong oras po kayo natatapos?

EB: Depende po sa dami ng basura. Minsan 6-10 am, 6-11 am ganoon di pare parehas eh.

CHE: Sa hapon po ba nangongolekta o sa umaga lang po?

EB: Umaga lang po hanggang sa matapos tapos kinabukasan ulit.

CHE: Sa part two naman po ay tungkol sa awareness pagdating sa mga policy on solid wastes.

EB: Tungkol po yata ito sa pagsesegregate. Sa tingin ko po isesegregate po ng barangay niyo ang mga nakolektang basura.

CHE: Tingin nyo po sa bahay bahay po dapat isegregate o pagdating na sa brgy?

EB: Bale po may pupunta po sa amin na magbahay bahay para magbibigay ng flyers. Nandoon na po lahat ng detalye sa pagsesegregate.

CHE: Bale ang sinasabi niyo po dapat sa bahay bahay na magsimulang magsegregate ang mga tao.

EB: Oo.

CHE: Ano po ba sa tingin ninyo ang dapat gawin para sa malinis na kapaligiran?

EB: Dito kasi ngayon pagdating ng truck nakalabas na po ang basura dapat. Pag dating lang ng truck saka lang po dapat ilalabas para hindi kinakalat ng mga aso't pusa. Kaya po dapat ganoon.

CHE: Maglabas ng basura on time. Meron pa po ba kayong gusto idagdag? Ano pa po sa tingin nyo ang dapat gawin ng mga tao para maiwasan yung kalat kalat na basura o kaya dapat gagawin ng Barangay Alicia?

EB: Dapat laging iimplement ng barangay na tuwing darating ang truck saka lang ilalabas ang basura.

CHE: Parang mag-aannounce po ang barangay?

EB: Oo, barangay dapat nag-iimplement para sa kalinisan ng barangay niyo.

CHE: Tama po kasi siyempre kami rin ang makakaipon ng dumi. Mahirap ang madumi at magkakasakit ang mga tao. Sige po, ang pangatlong part po natin ay tungkol sa waste transport po. Tulad ng nasabi niyo kanina every day at once a day di po ba?

EB: Oo, Linggo lang po wala.

CHE: Pero pag holiday po ba tuluy tuloy pa rin?

EB: Tuluy tuloy po wala po kaming holiday. Kami kasi ang matatambakan pag nagholiday kami.

CHE: Oo nga eh pero sa inyo po ba ok lang po ba yun na walang holiday lalo na kung mabigat ang trabaho ninyo?

EB: Okay lang naman po dahil trabaho namin iyan. Katulad ng pasko't bagong taon, mahal na araw wala kaming day off eh.

CHE: Paano po yung bayad sa inyo? Tuluy tuloy din?

EB: Ganoon din po walang doble. Normal na sahod lang.

CHE: Kahit na holiday?

EB: Opo.

CHE: Ang hirap pala talaga. Ang sasakyan po ninyo provided ng city hall or barangay?

EB: Opo. Bale po kinontrata po ng city hall yung truck na iyan para ihakot ang mga basura po sa Quezon City.

CHE: Di po parang inoutsourced galing sa labas?

EB: Oo, tapos inarkila lang po ng city hall na ihakot parang kinontrata lang po.

CHE: Pare pareho po ba yung sasakyan sa buong Quezon City?

EB: Pareparehas po.

CHE: Ilang sasakyan po lahat ginagamit sa tingin ninyo?

EB: Alin po? Lahat ng district o...

CHE: Sa barangay Alicia lang po mga ilang truck?

EB: Isa lang po. Ako lang ang driver.

CHE: Kayo lang po? Grabe eh paano kung absent po kayo?

EB: May kapalit naman po kung ganoon. Hindi po mapapalyahan iyan. Kung nasiraan ako may kapalit kaagad at may pupunta agad dito. Sasabihin ko agad sa management namin na sira ang truck ko para mayroon nang kapalit dito.

EB: Magkaaberya man ang truck ay may kapalit. Para hindi na matambakan ng basura ang barangay.

CHE: So susunod naman pong part ay ang challenges pagdating sa solid waste. Ano ba yung mga issues sa tingin niyo na dapat maayos o may mga mahihirap na pagkakataon kayong naencounter pagdating sa pagdrive at pangongolekta ng basura?

EB: Ayun po yung masikip ang kalye minsan nakakasagi ako. Sa mga sasakyan, di maiwasan sobrang sikip dahil sa double-parking.

CHE: Kumbaga yung daanan po ng truck mismo?

EB: Oo, halos nakadoble sa kabila kaya parehas lang double parking ba nakakasagi ako eh.

CHE: Tapos sa mga pangongolekta naman po ng basura, mayroon po ba kayong mga naencounter na mga issues o challenges?

EB: Mayroon po. Minsan may isang nagpapagawa ng bahay tapos pinapahakot yung mga debris.

CHE: Paano po yun?

EB: Kailangan pag-usapan sa barangay.

CHE: Marami po yun kasi nagpapaayos ng bahay.

EB: Opo pero hindi po isang hakutan. Kinabukasan yung iba at pakonti konti lang po hanggang sa maubos ang mga debris. Hindi po lahat kasi paano yung mga ibang basura hindi mahahakot.

CHE: Wala naman pong parang aksidente na mga ganun ba halimbawa may mga bubog ang mga basura?

EB: Madalas nga silang madale sa pagbubuhos ng sako. Nabububog yung paa nila tsaka kamay tsaka yung stick paghawak nila ng basura may nakatayo na stick kaya natutusok sila.

CHE: Paano yung pagamot nagbibigay naman o sarili lang?

EB: Wala naman po. Sariling sikap sa pagpapagamot.

CHE: Pagka ganyan po ba ang natatanggap niyo ay sahod lang talaga?

EB: Sahod lang po. Sahod lang per trip.

CHE: Wala kayong mga insurance? Health insurance siyempre ang bigat ng trabaho ninyo papaano kung mapaano kayo?

EB: Sa driver mayroon yata kasi bago pa lang ako. Mga pitong buwan pa lang ako diyan.

CHE: Seven months in service. Saan na po nakaassign yung pinalitan ninyo?

EB: Bale po noong nagpalit na ng ibang company yung contractor, kami na po ang ipinalit. Siguro mga two years na po. Dati po ang humahakot na company dito ang pangalan nila LEG tapos natalo po sa kontrata noong nagbidding.

CHE: LEG Company ang may hawak?

EB: Dati.

CHE: Ngayon po?

EB: ISWEM.

CHE: Sa kanila din po ba yung truck o hindi?

EB: Iba po yung truck na iyan. Pati po may-ari.

CHE: Pero ano po ba ang pinagkaiba ng before and during covid sa pangongolekta ng basura?

EB: Dati nadadaan naming lahat. Nitong may covid, halos yung iba di namin pinapasok dahil nga may lockdown.

CHE: May restrictions kumbaga.

EB: Oo, may ganoon. Hind napapasok ng truck.

CHE: Paano pong ginagawa doon sa mga basura ng mga hindi napapasukan?

EB: Ano po yung nilalabas lang po sa gilid ng kalsada sa gabi may kumukuha doon sa main road. Yun na lang po parang ganyan na rin po ginagawa ng nag-iimplement kung may ganoon sa isang lugar.

CHE: Pero dati po noong wala pong covid kahit saan nakukuhanan nyo ng basura?

EB: Opo kahit saan.

CHE: Pero yung dami po ng basura noon at ngayon, may pagkakaiba po ba?

EB: Mas marami po noon. Kasi po noon ang hakot lang talaga ay tatlong beses sa ilang linggo. Ngayon inaraw araw na halos di kami napupuno eh. Pag hinahakot namin noong araw, may natitira pa. Di ba MWF, Monday hahakot kami para sa nagdaang lingo. Ang daming basura may naiwan na kaming isang street. Binabalikan ng truck yun pagkahapon na.

CHE: Kaya mas marami noon kasi hindi ganoon kadalas ang pangongolekta?

EB: Oo, di ganoon kadalas. Mas maganda na ngayon nahahakot ang basura araw araw.

CHE: Pero may pinagkaiba po ba ang basura noon at ngayon o halos pareho lang? O tingin nyo ano po yung klase ng basura na nilalabas ng mga tao?

EB: Parehas lang din po. Kasi po hindi po nasegregate parang halo halo lang din po ganoon lang.

CHE: Sige po. Last portion na po tayo ng interview. Ano po sa tingin ninyo. Kanina ang mga nabanggit ninyo na challenges ay masisikip na kalye at may double parking. Kumbaga yung structure ng dadaanan ninyo ay isa sa mga problema. Tsaka yung health hazard kumbaga walang insurance halimbawa kung mapaano

kayo ay sariling sikap po ang pagpapagamot. Ano po kaya ang recommendation inyo o anong masasabi ninyo para malutas ang problema?

EB: **Kung sana mabigyan po kami ng benepisyo.** Yun lang po para kung sakaling maaksidente ay may makukuha naman kaming mga insurance sa company. Yun ang kahilingan lang namin.

CHE: Benefits po o kasama sa sahod?

EB: Oo nga po saka sa **sahod din na tumaas din.** Medyo mababa po. **Per trip kami eh pag sira ang truck wala kaming sahod.**

CHE: Naku per trip po pala. Paano po kung per trip eh sira yung sasakyan at di nyo naman kasalanan iyon.

EB: Wala pa rin kaming sahod.

CHE: Sa mga basura naman pong kakalat kalat, ano sa tingin ninyo ang dapat na solusyon diyan?

EB: Sa ganyan naman po, **sa barangay din po ang mag-iimplement niyan.** Kasi di po namin kayang sawayin yung mga nagtatapon kung saan saan.

CHE: Tanong ko lang din po halimbawa nakolekta nyo na po yung basura, saan na iyon pupunta?

EB: **Pagkatapos po naming kolektahin ito, dinadala namin ito sa landfill sa Montalban, Rizal.**

CHE: Puno na po ba yung sa Payatas?

EB: Wala na po yung sa Payatas matagal na.

CHE: May iba pa po bang pinagtatambakan ng basura bukod sa Montalban?

EB: Meron po kaso hindi na po sakop natin. San Mateo, sa Boso-Boso.

CHE: Puro landfill pala doon? Tapos ano po yun itatambak lang din po doon lahat?

EB: **Sa bakanteng mga malaking lote bundok po yun maam tapos tatabunan ng lupa.**

CHE: Sino po magtatabon ng lupa o kumbaga sama sama muna tapos tatabunan?

EB: Oo tapos tatabunan ng lupa ng bulldozer. Bundok po yun malaking bundok. Tinatabunan ng lupa tapos basura, lupa, basura, lupa...

CHE: Pero pagdating po doon halo halo na malamang lahat ng basura.

EB: Oo, lahat ng segregation kung saan mang ibang lugar kasi sa Quezon City may ibang lugar din na may segregation eh. **Pagdating doon sa tapunan ay halo halo na rin yun.** Wala nang segregation basta pag tinapon na doon halo halo na iyan.

CHE: Sayang eh di ibig sabihin halimbawa yung pwedeng ibenta hindi na mabebenta kasi halo halo na doon sa landfill.

EB: Opo, **yung pahinante ko naman nakakahakot sila ng mga kalakal.** Yung mga nakikita lang nila at naiipon nila pero mayroon pa ring natitira sa tapunan at may kumukuha pa rin doon. Meron pa ring kinakalkal doon.

CHE: May nakatira po bang mga malapit doon? Hindi pa po kasi ako nakarating. Kayo po ba naghahatid doon?

EB: Oo, **ako rin nagtatapon doon ng mga nakolektang basura. May mga bahay bahay sa gilid noon eh. Yun ang mga nangangalakal.**

CHE: Paano po yung truck ninyo? Halimbawa naihatid na doon tapos saan na iyon dadalhin?

EB: **Doon po sa dispatching area. Pinaka motorpool.**

CHE: Saan po iyon?

EB: **Doon sa may bandang Payatas.**

CHE: Doon niyo rin po kinukuha yung truck na iyan kada umaga?

EB: Opo, doon po namin kinukuha kada umaga.

CHE: Galing Fairview ang ruta nyo kuya ay Fairview, Payatas, dito sa Alicia tapos balik na naman ng Payatas?

EB: Oo, tapos pupunta kami sa dispatcher namin kukunin namin yung ticket. Titingnan namin kung saan kami naassign. Eh ako lagi ako nakaassign dito araw araw.

CHE: Mayroon pa po ba kayong maidadagdag kumbaga anong gusto ninyong enhancement o improvement para maayos itong barangay Alicia pagdating sa basura?

EB: Ayun lang po sana magsegregate. Maganda malinis. Segregation tsaka hindi nakakalat ang mga basura sa kalsada. Wala pang truck, nakalabas na kaya sabog sabog.

CHE: Gusto niyo sana pagdating ng truck ay saka ilalabas.

EB: Oo, para hindi na nagwawalis pa kasi kalat kalat eh.

CHE: Paano po yung mga basura di ba parang may dikit dikit na bahay diyan sa tulay? Paano po yung basura nila? Naisasama ba sa inyo o baka sa ilog na nila itinatapon.

EB: Yung iba yun daw sabi sa ilog na tinatapon eh. Pero nung inaraw araw na ang pagkuha ng basura, hindi na raw sila nagtatapon sa ilog. Kasi nung nakaraan, tatlong beses lang. Natatambakan sila tapos tinatapon sa ilog. Sa gabi nila tinatapon sa ilog. Pero ngayon di na daw sila nagtatapon sabi ng barangay. Tinanong ko.

CHE: Kasi mahirap po, madumi na ang ilog sa likod.

EB: Oo, tapos itatapon pa yung basura sa ilog. Marurumihan lalo.

CHE: Sige po, maraming salamat sa mga inputs ninyo.

--getting contact details---

CHE: Pagtapos po nito ay sa barangay naman ang aking tungo.

EB: Oo, tama yan.

CHE: Kasi mas mainam kayo muna nakausap para at least yung mga concern ninyo, masasabi ko sa kanila.

EB: Opo, marinig nila yung sinabi ko na double parking. In case din po kung sakaling may sunog yung bumbero di makapasok. Basura nga di makapasok, yung bumbero pa kaya. Mas malaki yun eh di masusunog na yung bahay.

CHE: Paano yun kuya kung di kayo makapasok, ilalabas nila yung basura nila?

EB: Aatraas kami at babalik sa kabilang lugar. Tapos sasabihin namin paano ito eh hindi kami makapasok. Eh bahala na sila.

CHE: Baka dapat may policy din na bawal ang double parking.

EB: Kaya nga tama po iyan.

CHE: Maraming salamat po sa paglaan ninyo ng oras para sa interview na ito.

6. Interview with Mr. Alvin Fortea, Brgy. Consultant and Kgdw. Enriquez (Brgy. Alicia)

ALVIN FORTEA

CHE: Magandang araw po! Ako po si Ms. Cherry Holgado. Naparito po ako para magconduct ng interview para sa aking masters sa UPOU kung saan ang topic ko po ay tungkol sa Solid Waste Management.

AF: Emphasize ko lang na ang problem talaga is waste segregation considering na ginawa namin lahat ng campaign, advocacy, even yung mga flyers, distribution of flyers was undertaken but ang hirap nila pasunurin eh.

CHE: Sa tingin niyo po sir ang pinakakailangan talaga is more on strategy? Pero may existing policy na kayo Sir with regards sa local policies?

AF: Local policies at tsaka mga guidelines na issued ng Quezon City Government sinusunod namin but unfortunately eh siyempre yung residents na andoon pa rin matigas ang ulo hindi mo mapilit eh. Kasi pag isinunod at inimplement namin, inapply namin lahat ng laws and ordinances natin eh mauubos lahat ng residente. Baka 90% natiketan. Kasi yung practice ng waste segregation ang pinakamahirap di ba? Ang pinakamahirap segregation at source. So iyan ang challenge. Hindi ko makita na kung kailan kaya mangyayari at magkatotoo talagang nasusunod na ng mga residents natin. Kasi dito wala naman tayong big companies, supermarket na lahat at usually most ay residential sa atin eh. Eh doon naman sa part na pamilyar ka naman sa ilog natin. Eh continuously naman ang paglilinis namin niyan.

CHE: May schedule po ba kung kailan siya usually nililinis?

AF: Nag-iischedule kami at least once a month. May mga pictures din kami. May mga pictures diyan yung mga tao natin ay mismong nandoon at naglilinis kasama yung mga kagawad namin na naglilinis din doon. Problema lang siyempre yung mga residente malapit doon sa ilog kung pamilyar ka. Alam mo kung sino. Eh whether gawin namin everyday iyan eh mas maraming natatapon kesa nalilinis namin. Yun yung kanilang ginagawang disposal area. Sa residents naman, yun nga lang yung waste segregation yung isang problema namin - at source na segregation. Tapos ang sabi pa di ba bawal ang plastic eh di naman puwedeng walang plastic. Pagkain, diba bibiling ulam, nagtitinda ng ulam, hindi natin pwede iapply na para tayong nasa America.

CHE: Actually, finafast track na po nila iyan sa Congress iyang single use plastic na iyan.

AF: We try dito talaga na may strict implementation noong inilaunch ang city ordinance ng bawal na paggamit ng plastic. Eh ang tanong paanong bibili ka ng ulam sa palengke at di pwede sa papel. Eh sa supermarket oo. Most supermarkets talagang iniimplement nila wala nang plastic bag. Okay lang iyan. Eh pero sa labas yung mga nagtitinda ng ulam na residente gagamit ng plastic iyan. And then ngayon, ang problema ko pa sa mga basura natin, eto na dapat separate ang pinaglalagyan nila.

CHE: Hazardous wastes po ba?

AF: Oo kasi hazardous nga siya at infectious din. Kasi probably di natin alam kung may covid ba. Dito inaadvise amin yung utility as much as possible iseparate niya yung mga ganito.

CHE: May MRF po ba dito sa brgy Alicia?

AF: Wala tayong lugar. Pero alam ko mayroon kaming MRS. Facility wala. Kasi maglagay ka ng facility eh wala namang area. Ni basketball court nga wala ang brgy Alicia. Di tayo sinuwerte. Unlike ng Santo Cristo at Magsaysay, parehas silang malalaking barangay.

CHE: May profile naman po ng barangay Alicia na pwedeng mahingi sa inyo?

AF: Lahat mayroon. Kumpleto naman tayo na pwedeng makatulong diyan sa thesis mo.

CHE: Sir, ano po name ninyo? Sorry hindi ko po nakuha kanina.

AF: Alvin Fortea

CHE: Consultant po kayo?

AF: Utility na lang wala naman pinagbago ang suweldo ng consultant and utility parehas allowance eh. Inaassist ko lang naman sila dito especially on legal matters.

CHE: Ano pong hinahandle nyo sir, all aspects sir? Di lang sa solid waste?

AF: Ako? Yung mga legal concerns nila tapos barangay procedure kasi si Kap bago lang, newly elected siyempre sa LGU code hindi siya familiar pati sa mga procedure dito sa brgy so kung anong datnan dapat ay matutunan.

CHE: Matagal na kayo dito sir?

AF: Dito sa barangay nag start ako last 2019. Kasi 2018 siya noong naelect. So, January 2019 ako nagstart dito. Pero sa government service matagal na ako. Kasi I was the chief of staff ng isang counsellor Calalay before siya naging congressman. Nagkahiwalay kami kasi namatay siya. Pero during that time, nagstart kami ng 2004. Ako ang naging chief of staff niya hanggang congress. Kaya medyo familiar ako sa procedure ng gobyerno.

CHE: Suwerte naman po ng barangay Alicia.

AF: Hindi tumutulong lang. Yun nga lang kasi may mga ilang information na hindi ko maibigay kasi siyempre nasa kanila naman yung mga dokumento pero yung mga activities na ginagawa dito **number one talagang sinisigurado namin yung waste collection and dapat on time.** Siyempre masaya nga kami kasi everyday na nga ang collection natin. Pero ang request ng city hall dahil nga everyday na is **still sana mapractice yung segregation at source.** Kasi anjan na, everyday na kaya wala nang naiipon eh. Simula nung nilaunch namin last Monday. **Nilaunch namin so nagkaroon ng information campaign. Last Monday nagstart yung everyday. If I'm not mistaken nilaunch yung everyday collection.**

-recording paused-

AF: **Puro nauuna yung pakisama before natin iapply yung batas hindi katulad sa America kahit sino ka pag nagviolate ka di ba may parusa?** Talagang either kasuhan ka o immediately issuehan ka ng violation ticket naseset aside doon sa pakikisama. **Laging yung mga career ng ating mga politicians ay nangunguna so iyan yung mga bagay na problema kung bakit di natin siya strictly maimplement.** At least hindi naman kami humihinto diyan sa aming campaign kasi pag umiikot yung truck natin ng basura, may kasama sya kasi may **nakaassign kaming tanod to make sure na maayos ang pangongolekta.** Hindi naman pupuwedeng ilabas mo lang eh. Inadvise namin hindi pwedeng ilabas ang basura kung wala pa naman ang truck. Malakas naman yung busina ng truck. At tsaka hangga't maaari, may mga lalagyan sila. **Yun nga lang talagang hindi talaga nakasegregate.**

CHE: So parang ang lumalabas sir, **hindi lang talaga issue on solid waste. Marami siyang kakabit na usapin. Interconnected siya.**

AF: Talaga. Pero number one hangga't maaari siyempre we're trying our best na maimplement and makapagcomply yung mga residents natin sa batas. **Tsaka ngayon, mahirap ang function ng barangay kasi nakabantay lagi ang DILG sa amin. Mahigpit hindi katulad ng dati especially wala pang pandemic noon. Medyo relaxed yung brgy officials. Pero ngayon, hindi pwede na ang brgy official ay hindi nagfunction.** **Once may committee kay, make sure may accomplishment report ka at nagfunction nang maayos iyan at nagcocomply sa DILG.** Tsaka lagi kaming may ganoon. Ngayon utos from national government, possible galing sa inyo yung mga clean up drive na iyan. **Tapos meron din kaming tinatawag na TUPAD project ng DOLE. So sila yung mga nakaassign na street sweeper kung saan nakakatulong sila sa paglinis ng lugar natin aside doon sa talagang appointed namin na dalawa o apat na street sweepers namin everyday.** Naka schedule sila at may kanya kanyang area rin yung street sweepers.

CHE: Under po yun ng DOLE?

AF: Oo, project kasi ng DOLE iyan tsaka ng DSWD. TUPAD iyan yung para sa mga displaced workers. Eh dahil ngayong pandemic, ang ginagawa namin is to identify families na walang income. So maayos naman yung katawan, sila na ang qualified na maglilinis. Minsan 10-15 days maglilinis pero marami sila. Mga 10-20-30 na tao.

CHE: Sino po ang may sagot ng compensation nila? Sa barangay din or...

AF: Hindi galing sa OO. Dahil nga dumadaan. Gaya ng kay congressman Crisolago, yung fund galing sa kanya pero galing daw ng DOLE. So pagkatapos naman niyan may accomplishment report, may mga pictures yung mga tao. Kami naman is magcecertify lang na talagang nagtrabaho yung mga tao na kasama doon sa TUPAD.

CHE: Ongoing po yan sir hanggang ngayon?

AF: Katatapos lang yata alam ko tapos magsasabi ulit sila kung may budget ay mag allocate sila per barangay. Malalaman namin kung ilan so magsusubmit na naman kami ng panibagong tao. So aside doon sa nakakatulong sila makalinis ng barangay natin, natutulungan din yung family.

CHE: Mga ilan ang estimated sir? Mga ilang family members ang nahire as street sweeper?

AF: Hindi kagaya ng nakaraan mga 30. So meaning mga 30 HH agad iyon. Hindi naman puwedeng magkapatid ang kukunin namin kasi ang nagiging requirement namin diyan is tingnan namin yung mga naapektuhan pag nagtrabaho. Lalaki babae kinukuha namin.

CHE: Sir meron po kayo dito parang localized action plan for solid waste management? Kumbaga from the ordinances or resolution na nilalabas ng city hall meron kayo sa brgy level?

AF: Hindi ko lang alam kong may nagawa noon. Siguro baka meron kay kagawad.

KAGAWAD

CHE: Magandang hapon po Kagawad. Ako po si Ms. Cherry Holgado at nakatira ngayon sa Cotabato St. Nandito po ako ngayon para magconduct ng interview tungkol sa solid waste management before at ngayong pandemic. Ito po ay para sa thesis ko ngayong masters sa UP. Ang tinetake ko po is environmental management kaya po yan po ang topic na pinili ko. Habang nag-isip po ako ng topic, bakit di po ako magfocus kung saan po ako nakatira? At least makaambag pa ako. Baka yung pagaaral ko po ay makatulong pa sa pagstrategize kung paano masosolve yung problema on solid waste management.

KAG: Ito kasing nagdaan na pandemic, hindi namin naisagawa yung project namin kasi bawal pa ang mga seminars. Pero marami pa po kaming dapat na gagawin sa brgy. Concern ko din ay senior na rin ako kaya di ako pwede.

CHE: Kung pwede pong malaman, how young are you na sir?

KAG: 71 na ako. Kaya itong mga nagdaang pandemic, di ako masyadong naging active. Pero yung collection basura naman dito sa barangay ay tuloy tuloy naman every other day. Pero ngayon, nitong two weeks ago, everyday collection na. Bale ang biodegradable MWF. Ang non-biodegradable, T-TH-S.

CHE: Sunday sir day off na nila?

KAG: Pero ang problema sa amin yung pag assign ng basura. Doon sa binigay sa amin na assignment ng EWMD ni Sir Manny, ang assigned sa amin ay one dump truck lang. Pero di nasunod iyon kasi madami pa ngang waste material na naiiwan.

CHE: So ilan na sir ang truck na uumiikot?

KAG: Dati every other day ay dalawa. Isang forward at tsaka isang mini dump truck kasi may tatlong araw na hindi nakukuha talaga. Kasi Monday biodegradable. Wednesday non-biodegradable. Friday. Bale isang araw lang ang di nabubulok na kinukuha tapos lalagpas ng Saturday ang Sunday tapos matatambak pagdating ng Monday. Naging pabor naman sa amin yung ginawa na everyday na collection. Pero di pa rin na naensure yung paghakot kasi yung iba di naman nasusunod yung segregation. Dito sa amin kasi merong informal settler. Yung part ng Tacloban exit. Yung iba nagsesegregate, yung iba hindi. Kahit naman hindi magsegregate, ang pakay naman namin kunin na kahit di naseggregate kasi pag hindi kinuha, itatapon nila sa ilog.

CHE: So parang wala pong choice sir.

KAG: Itatapon naman nila sa creek pag di namin kinuha di ba? Kaya pag sinabi ng tanod na naka-assign diyan, sabihin na lang sa nagmomonitor ng EWMD na kukunin namin kasi pag di namin kinuha, itatapon nila sa ilog, sa creek. Kaya ganoon po yung problema. Pero ngayon, okay naman. Kasi minsan nasa 70 percent yung laman ng truck. Sa ngayon, ang nakukuha kasi nga naglabas nga sila ng basura at isang supot lang kasi noong nagdaang araw nakuha na yung iba kumbaga. Sa mga malaki naman, bulky wastes, gumagawa kami ng request ni sir Alvin. Ang bulky waste po namin dito inaayos muna. Yung nagtrim ng puno, tapos yung mga concrete debris sa construction. Depende. May request po yun sa EWMD. Gagawa po kaming request papipirmahan kay Kapitan. Bale Tuesday afternoon dapat maipasubmit na. Every Tuesday kung magrequest po tayo in bulky waste. Tuesday dapat maisubmit sa EWMD para kinabukasan po Wednesday, maiforward doon sa contractor ng garbage collector at gagawa po sila ng assignment ng truck kung alin ang dadalhin. Pag nakagawa naman po sila ng assignment ng truck, pinagbibigay alam po sa amin dahil yung truck po na darating, Sunday na po iyon.

CHE: So strict po yung timeline nyo sir ibig sabihin Tuesday dapat ilalabas na talaga siya tapos kinabukasan, sa contractor, by Sunday kailangan mailabas na yung truck to collect the bulky waste.

KAG: Dapat hindi na nila pwedeng ilabas yung basura hangga't di dumadating yung truck sa harap nila. Ang nangyayari naman kasi inutusan lang ang katulong siyempre marami silang trabaho. Di nila maintay yung paglabas ng basura pag nandyan na yung truck dahil may ginagawa silang iba. Kaya ngayon, nilalabas na agad yung basura kahit wala pa yung truck. Ang nangyayari naman maam ganito. Pag di nakadating sa amin yung truck ng assigned na oras, inaabot ng tanghali at nakatiwangwang yung basura pero ang ginagawa namin, kokontakin namin yung dispatcher dun sa contractor. Sabihin namin yung mga basura nasa labas na. Kung may maiwan po, may ididivert silang truck dito kasi maam may ipipick up pa na basura. Itatawag po namin sa contractor at magdidivert sila ng truck na galing sa ibang barangay para makuha yung naiwan. Ganoon po nangyayari.

CHE: Parang salitan po? Halimbawa walang ibang naka-assign, may iba pong kukuha ng natira?

KAG: Hindi naman napapabayaang ng contractor yung katungkulan nila na hakutin yung basura. Basta pag nagreport kami na may naiwan pang basura, magdidivert sila ng truck. Kahit na hapon na, kahit gabi. Kasi po pag nagreport kami sa EWMD na hindi nahakot, mapagmumulta yung contractor. Ginagawan naman nila ng paraan. Kukunin naman po iyon. Hindi naman nila pinapabayaang na dumating pa ang kinabukasan.

CHE: Sir, marami po ba kayong junkshops dito sa barangay Alicia?

KAG: Doon po sa mga stakeholders namin dati, dalawa po yun. Ngayon po na nagpandemic, bumitaw po yung isa noong nakaraan. Ang natira po yung isa na lang.

CHE: Bakit daw po?

KAG: Nangungupahan lang po kasi sila sa pwesto. Ngayon po ang natitira yung RTD na junkshop, bandang Ilocos Sur. Noong wala pang pandemic, mayroon kaming stakeholders' meeting every third month of the quarter. Kasama dito ang mga may-ari po ng town houses, yung mga apartment. Iniimbitahan po namin sila dito para magusap-usap po kami sa problema nila sa basura.

CHE: Actually sir, isa sa mga focus ng study ko ngayon is to compare before and during pandemic. May pinagkaiba po ba?

KAG: Malaki nga po ang pinagkaiba maam kasi nga po yung ganoon pong pagmimmeeting ng stakeholder di na po nasunod ksi po di ba bawal na. Wala po kami naganap na mga seminar tsaka meeting.

CHE: So since pandemic last year, wala pa po sir?

KAG: Hanggang ngayon po. Yung EPWMD po kung magpatawag, Zoom na lang. Last march lang po nagpameeting sila. Parang last week of March lang po noong inannounce nila yung collection is everyday na.

CHE: Meron po bang directive from Mayor Joy Belmonte regarding doon sa everyday collection?

KAG: Maganda nga po nangyari kasi kahit hindi nga po nasusunod ung segregation, nakokolekta naman po lahat.

CHE: Bago po ako pumunta dito, may nainterview na akong taga task force. Nabanggit niya ang tungkol sa pangongolekta ng basura. Sabi ko sir, paano po iyon let's say nakasegregate o di nakasegregate and basura pag tinambak naman from collection nito sa barangay Alicia, saan na dinadala? Sabi nya "eh sa landfill na. Pagdating doon ay halo halo na".

KAG: Ang sistema kasi doon ganito po. Pag hinakot po sa amin dito, may station po yan diyan sa Payatas. Kasi pag dinala doon, meron pong 16 wheeler truck na mahaba at yun po ang magdadala sa Montalban. Sila po ang nagtatravel papunta po doon. Kasi po itong mga humahakot dito na dump trucks, mga 6 wheeler, 10 wheeler, hindi po makakapanhik doon sa landfill kasi po matarik. Pero may isang truck po na sila ang nagtatravel papunta doon. Yung lahat po na nakuha sa mga districts, doon po lahat dinadala.

CHE: So sir sa lahat po ng districts, Payatas muna bago dalhin sa Montalban?

KAG: Oo. Mayroon po doon na transfer area doon lang po pupunta pag nagbibiyaha siya. Bukod po yung humahakot dito at doon.

CHE: Ganoon pala kasi ang pagkakaintindi ko kanina yung mga 6 wheeler truck, sila yung nagdadala diretso sa Montalban.

KAG: Hindi po isang contractor din po yun. Kung sino po nag-ooperate ng landfill, sila din po yung contractor nila. Kung sino po yung nagcocollect ng basura doon, SWEM po yung contractor ngayon. Kung sino po yung nangongolekta sa mga district, sila din po yung nag-ooperate sa mga landfill.

CHE: Sige po. Next naman po yung mga existing policies. Meron po ba tayo niyan dito? Tulad ng mga brgy ordinances?

KAG: Sa solid waste po namin, ganoon po yung policy nga po yung segregation. Pero sa wastewater po, yun pong inoobliga ng DENR na dapat ang bawat restaurant ay meron grease trap. Actually, wala naman po kami masyadong kainan dito sa Alicia. Yun lang po tapsilog na ano dyan. Wala naman pong malaking restaurant dito sa brgy. Tapos itong mga eskwelahan, panay residential naman po

ang nandito. Ito naman pong hospital, meron pong hazard waste iyon. Di naman namin sinasakop. Sa Magsaysay po iyong hospital. Iba po ang waste diyan. May hazardous waste, hospital waste po, etc.

CHE: Paano sir yung mga hospital po?

KAG: Medical waste po iyon kaya po iba ang hakot niyan. Kasi nga po stationary iyan pero di na sa amin iyan. Everyday kinocollect din iyan.

CHE: So di na po sila dinadaan. May nangongolekta po sa kanilang hiwalay?

KAG: Hindi po. Mayroon diyan na social team ng EPWMD. Lahat po iyan kinukuha pag may eskwelahan na malapit po tsaka sa mga main road. Iba po collection diyan pero everyday din. Di kasama sa barangay natin iyan.

CHE: Bale ano lang po ang hawak ng barangay?

KAG: Street lang po. Yung mga main street po, yung sa mga highway, main street po, iba din pong hahakot diyan. Eskwelahan, hospital, di po sa amin. Kaya di po namin sila maaddress kung dapat nilang isegregate yung basura. Basta araw araw kinukuha kahit di nakaseggregate.

CHE: Sir, may copy po ba ng profile si Secretary ng Brgy Alicia?

KAG: Mayroon po. Siya po naghahawak ng mga dokumento namin. Kasi po every quarter of the month po, meron pong sinusubmit si Sec na report sa EPWMD. Yung tinatawag pong ECA. Ito po ay para sa Environment Certificate po ng barangay. Alam po ni Sec yun. Bukod sa EPWMD, ang brgy po, under din po ng Barangay Community Relation ay kasa kasama po. Sa reporting po kasi pag may problema, doon po namin sa BCRD kinocoordinate. Ang BCRD naman irerelay ito sa EPWMD. Pag bumaba po yung DENR, Tinitignan po nila yung creek.

CHE: Tuwing kailan po pumupunta yung DENR dito?

KAG: Dati po pumupunta ang DENR every quarter din po. Nagrereport din po kami sa kanila.

CHE: Even during pandemic po? Kahit po nitong may pandemic pumupunta po sila?

KAG: Hindi po, noong normal pa po noon. Wala po nitong pandemic.

CHE: Ano po ang kanilang ginagawa sir? Nagmomonitor po ba?

KAG: Sa creek lang po inoobserbahan nila kung mayroong factory or establishments na nagtatapon ng dumi sa tubig diyan.

CHE: Usually po di ba informal settlers ang problema natin doon kasi nga po pagka gabi sila nagtatapon?

KAG: Ang huli pong seminar na inattendan namin sa DENR main office ay tungkol sa kung paano maglagay ng trap doon sa ilog para mahold yung mga basura. Ang kaso naman po, wala po kaming lugar na pwedeng paglagyan ng trap na iyon kasi po malalim po yung mga lugar namin saka po yung lugar na pagsasabitan namin sa kabila di na sakop na barangay iyon. Bale ang sakop lang po ng barangay, ito lang pong side na ito. Wala pa pong isang kilometro ang sakop ng brgy Alicia sa creek. Kasi po kabila po roon yung brgy Santo Cristo. Mga ilang meters lang po iyan. Wala pang 800m, Ramon Magsaysay na iyon. Di ba sa 81 Cotabato po kayo, side kayo ng creek siguro wala pa pong 200m ay ibang barangay na iyon. Di na po naming sakop iyon. Brgy Magsaysay na po iyon.

CHE: Paano yung isesetup na trash trap? Sila po ba ang dapat na maglagay kasi sila yung mas may mahabang jurisdiction sa creek?

KAG: Hindi naman po sila umattend nung nagpatawag ang DENR. Noong nag launching po ng trap na iyon, sa Novaliches proper ipinakita. Kami naman po naghanda naman po kami. Ang sabi naman po ng DENR, magpoprovide sila ng mga net kaso hindi naman po sila nagbigay. Mayroon pong involved na NGOs

doon eh. Ang NGO po yung sa rotary ng Cubao EDSA. Dalawa po iyan tsaka yung sa Novaliches po.

CHE: Novaliches po yung isa?

KAG: Opo.

CHE: O sige po. Baka dapat ay i-follow up na po with DENR kung nagcommit sila na magprovide ng trash trap. Kumbaga iseset up na lang ng barangay.

KAG: Sila po magprovide ng net at floaters. Yun palang ilalagay doon sa net, mayroon naman pong iniipon na PET bottles. Yun po ang ilalagay kasi umaangat. Tapos yung net po naman na ilulubog doon ay may habang 1.5M kasi dito po sa amin, walang shallow water dito.

CHE: Pero sa tingin nyo po yung 1.5 M masasala niya yun hanggang ilalim?

KAG: 1-1.5 meters po yung tinitingnan namin. Nakalubog po yun tapos yung maghohold sa ibabaw ay yung mga masasalang basura.

CHE: Tingin ko nga po sir, mas convenient po yun kesa kakalkalin galing ilalim.

KAG: Pag kukunin naman po doon ay irerequest pa sa EPWMD kung kailan kukunin at kung kailan papanhik. Ang problema po sa amin, ang sabi nila yung lugar dito ay wala nang madaanan kasi nga po may mga bahay na nakapaligid. Noong nagbigay sila ng relocation area sa Pandi, di nila tinanggal yan. Bale andiyan pa po yun. Saka po yung mga nabigyan doon, wala pa pong isang taon, lumipat po ulit sa dati nilang bahay. Bumalik pa rin po dito. Ganoon po nangyari kaya kung sasabihin na po na dapat alisin ang mga eskwater ay di po namin magawa kasi wala po kaming police power. Dapat ang maghandle po nyan ay yung in-charge sa urban poor. Dapat noong binigyan ng relocation site iyan, dapat tinanggal na yung kanilang dating pwesto.

CHE: Sa tingin nyo po sir dapat po mag-intervene ang HLURB diyan?

KAG: Oo, sila po dapat ang umaksyon dyan.

CHE: Maishare ko lang po Sir. Para naman po sa clean up program sa Manila Bay, ang hirap kasi everytime na lilinisin ganoon pa rin kasi nandoon yung nakatirang informal settlers sa paligid. So yung mga wastes nila tatambak lang din ulit at yun din ang lilinisin. Paulit ulit lang. Hindi siya kumbaga sustainable in the long run kasi lilinisin nang lilinisin lang din ulit.

KAG: Mayroon nga pong Mandamus sa Manila Bay yung ano po ruling ng Supreme court, mahigpit nga po kaso noong nagpandemic, di na po nasunod yung mga activities na dapat gawin. Malaki ang naging impact ng pandemic kasi di makakilos ng maayos ang mga tao.

CHE: Anu ano naman po ang mga activities na hindi na magawa dahil sa pandemic pagdating sa solid waste management?

KAG: Yun nga po yung mga meetings at kinakailangan ng maraming tao.

CHE: Pwede po ba kayong magbigay ng example na ginagawa niyo before as regards to solid waste management na hindi niyo na magawa ngayon kasi siyempre mas mahigpit?

KAG: Itong pandemic, kapag nangongolekta ng basura, yung grupo ng contractor dapat ay may suot silang gloves at bota. Ang EPWMD po ang nagrerequire nyan. Ngayon nga pong pandemic dapat naka face mask sila tsaka nakagloves. Required po talaga iyon. Tsaka dapat pag aalis sa dispatching area, kumpleto po yung dala. May gas pump sila at may walis. Kaso ang nangyayari po pag umaalis po yung truck, naiiwan po yung ibang basura. Di naman po lahat nahahakot at nakakalat. Kaya mayroon po kaming street sweeper. Kami na lang po nag-aasikaso.

CHE: Mayroon pa po kayong gustong idagdag sir?

KAG: Yung pagkaroon lang po ng collection segregation naachieve naman po yun. Kapag di naman po namin kinuha, doon po sa parte ng Tacloban St, talagang itatapon nila sa creek. Kaya nga po yung lugar na iyon, di nila mapasok dahil marami pong nakaparadang tricycle at iba pang sasakyan at tsaka yung maliliit na establishments tulad ng karinderya, ayaw pumayag na sa kanila pumarada yung truck. Kasi nga po pag lumabas po yung basura, doon po tinatambak sa harap nila. Nangangamoy po kasi nga yung tindang ulam, wala namang takip minsan. Kaya ginagawa po namin, di po namin pinapapasok yung truck doon. Doon lang po sa main road tsaka Cotabato St. na lang. Doon pinaparada yung truck sa kanto at hahakutin lang nila. Pag alis po ng truck, ako na po ang naglilinis ng iba. Binabaldehan ko na lang po.

CHE: Sir, may mga policy po ba kayong iniimplement on this? Bawal ang double parking kasi siyempre hindi lang naman sa solid waste paano kung may sunog, huwag naman sana. Kailangan po pumasok ng malaking truck.

KAG: Minsan po kasi ang nakatoka eh batugan, minsan pag-uutusan ng barangay, parang may inutusan ding iba. Kaya minsan po hindi masundan ang truck. Nagkakaproblema gaya nga po nagkakatraffic traffic. Tapos yung paparadahan ng truck, may nakaharang. Di makaparada kasi nga po may nakaparada na. Nagagalit naman minsan yung harap. Bakit ipaparada niyo sa amin ang baho baho ng basura.

CHE: Saan ilalagay yung truck?

KAG: Yun nga po eh. Ako nga po yung sister ko cancer patient pa iyan eh. Pinababaya ko lang po. Isarado na lang po yung bintana.

CHE: Oo, pwede naman po isara na lang yung bintana para at least may malulugaran yung truck.

KAG: Para mahakot na agad.

CHE: Next, ito naman pong source separation. Sinasabi niyo sir na isang malaking challenge ngayon ang separation at source. Tingin niyo sir nagagawa naman ng mga tao iyan kahit paano?

KAG: Opo, kasi po noong wala pang pandemic, may mga containers po galing sa EPWMD. Mayroon din pong flyers na binibigay sa mga bahay bahay.

CHE: Mayroon po kayong kopya sir? Pwede po ba ako makahingi? IEC material rin po iyan eh ginagamit ninyo sa mga campaign.

KAG: Pag nagrequest naman po tayo sa EPWMD, magpoprovide naman sila ng mga tao. Nagdedeploy sila.

CHE: Pero mayroon po ba tayong pinoproduce sa barangay?

KAG: Wala po tayo dito. Ang campaigner po namin yun na rin pong street sweeper namin. Sila na rin po nagsasabi sa bahay bahay na start na po yung daily collection.

CHE: Ilan po sir yung street sweepers?

KAG: Anim po yung street sweepers natin.

CHE: For the whole barangay po?

KAG: Oo, may naka assign na silang kalye. Anim po yun. Yung dalawa po yung mag-asawa, kalye po nila yung sa Pangasinan, Ilocos Norte, Ilocos Sur at Batangas. Yung dalawa doon naman po sa Ilocos Norte, Davao, at Fort Santiago. Yung dalawa po sa Tacloban, Tacloban exit, at Cotabato. Anim lang po ang natirang street sweepers.

CHE: Before pandemic, gusto ko pong malaman kung ano po yung mga types na basura na napoproduce sa residential areas within barangay Alicia po.

Halimbawa, mas marami ba ang food wastes o plastic wastes? Tsaka during covid po sana. Gusto ko silang icompare, sir.

KAG: Bale ang nangyayari po diyan maam sa biodegradable po, nasasama na po ang food waste pati yung kitchen waste. Kasi wala naman po kaming storage facilities. Wala po kami niyan.

CHE: Pero sir MRS? Mayroon daw po kayong MRS dito sa barangay Alicia. May available data po ba kayo dito on waste generated before and during covid? May ganoon po ba kasi nagbibigay rin po kayo ng mga accomplishment reports sa EPWMD.

KAG: Mayroon po kaming record ng volume ng basura na nakokolekta.

CHE: Kumbaga last year, ito po yung waste generated, ilang percentage ang plastic, food waste, vs ngayon na pandemic.

KAG: Every second quarter po, mayroon pong best practices na nilalabas po ang barangay. Nasusunod naman ang mga iyon.

CHE: May mga documentation naman kayo sir or compilation kung ano yung mga best practices na iniimplement ninyo sa barangay?

KAG: May dokumento naman po kami noon. Marami nga kasing di nasunod nitong pandemic. Dati kasi pag bumaba naman po yung taga city hall, mayroon po kaming clean up drive every 15th po ng month or second week of the month. Buwan buwan po yun at may naka assign pong kagawad doon kung sino mag-iisponsor. Siya po magpapakain, ganoon.

CHE: Tapos namomobilize po lahat ng tao dito sa barangay?

KAG: Nagmomobilize po kami mga tanod, kasama yung dalawang sasakyan, tsaka yung checker. May dokumento naman po iyon. Kaya nga lang po ngayong pandemic, di nagawa.

CHE: Okay lang po iyon at least mainote natin ano yung mga activities na di naimplement nitong pandemic.

KAG: Panahon po iyon noong normal pa. Nasusunod po iyon. Kasi po pitong kagawad ang nakaassign kung sino ang mag-iisponsor.

CHE: Next sir, waste storage naman po since wala po tayong MRF dito sa barangay.

KAG: Wala kaming MRS, wala kaming storage. Bale system na lang po ginagawa namin kagaya yung mayroon po kami dyang cage for recyclables. Doon lang po nilalagay tapos pag naibenta po yun, kikilohin at irereport kay Secretary ang naipon na basura.

CHE: Saan po binebenta? Doon din po ba sa junkshop yung RTD?

KAG: Opo.

CHE: So parang temporary storage siya sir until such time na mapuno na tapos ibebenta siya sa RTD.

KAG: Ganoon po nangyayari kahit sa mga papel. Tsaka mayroon pa kaming isang nangongolekta ng mga recyclables. Pag nakapagbenta po siya, irereport na lang po dito kung gaano karami.

CHE: Sa waste transport, paano po yung non-recyclables? So direktso po ba sa Payatas yun?

KAG: Doon din po lahat ang bagsak nun. Saka bukod pa po sa biodegradable and non-biodegradable, yun pong bulky wastes tulad ng mga debris at yung mga bato. Yung pinagtriman ng puno. Nirerequest po namin iyan sa EPWMD para hakutin.

CHE: Ibang sasakyan po ginagamit sir pagka sa mga bulky wastes?

KAG: Oo, iba po iyon. Basta pag sinabi mo na bulky waste, iba pa po ang papadalhin nilang truck.

CHE: Regardless kung anong bulky waste basta malalaking basura sir?

KAG: Yung malimit pong nagdadala pag bulky waste ay yung forward, 6 -wheeler. Malaki po yun kasi di po pwede yung normal na truck eh.

CHE: Pwede pala iyon?

KAG: Yun po kasing contractor ngayon, ang pinoprovide po sa barangay ay open truck na forward saka yung mini dumptruck. Last time na nagdaang contractor, yung LEG. Nagpoprovide sila ng nagcocompact ng basura. Hindi na po ginagawa ng bagong contractor dito. Tsaka hindi po pwede ilagay doon yung nabubulok tulad ng mga kahoy.

CHE: Sige po. Next sir yung mga challenges naman po pagdating sa solid waste na na-encounter before. Doon muna tayo sir sa before pandemic. Tingin niyo sir, may problema po ba sa solid waste management before pandemic?

KAG: Wala naman po.

CHE: Socio economic sir. Halimbawa anong impact ng solid waste management sa pangkabuhayan na aspeto pagdating sa mga tao within the community?

KAG: Yun nga po, yung iba po ay nangangalakal kaya kumikita sila sa basura.

CHE: So may increase in income. Mas nakatulong siya sir?

KAG: Oo. Hindi naman po sila pinagbabawalang mangalakal dito but yun lang pong basura, dapat ibalik lang po sa dating pagkakaayos para di nakakalat. Kaso ngayon ngang pandemic, hindi po pwede yung ganoon kasi mas mahigpit.

CHE: Kaya ibig sabihin sir halimbawa itong sa human health, during pandemic, mas mataas ang risk. Di po ba?

KAG: Opo. Sabi nga gaya ng face mask tinatapon lang din kaya posibleng kumalat ang covid.

CHE: Last sir sa environment naman. Before pandemic sir, tingin niyo may impact ang solid waste sa environment?

KAG: Maayos naman po kasi noong kami po ay may clean up drive pa, di na po kami nagrerequest ng truck ng bulky waste. Kami na po mismo ang naghahakot.

CHE: Walang restriction before so mas madali pong gumalaw.

KAG: Opo, kasi delikado ngayon gawa ng pandemic.

CHE: Sir, doon naman tayo sa best practices. Gusto ko lang pong malaman kung may compilation po kayo nito? In terms of promoting proper solid waste management.

KAG: Doon sa cleanup drive namin mayroon pong before and after. Isa po sigurong problema, yung ibang lugar nagtatapon sa amin ng basura. Ginagawan na lang po namin siya ng report tapos after noon, nakikita naman po kung nalinis namin o hindi. Yun lang po ang best practice namin.

CHE: Pero sir ngayong pandemic tingin nyo po may mga best practices din kayo sa pagmanage ng solid waste?

KAG: Sa ngayon po limitado talaga ang activities pagdating sa solid waste.

CHE: Ano po sir ang marerecommend ninyo para maaddress yung problema natin on solid waste? May mga gusto pa po ba kayong mangyari for the barangay tulad ng mga activities na dapat iconduct kaso di natuloy ngayong pandemic?

KAG: Dapat po yung project ng DENR ay matuloy. Sana po ay maimplement na po namin pagtapos nitong pandemic.

CHE: Pero sir habang hindi pa natatapos ang pandemic, mayroon po ba kayong gustong activity na gagawin?

KAG: Wala po. Basta nirerequest lang po namin sa mga stakeholder tulad ng mga apartment, town houses, na yung waste bin nila, may marking po ng biodegradable at non-biodegradable. Di rin po sila maglalabas ng waste bin na biodegradable pag

araw po ng non-biodegradable ang hinahakot. Kasi yung mga townhouses po diyan, di naman nila maregulate yung pagtatapon ng basura ng tenants nila. Tapon lang po nang tapon. Dapat po sila ang magsasabi sa mga tenants. Para paglabas po ng araw na nabubulok, yun lang po yung ilalabas nilang bin. Di po pwedeng ilabas po yung di nabubulok. Nangyayari kasi diyan kaya kinukwestyon namin yung mga townhouse sa dami pong hindi sumusunod.

CHE: Halimbawa di sila sumunod, nag-iissue kayo ng ticket? Or parang violation.

KAG: Warning lang po. Di po namin binibigyan ng Notice of Violation. Kasi po pag binigyan namin ng Notice of Violation, pupuntahan po sila ng EPWMD. Winawarningan lang po namin. Saka hindi na po namin kinukuha alam po nila iyon eh. Pagka natiyempuhan po ng BPSO namin na di nabubulok at ang hakot po ay nabubulok, iniwan po talaga iyon. Ibinabalik sa compound nila kahit po nailabas na. Di kokolektahin po yon.

CHE: Pagka townhouse pero pag regular na residential area po?

KAG: Pag regular po na di nabubulok ang kukunin, kukunin po yun. Nangyayari po kasi may mga drum sila pero sari-saring basura ang nakalagay. Nabubulok, di nabubulok pero araw ng nabubulok. Nilalabas po nila. Natiyempuhan lang po talaga kasi yung monitoring po ng EPWMD, mahigpit din po. Bukod sa monitoring ng contractor, dalawa po iyan. Si sir Jackson at si sir Ares dalawa po sila nagmomonitor diyan. Pag nakita po diyan, sasabihin sa amin, “bakit po kagawad naglabas po ng mga kahoy doon”? Pupuntahan namin iyon. Sasabihin po namin sa may-ari ng bahay na di nila pwedeng ipahakot muna. Don po sa Cotabato St. maraming insidenteng ganoon. Malapit sa may kanto ng Ilocos Norte. Madalas silang maglabas ng kahoy at mga bato. Mga klase ng basura na di pa dapat hakutin. Sabi namin sa nangongolekta noong araw na iyon, huwag pong hakutin iyan. Kahit magreklamo sila sa brgy, haharapin namin.

CHE: Kasi di naman po sila sumusunod sa patakaran. Sir, mayroon pa ba kayong gustong idagdag na mga activities? Gusto ko rin po sanang itanong kung ilan pala kayo dito sa barangay na naghahawak ng concerns on solid waste?

KAG: Doon sa committee po ng environment. Yun din pong anim na street sweepers, in charge din po sila sa paglilinis. Nagsisimula po silang magwalis ng mga 6 oclock ng umaga. Yung iba naman, eight oclock.

CHE: Hapon po ba nagwawalis din? O every morning lang?

KAG: Sa umaga lang po.

CHE: Pero araw araw po ba ito?

KAG: Araw araw po iyon. Mayroon naman pong attendance yan.

CHE: Very helpful sir kasi kumbaga nakikita ko dito hindi lang talaga solid waste ang issue. Kaya until now, karamihan sa mga LGUs ay talagang ito ang problema yung solid waste management.

KAG: Sasabihin nila di niyo kukunin ito? Itatapon namin sa ilog. Eh pag kami naman po natiyempuhan ng DENR na marumi yung ilog, kami din po ang mapapagalitan. Kapag nagmomonitor, kung konti lang naman po yung diperensya sa dami ng basura, kinukuha na po namin.

CHE: Karamihan po ba dyan ay galing sa mga informal settlers?

KAG: Mahigpit po yung mandamus ng Manila Bay, di ba? Ang creek naman na aming nasasakupan ay di masyadong mahaba. Kami din po ay sumusunod eh iyon naman pong brgy sa kabila ay di sumusunod. Wala naman pong pagkakataon na bumaba yung DENR at binigyan kami ng notice na ganoon.

CHE: Kasi syempre nag issue din sila ng notice of violation.

KAG: Yung lugar namin ay di naman mahaba. Pag pumupunta sila dito, dinadala namin sila doon sa umpisa ng nasasakupan namin. Boundary ng brgy Santo Cristo at Alicia, doon namin sila dinadala. Nakita naman nila na malinis naman.

CHE: Sa bagay kanya kanyang jurisdiction iyan. Kailan po pala yung huling clean up drive sir?

KAG: May documentation naman kami. May picture naman po iyon.

CHE: Yun lang po sir at nacover naman po natin lahat. Kay secretary na lang po ako hihingi ng documents.

KAG: Kung may ano po talagang di po natin nagawa ngayong pandemic yung mga dapat gawin.

CHE: Understandable po kasi pandemic. Tanong ko na rin po sir yung mga policies na iniimplement dito as regards to solid waste.

KAG: Yung sa ano wala naman kaming best practices masyado. Nacomply naman namin lahat ang sinasabi ng solid waste management, kaya lang po yun nga pandemic at di makakilos.

CHE: Sige po sir, maraming salamat po! Mailalagay ko naman po sa aking thesis ang mga recommendations para maimprove ang solid waste management during pandemic dito sa brgy Alicia.

ANNEX V: SUMMARY OF KEY POINTS DURING INTERVIEWS AS INPUTS TO THE THEMATIC ANALYSIS CONDUCTED

1. Small Enterprise owner (Ms. Allodia Enriquez)

- waste segregation mga bio, non-bio
- Hindi naimplement pero Pag kinollect din kasi sabay-sabay. As far as I remember may time na talagang sobrang strict.
- Before Covid. Parang may days na kinocollect ang nabubulok tapos may days na hindi nabubulok parang wait lang
- Monday at Friday tapos Wednesday yung hindi nabubulok
- during covid, naging everyday
- Nag-iikot sila tapos nagpapaalala sila na magsegregate ng waste. Tapos meron talaga from the city hall na kasama ng truck. May isang person silang in-charge na nagmamake sure na o ito ba ay nabubulok ay di namin yan kukunin. Meron siyang sumasama parang nakaassign siya talaga for collection. Ngayon nga siguro dahil nga sa pandemic ay hindi na nagagawa.
- itong mask kinucut namin yung garter para hindi na magamit ng iba
- Ayun yung mga PET bottles hinihiwalay namin siya tapos ang nagcocollect naman niyan binibigay ko sa nangangalakal.
- Pagka basura naman ay dyan din, pupunta na diyan si Nanay. Kasi sabi ko sa kanya sasave ko talaga iyan sa iyo kaya pagka ano kunin mo na lang.
- Yung mga peelings ng mga gulay, yung mga food nilalagay din namin siya sa isang plastic.
- Separate naman po siya tapos yung mga plastic hinihiwalay yung mga cellophane ay yung mga lalagyan ng ulam, mga plastic bag, ganoon.
- Yun lang. Yung left over food. Pero minsan yung mga leftover food pinapakain na lang namin sa stray dogs ganun
- Pero kasi nga regular naman ang collection, pinapadala namin siya sa ano truck
- Siguro ang challenge lang kasi even kung gusto mo magsegregate mahirap talagang gawin.
- Ang hirap wala kasing container na pinoprovide
- Sana din may initiative din bawat household. That is our responsibility.
- Kasi diba halimbawa ikaw nagsesegregate pero iba di naman nagsesegregate. Kaya labo labo pa rin sila pagdating sa tao.
- So during pandemic, sa tingin ko na-lessen yung challenge, kasi everyday na sila halos nangongolekta ng basura. Pero yun nga sana strict implementation pa rin ng waste segregation.
- Kasi wala din siyang compost area, 'di ba? Parang kasi talagang mag-uumpisa sa barangay pero dahil kasi napakaurbanized ng area, hindi din talaga
- Nagagalit din si kapitan kapag nakita niya na basura day tapos hindi nakuha yung basura dito so naalarm din siya. So bukod din sa city hall na nag-aassist before, meron ding tanod na nag-assist.
- Pero sanay kasi yung mga tao kahit si Brgy Kap Koro ang nakaupo, tinatawag namin si Kap Ding kasi siya yung pinakamalapit kasi pag may mga problema kaming pambarangay, sa kanya talaga

- Yun pa rin kasi everyday nagluluto si Olan yung peelings nasa isang plastic bag yun ako din automatic practice ko din yung empty bottle ng mga toyo diyan talaga nilalagay sa iisang lagayan
- You help community, you help din yung mga tao na nangangailangan iyan. Iniisip namin ibebenta pa ba natin eh kailangan naman. Tayo naman ididipose naman iyan. Ba't mo pa pagkakakitaan eh makakatulong naman.
- gusto ko magkaroon din tayo ng alam mo yung truck ng basura na nagccrush na siya talaga ng wastes. Kasi ano lang siya ang nakita ko na may ganyan Marikina, Cogeo, parang mga Rizal Area.
- Sa totoo lang, ang dami din kasing mga residente na walang ginagawa
- project livelihood program
- Tapos ayun for livelihood talaga after you educate the community
- Tayo din kasi yung mga pinakamahirap na barangay kasi lahat ng commercial establishments nasa Sto Cristo at Ramon Magsaysay. Dito talaga ay purely residential

2. Small enterprise owner (Raquel Moreno)

- Ang alam ko ay yung separation ng wastes. Ilang years na iyon di ba pinapagawa sa atin?
- ngayon ay nagagawa namin yan kasi ginagamit namin yung mga na nabubulok doon sa halaman bilang pataba.
- Yung nabubulok sa hindi nabubulok
- pang recycle tulad ng mga bote at karton
- pinamimigay ko na lang
- Pero diyan lang yung alam ko sa separation na nagdistribute sila ng mga materials. Katuwang doon yung city hall. Alam ko yun yung ordinance natin dito sa barangay.
- Mga one year ago
- plastic bottles
- May mga papers din
- Kami nagagamit din naman namin sa mga halaman yung malalaki.
- Sa solid waste, parang wala naman.
- Noon, pag sa nabubulok kasi dati di kami nagcocompost. Sa mga nabubulok, pag di agad napick up, bumabaho.
- Nitong pandemic wala naman so far.
- Oo everyday yung pagkuha nila mas maganda.
- Best practice siguro yung pagseseparate. Dapat ano iyan talagang ginagawang kaugalian. Ituro mo rin sa mga bata
- Kailangan magsisimula sa matatanda ang tamang gawain dahil makikita ng mga bata.
- Sana kasi dapat sa kanila din magsisimula yung strict na pag implement ng mga batas nila eh
- Oo, yung sa paglilinis ng ilog

3. Household member (Ms. "Amy")

- Like yung collection po ng basura. Ano po yung hindi nabubulok every Wednesday, pag nabubulok Monday-Friday.
- Kaya sinesegregate namin yung nabubulok tsaka di nabubulok.

- Kami po ay dalawa yung basurahan namin. Ang isa para sa nabubulok. Isa po para sa hindi nabubulok.
- Food wastes
- Bottles. Boxes like yung mga ganito po yan, plastics.
- Yung malalaki, mabigat siyempre medyo masikip na siya sa waste bin kaya dito ko nilalagay sa labas para mas madaling ilabas sa gate. Yung mga winawalis, ganoon din
- Binibigay na lang din kasi sayang eh. Kung kukunin ng basura iyon at least nakatulong pa ako.
- hinihiwalay ko na lang din para pag kaya pa pakinabangan magagamit pa dahil malinis.
- halos everyday may collection
- Nasa loob lang ng bahay. Di namin nilalabas
- Ok naman kasi yung di nabubulok minsan nagagamit ko
- Segregation lang
- nagrerecycle naman
- Yung maayos na pagtatapon
- Hindi kasi ako masyadong aware sa mga programs nila
- di naman sila nagpopost parati
- Pero kahit noon parang wala naman
- May nagwawalis po everytime pag may basura sa labas

4. Household Member (Ms. Elvie Razo)

- Oo pero di naman nagagawa di ba? Sa umpisa lang ganoon naman ang Pilipino ever since di ba?
- Yung segregation lang
- Hindi naman naiimplement nang maayos pero ako nagtatanim kami rito so yung mga balat balat ng mga prutas pwedeng gawing compost
- Hindi ako active kasi.
- Meron kasi silang parang binabayaran na tagawalis sa kalsada.
- pagdating sa allowance nila (street sweeper), di ganun kalakihan
- Kasi di ba nagtatanim kami so yung mga papel, hinahalo namin siya sa mga balat tsaka yung mga tira tirang pagkain so plastic lang bale yung nailalabas tapos yung bote tsaka yung plastic itinatabi din namin kasi binibigay namin sa nagbabasura.
- Hindi. Iniipon din namin.
- Oo, ganun na kami. Sa lahat ng mga plastics.
- Sa mga empty na gallon na ginamit, mga bote ng mantika may nakalagay na recycled na mantika tapos yung malalaking lalagyan ng mineral water kahit yung mga softdrinks nandoon din yung mga nabubulok tapos nilalagyan ng lupa.
- So far naman mas maganda this year dahil nagsimula na everyday sila nangongolekta. Before kasi MWF lang, three times a week lang ngayon everyday na.
- Oo, tinuturuan ko din sila kung saan ilalagay kasi sa kusina pa lang meron na para sa plastic tapos siyempre tinetrain ko yung mga bata kasi mga anak ko sila.
- Yung paglilinis sa loob at labas ng bahay.

- Dapat kasi magmeeting kasi walang coordination eh. Magbibigay lang sila ng leaflet tapos di naman talaga nila actually naiimplement yung mga ganoon. Kung ano dapat bawal o ano. Sa umpisa lang yung efforts nila tapos wala na. Kasi dati nun schedule yung nabubulok at di nabubulok. Ngayon everyday naman nila kinukuha so sama sama na yung basura basta kami nabubulok ayun naiwan sa bahay namin.
- Hindi kasi nagbibigay naman sila ng mga leaflet. Alam mo naman tayong mga pinoy sa umpisa lang gumagawa.
- Kasi kung halimbawa ako gumagawa eh yung iba naman hindi kasi wala namang penalty, wala ring mangyayari. Eh kumikilos lang yung Pilipino pag may penalty. Nagiging masunurin dahil takot magkapenalty.
- So katulad noon halimbawa naglabas sila ng nabubulok, tapos marami pa siyempre mamamaho kaya kukunin na nila.
- Sana nga di ba kasi tayong mga Pilipino pag may kinain, soft drinks itatapon na lang.
- kaso itatapon lang yun sa kalsada
- konti lang naman
- ang dami kapag pinagsama-sama
- tsaka dapat talaga ineducate mo ang mga bata dahil sa bahay magsisimula iyon.
- itetraining mo na sila at an early age para matuto yun

5. Garbage Collector (Mr. Enrique Boco)

- Bale itong barangay niyo po araw araw po namin hinahakutan. Dati sa isang linggo, tatlong beses hinahakutan. MWF po.
- Bale dalawang linggo na po.
- Yun po ang utos ng city hall ni Mayor Joy Belmonte.
- Ganoon po araw araw po. Ang start po namin dito ay 6 ng umaga.
- Depende po sa dami ng basura. Minsan 6-10 am, 6-11 am ganoon di pare parehas eh.
- Sa tingin ko po isesegregate po ng barangay ninyo ang mga nakolektang basura.
- Bale po may pupunta po sa amin na magbahay bahay para magbibigay ng flyers
- Dito kasi ngayon pagdating ng truck nakalabas na po ang basura dapat.
- Linggo lang po wala
- Tuloy tuloy po wala po kaming holiday. Kami kasi ang matatambakan pag nagholiday kami. Katulad ng pasko't bagong taon, mahal na araw wala kaming day off eh.
- Ganoon din po walang doble. Normal na sahod lang
- Opo. Bale po kinontrata po ng city hall yung truck na iyan para ihakot ang mga basura po sa Quezon City.
- Isa lang po. Ako lang ang driver.
- Hindi po mapapalyahan iyan
- Magkaaberya man ang truck ay may kapalit. Para hindi na matambakan ng basura ang barangay.
- Ayun po yung masikip ang kalye minsan nakakasagi ako
- Minsan may isang nagpapagawa ng bahay tapos pinapahakot yung mga debris.

- Kailangan pag-usapan sa barangay.
- Madalas nga silang madale sa pagbubuhos ng sako. Nabububog yung paa nila tsaka kamay tsaka yung stick paghawak nila ng basura may nakatayo na stick kaya natutusok sila.
- Sariling sikap sa pagpapagamot
- Sahod lang po. Sahod lang per trip
- Sa driver mayroon yata kasi bago pa lang ako. Mga pitong buwan pa lang ako diyan.
- Dati nadadaanan naming lahat. Nitong may covid, halos yung iba di namin pinapasok dahil nga may lockdown.
- Ano po yung nilalabas lang po sa gilid ng kalsada sa gabi may kumukuha doon sa main road.
- Mas marami po noon. Kasi po noon ang hakot lang talaga ay tatlong beses sa ilang linggo.
- Kasi po hindi po nasegregate parang halo halo lang din po ganoon lang.
- Kung sana mabigyan po kami ng benepisyo
- sahod din na tumaas din
- Per trip kami eh pag sira ang truck wala kaming sahod.
- sa barangay din po ang mag-iimplement niyan
- Pagkatapos po naming kolektahin ito, dinadala namin ito sa landfill sa Montalban, Rizal.
- Sa bakanteng mga malaking lote bundok po yun maam tapos tatabunan ng lupa.
- Pagdating doon sa tapunan ay halo halo na rin yun.
- yung pahinante ko naman nakakahakot sila ng mga kalakal
- ako rin nagtatapon doon ng mga nakolektang basura. May mga bahay bahay sa gilid noon eh. Yun ang mga nangangalakal.
- Doon po sa dispatching area. Pinaka motorpool. Doon sa may bandang Payatas.
- Oo, tapos pupunta kami sa dispatcher namin kukunin namin yung ticket. Titingnan namin kung saan kami naassign. Eh ako lagi ako nakaassign dito araw araw.
- Ayun lang po sana magsegregate. Maganda malinis. Segregation tsaka hindi nakakalat ang mga basura sa kalsada. Wala pang truck, nakalabas na kaya sabog sabog.
- Yung iba yun daw sabi sa ilog na tinatapon eh.
- Natatambakan sila tapos tinatapon sa ilog. Sa gabi nila tinatapon sa ilog. Pero ngayon di na daw sila nagtatapon sabi ng barangay. Tinanong ko.

6. Barangay Officials (Mr. Fortea and Kgw. Enriquez)

- Emphasize ko lang na ang problem talaga is waste segregation considering na ginawa namin lahat ng campaign, advocacy, even yung mga flyers, distribution of flyers was undertaken but ang hirap nila pasunurin eh.
- Local policies at tsaka mga guidelines na issued ng Quezon City Government sinusunod namin but unfortunately eh siyempre yung residents na andoon pa rin matigas ang ulo hindi mo mapilit eh. Kasi pag isinunod at inimplement namin, inapply namin lahat ng laws and ordinances natin eh mauubos lahat ng residente. Baka 90% natiketan. Kasi yung practice ng waste segregation ang pinakamahirap di ba? Ang pinakamahirap

segregation at source. So iyan ang challenge. Hindi ko makita na kung kailan kaya mangyayari at magkatotoo talagang nasusunod na ng mga residents natin. Kasi dito wala naman tayong big companies, supermarket na lahat at usually most ay residential sa atin eh. Eh doon naman sa part na pamilyar ka naman sa ilog natin. Eh continuously naman ang paglilinis namin niyan.

- Nag-iischedule kami at least once a month. May mga pictures din kami. May mga pictures diyan yung mga tao natin ay mismong nandoon at naglilinis kasama yung mga kagawad namin na naglilinis din doon. Problema lang siyempre yung mga residente malapit doon sa ilog kung pamilyar ka. Alam mo kung sino. Eh whether gawin namin everyday iyan eh mas maraming natatapon kesa nalilinis namin. Yun yung kanilang ginagawang disposal area. Sa residents naman, yun nga lang yung waste segregation yung isang problema namin - at source na segregation. Tapos ang sabi pa di ba bawal ang plastic eh di naman puwedeng walang plastic. Pagkain, diba bibiling ulam, nagtitinda ng ulam, hindi natin pwede iapply na para tayong nasa America.
- We try dito talaga na may strict implementation noong inilaunch ang city ordinance ng bawal na paggamit ng plastic.
- Dito inaadvise amin yung utility as much as possible iseparate niya yung mga ganito.
- Wala tayong lugar. Pero alam ko mayroon kaming MRS. Facility wala. Kasi maglagay ka ng facility eh wala namang area. Ni basketball court nga wala ang brgy Alicia. Di tayo sinuwerte. Unlike ng Santo Cristo at Magsaysay, parehas silang malalaking barangay.
- number one talagang sinisigurado namin yung waste collection and dapat on time
- still sana mapractice yung segregation at source
- Nilaunch namin so nagkaroon ng information campaign. Last Monday nagstart yung everyday. If I'm not mistaken nilaunch yung everyday collection.
- Puro nauuna yung pakisama before natin iapply yung batas hindi katulad sa America kahit sino ka pag nagviolate ka di ba may parusa?
- Laging yung mga career ng ating mga politicians ay nangunguna so iyan yung mga bagay na problema kung bakit di natin siya strictly maimplement. At least hindi naman kami humihinto diyan sa aming campaign kasi pag umiikot yung truck natin ng basura, may kasama sya kasi may nakaassign kaming tanod to make sure na maayos ang pangongolekta
- Yun nga lang talagang hindi talaga nakasegregate
- Tsaka ngayon, mahirap ang function ng barangay kasi nakabantay lagi ang DILG sa amin. Mahigpit hindi katulad ng dati especially wala pang pandemic noon. Medyo relaxed yung brgy officials. Pero ngayon, hindi puwede na ang brgy official ay hindi nagfunction. Once may committee kay, make sure may accomplishment report ka at nagfunction nang maayos iyan at nagcocomply sa DILG.
- Tapos meron din kaming tinatawag na TUPAD project ng DOLE. So sila yung mga nakaassign na street sweeper kung saan nakakatulong sila sa paglilinis ng lugar natin aside doon sa talagang appointed namin na dalawa o apat na street sweepers namin everyday.

- Oo, project kasi ng DOLE iyan tsaka ng DSWD. TUPAD iyan yung para sa mga displaced workers. Eh dahil ngayong pandemic, ang ginagawa namin is to identify families na walang income. So maayos naman yung katawan, sila na ang qualified na maglilinis. Minsan 10-15 days maglilinis pero marami sila. Mga 10-20-30 na tao.
- pagkatapos naman niyan may accomplishment report, may mga pictures yung mga tao. Kami naman is magcecertify lang na talagang nagtrabaho yung mga tao na kasama doon sa TUPAD.
- So aside doon sa nakakatulong sila makalinis ng barangay natin, natutulungan din yung family.
- Hindi kagaya ng nakaraan mga 30. So meaning mga 30 HH agad iyon. Hindi naman puwedeng magkapatid ang kukunin namin kasi ang nagiging requirement namin diyan is tingnan namin yung mga naapektuhan pag nagtrabaho. Lalaki babae kinukuha namin.
- Ito kasing nagdaan na pandemic, hindi namin naisagawa yung project namin kasi bawal pa ang mga seminars. Pero marami pa po kaming dapat na gagawin sa brgy. Concern ko din ay senior na rin ako kaya di ako pwede.
- Kaya itong mga nagdaang pandemic, di ako masyadong naging active. Pero yung collection basura naman dito sa barangay ay tuloy tuloy naman every other day. Pero ngayon, nitong two weeks ago, everyday collection na. Bale ang biodegradable MWF. Ang non-biodegradable, T-TH-S.
- Pero ang problema sa amin yung pag assign ng basura. Doon sa binigay sa amin na assignment ng EWMD ni Sir Manny, ang assigned sa amin ay one dump truck lang. Pero di nasunod iyon kasi madami pa ngang waste material na naiwan.
- Dati every other day ay dalawa. Isang forward at tsaka isang mini dump truck kasi may tatlong araw na hindi nakukuha talaga. Kasi Monday biodegradable. Wednesday non-biodegradable. Friday. Bale isang araw lang ang di nabubulok na kinukuha tapos lalagpas ng Saturday ang Sunday tapos matatambak pagdating ng Monday. Naging pabor naman sa amin yung ginawa na everyday na collection. Pero di pa rin na naeensure yung paghakot kasi yung iba di naman nasusunod yung segregation. Dito sa amin kasi merong informal settler. Yung part ng Tacloban exit. Yung iba nagsesegregate, yung iba hindi. Kahit naman hindi magsegregate, ang pakay naman namin kunin na kahit di naseggregate kasi pag hindi kinuha, itatapon nila sa ilog.
- Sa mga malaki naman, bulky wastes, gumagawa kami ng request ni sir Alvin. Ang bulky waste po namin dito inaayos muna. Yung nagtrim ng puno, tapos yung mga concrete debris sa construction. Dependeng. May request po yun sa EWMD. Gagawa po kaming request papipirmahan kay Kapitan. Bale Tuesday afternoon dapat maipasubmit na. Every Tuesday kung magrerequest po tayo in bulky waste. Tuesday dapat maisubmit sa EWMD para kinabukasan po Wednesday, maifoforward doon sa contractor ng garbage collector at gagawa po sila ng assignment ng truck kung alin ang dadalhin. Pag nakagawa naman po sila ng assignment ng truck, pinagbibigay alam po sa amin dahil yung truck po na darating, Sunday na po iyon
- Dapat hindi na nila puwedeng ilabas yung basura hangga't di dumadating yung truck sa harap nila.

- Pag di nakadating sa amin yung truck ng assigned na oras, inaabot ng tanghali at nakatiwangwang yung basura pero ang ginagawa namin, kokontakin namin yung dispatcher dun sa contractor. Sabihin namin yung mga basura nasa labas na. Kung may maiwan po, may ididivert silang truck dito kasi maam may ipipick up pa na basura. Itatawag po namin sa contractor at magdidivert sila ng truck na galing sa ibang barangay para makuha yung naiwan
- Kasi po pag nagreport kami sa EWMD na hindi nahakot, mapagmumulta yung contractor.
- Doon po sa mga stakeholders namin dati, dalawa po yun. Ngayon po na nagpandemic, bumitaw po yung isa noong nakaraan. Ang natira po yung isa na lang.
- Nangungupahan lang po kasi sila sa pwesto. Ngayon po ang natitira yung RTD na junkshop, bandang Ilocos Sur. Noong wala pang pandemic, mayroon kaming stakeholders' meeting every third month of the quarter. Kasama dito ang mga may-ari po ng town houses, yung mga apartment. Iniimbitahan po namin sila dito para magusap-usap po kami sa problema nila sa basura.
- Malaki nga po ang pinagkaiba maam kasi nga po yung ganoon pong pagmimmeeting ng stakeholder di na po nasunod ksi po di ba bawal na. Wala po kami naganap na mga seminar tsaka meeting.
- Hanggang ngayon po. Yung EPWMD po kung magpatawag, Zoom na lang. Last march lang po nagpameeting sila. Parang last week of March lang po noong inannounce nila yung collection is everyday na.
- Maganda nga po nangyari kasi kahit hindi nga po nasusunod ung segregation, nakokolekta naman po lahat.
- Sabi nya "eh sa landfill na. Pagdating doon ay halo halo na".
- Pag hinakot po sa amin dito, may station po yan diyan sa Payatas. Kasi pag dinala doon, meron pong 16 wheeler truck na mahaba at yun po ang magdadala sa Montalban
- Mayroon po doon na transfer area doon lang po pupunta pag nagbibiyahe siya. Bukod po yung humahakot dito at doon.
- Hindi po isang contractor din po yun. Kung sino po nag-oooperate ng landfill, sila din po yung contractor nila. Kung sino po yung nagcocollect ng basura doon, SWEM po yung contractor ngayon. Kung sino po yung nangongolekta sa mga district, sila din po yung nag-oooperate sa mga landfill.
- Sa solid waste po namin, ganoon po yung policy nga po yung segregation. Pero sa wastewater po, yun pong inoobliga ng DENR na dapat ang bawat restaurant ay meron grease trap. Actually, wala naman po kami masyadong kainan dito sa Alicia
- panay residential naman po ang nandito
- Medical waste po iyon kaya po iba ang hakot niyan. Kasi nga po stationary iyan pero di na sa amin iyan
- Street lang po. Yung mga main street po, yung sa mga highway, main street po, iba din pong hahakot diyan. Eskwelahan, hospital, di po sa amin
- Basta araw araw kinukuha kahit di nakasegregate
- Kasi po every quarter of the month po, meron pong sinusubmit si Sec na report sa EPWMD. Yung tinatawag pong ECA. Ito po ay para sa Environment Certificate po ng barangay. Alam po ni Sec yun. Bukod sa EPWMD, ang brgy po, under din po ng Barangay Community Relation ay

kasa kasama po. Sa reporting po kasi pag may problema, doon po namin sa BCRD kinocoordinate. Ang BCRD naman irerelay ito sa EPWMD. Pag bumaba po yung DENR, Tinitignan po nila yung creek.

- Dati po pumupunta ang DENR every quarter din po. Nagrereport din po kami sa kanila.
- Hindi po, noong normal pa po noon. Wala po nitong pandemic.
- Sa creek lang po inoobserbahan nila kung mayroong factory or establishments na nagtatapon ng dumi sa tubig diyan.
- Ang huli pong seminar na inattendan namin sa DENR main office ay tungkol sa kung paano maglagay ng trap doon sa ilog para mahold yung mga basura. Ang kaso naman po, wala po kaming lugar na pwedeng paglagayan ng trap na iyon kasi po malalim po yung mga lugar namin saka po yung lugar na pagsasabitan namin sa kabila di na sakop na barangay iyon. Bale ang sakop lang po ng barangay, ito lang pong side na ito. Wala pa pong isang kilometro ang sakop ng brgy Alicia sa creek. Kasi po kabila po roon yung brgy Santo Cristo. Mga ilang meters lang po iyan. Wala pang 800m, Ramon Magsaysay na iyon. Di ba sa 81 Cotabato po kayo, side kayo ng creek siguro wala pa pong 200m ay ibang barangay na iyon. Di na po naming sakop iyon. Brgy Magsaysay na po iyon.
- Hindi naman po sila umattend nung nagpatawag ang DENR. Noong nag launching po ng trap na iyon, sa Novaliches proper ipinakita. Kami naman po naghanda naman po kami. Ang sabi naman po ng DENR, magpoprovide sila ng mga net kaso hindi naman po sila nagbigay. Mayroon pong involved na NGOs doon eh. Ang NGO po yung sa rotary ng Cubao EDSA. Dalawa po iyan tsaka yung sa Novaliches po.
- Sila po magpoprovide ng net at floaters. Yun palang ilalagay doon sa net, mayroon naman pong iniipon na PET bottles. Yun po ang ilalagay kasi umaangat. Tapos yung net po naman na ilulubog doon ay may habang 1.5M kasi dito po sa amin, walang shallow water dito.
- Pag kukunin naman po doon ay irerequest pa sa EPWMD kung kailan kukunin at kung kailan papanhik. Ang problema po sa amin, ang sabi nila yung lugar dito ay wala nang madaanan kasi nga po may mga bahay na nakapaligid. Noong nagbigay sila ng relocation area sa Pandi, di nila tinanggal yan. Bale andiyan pa po yun. Saka po yung mga nabigyan doon, wala pa pong isang taon, lumipat po ulit sa dati nilang bahay. Bumalik pa rin po dito. Ganoon po nangyari kaya kung sasabihin na po na dapat alisin ang mga eskwater ay di po namin magawa kasi wala po kaming police power. Dapat ang maghandle po nyan ay yung in-charge sa urban poor. Dapat noong binigyan ng relocation site iyan, dapat tinanggal na yung kanilang dating pwesto.
- Mayroon nga pong Mandamus sa Manila Bay yung ano po ruling ng Supreme court, mahigpit nga po kaso noong nagpandemic, di na po nasunod yung mga activities na dapat gawin. Malaki ang naging impact ng pandemic kasi di makakilos ng maayos ang mga tao.
- Yun nga po yung mga meetings at kinakailangan ng maraming tao.
- Itong pandemic, kapag nangongolekta ng basura, yung grupo ng contractor dapat ay may suot silang gloves at bota. Ang EPWMD po ang nagrerequire nyan. Ngayon nga pong pandemic dapat naka face mask sila tsaka nakagloves. Required po talaga iyon. Tsaka dapat pag aalis sa dispatching area, kumpleto po yung dala. May gas pump sila at may walis. Kaso ang

nangyayari po pag umaalis po yung truck, naiiwan po yung ibang basura. Di naman po lahat nahahakot at nakakalat. Kaya mayroon po kaming street sweeper. Kami na lang po nag-aasikaso.

- Yung pagkaroon lang po ng collection segregation naachieve naman po yun. Kapag di naman po namin kinuha, doon po sa parte ng Tacloban St, talagang itatapon nila sa creek. Kaya nga po yung lugar na iyon, di nila mapasok dahil marami pong nakaparadang tricycle at iba pang sasakyan at tsaka yung maliliit na establishments tulad ng karinderya, ayaw pumayag na sa kanila pumarada yung truck.
- Kaya ginagawa po namin, di po namin pinapapasok yung truck doon. Doon lang po sa main road tsaka Cotabato St. na lang. Doon pinaparada yung truck sa kanto at hahakutin lang nila. Pag alis po ng truck, ako na po ang naglilinis ng iba. Binabaldehan ko na lang po.
- kasi po noong wala pang pandemic, may mga containers po galing sa EPWMD. Mayroon din pong flyers na binibigay sa mga bahay bahay.
- Pag nagrequest naman po tayo sa EPWMD, magpoprovide naman sila ng mga tao. Nagdedeploy sila.
- Wala po tayo dito. Ang campaigner po namin yun na rin pong street sweeper namin. Sila na rin po nagsasabi sa bahay bahay na start na po yung daily collection.
- Anim po yung street sweepers natin.
- Oo, may naka assign na silang kalye.
- Bale ang nangyayari po diyan maam sa biodegradable po, nasasama na po ang food waste pati yung kitchen waste. Kasi wala naman po kaming storage facilities. Wala po kami niyan.
- Every second quarter po, mayroon pong best practices na nilalabas po ang barangay. Nasusunod naman ang mga iyon.
- May dokumento naman po kami noon. Marami nga kasing di nasunod nitong pandemic. Dati kasi pag bumaba naman po yung taga city hall, mayroon po kaming clean up drive every 15th po ng month or second week of the month. Buwan buwan po yun at may naka assign pong kagawad doon kung sino mag-iisponsor. Siya po magpapakain, ganoon.
- Nagmomobilize po kami mga tanod, kasama yung dalawang sasakyan, tsaka yung checker. May dokumento naman po iyon. Kaya nga lang po ngayong pandemic, di nagawa.
- Kasi po pitong kagawad ang nakaassign kung sino ang mag-iisponsor.
- Wala kaming MRS, wala kaming storage. Bale system na lang po ginagawa namin kagaya yung mayroon po kami dyang cage for recyclables. Doon lang po nilalagay tapos pag naibenta po yun, kikilohin at irereport kay Secretary ang naipon na basura.
- Tsaka mayroon pa kaming isang nangongolekta ng mga recyclables. Pag nakapagbenta po siya, irereport na lang po dito kung gaano karami.
- Doon din po lahat ang bagsak nun. Saka bukod pa po sa biodegradable and non-biodegradable, yun pong bulky wastes tulad ng mga debris at yung mga bato. Yung pinagtriman ng puno. Nirerequest po namin iyan sa EPWMD para hakutin.
- Basta pag sinabi mo na bulky waste, iba pa po ang papadalhin nilang truck.
- Yung malimit pong nagdadala pag bulky waste ay yung forward, 6 -wheeler.
- Yun po kasing contractor ngayon, ang pinoprovide po sa barangay ay open truck na forward saka yung mini dumptruck. Last time na nagdaang

contractor, yung LEG. Nagpoprovide sila ng nagcocompact ng basura. Hindi na po ginagawa ng bagong contractor dito. Tsaka hindi po pwede ilagay doon yung nabubulok tulad ng mga kahoy.

- yung iba po ay nangangalakal kaya kumikita sila sa basura.
- Hindi naman po sila pinagbabawalang mangalakal dito
- Kaso ngayon ngang pandemic, hindi po pwede yung ganoon kasi mas mahigpit.
- Sabi nga gaya ng face mask tinatapon lang din kaya posibleng kumalat ang covid.
- Maayos naman po kasi noong kami po ay may clean up drive pa, di na po kami nagrerequest ng truck ng bulky waste. Kami na po mismo ang naghahakot.
- Doon sa cleanup drive namin mayroon pong before and after. Isa po sigurong problema, yung ibang lugar nagtatapon sa amin ng basura. Ginagawan na lang po namin siya ng report tapos after noon, nakikita naman po kung nalinis namin o hindi. Yun lang po ang best practice namin
- Sa ngayon po limitado talaga ang activities pagdating sa solid waste
- Dapat po yung project ng DENR ay matuloy. Sana po ay maimplement na po namin pagtapos nitong pandemic.
- Wala po. Basta nirerequest lang po namin sa mga stakeholder tulad ng mga apartment, town houses, na yung waste bin nila, may marking po ng biodegradable at non-biodegradable. Di rin po sila maglalabas ng waste bin na biodegradable pag araw po ng non-biodegradable ang hinahakot. Kasi yung mga townhouses po diyan, di naman nila maregulate yung pagtatapon ng basura ng tenants nila. Tapon lang po nang tapon. Dapat po sila ang magsasabi sa mga tenants. Para paglabas po ng araw na nabubulok, yun lang po yung ilalabas nilang bin. Di po pwedeng ilabas po yung di nabubulok. Nangyayari kasi diyan kaya kinukwestyon namin yung mga townhouse sa dami pong hindi sumusunod.
- Warning lang po. Di po namin binibigyan ng Notice of Violation. Kasi po pag binigyan namin ng Notice of Violation, pupuntahan po sila ng EPWMD. Winawaringan lang po namin. Saka hindi na po namin kinukuha alam po nila iyon eh. Pagka natiyempuhan po ng BPSO namin na di nabubulok at ang hakot po ay nabubulok, iniwan po talaga iyon. Ibinabalik sa compound nila kahit po nailabas na. Di kokolektahin po yon.
- Pag regular po na di nabubulok ang kukunin, kukunin po yun. Nangyayari po kasi may mga drum sila pero sari-saring basura ang nakalagay.
- yung monitoring po ng EPWMD, mahigpit din po
- Madalas silang maglabas ng kahoy at mga bato.
- Doon sa committee po ng environment. Yun din pong anim na street sweepers, in charge din po sila sa paglilinis. Nagsisimula po silang magwalis ng mga 6 oclock ng umaga. Yung iba naman, eight oclock.
- Araw araw po iyon. Mayroon naman pong attendance yan.
- Sasabihin nila di niyo kukunin ito? Itatapon namin sa ilog. Eh pag kami naman po natiyempuhan ng DENR na marumi yung ilog, kami din po ang mapapagalitan. Kapag nagmomonitor, kung konti lang naman po yung diperensya sa dami ng basura, kinukuha na po namin.
- Mahigpit po yung mandamus ng Manila Bay, di ba? Ang creek naman na aming nasasakupan ay di masyadong mahaba. Kami din po ay sumusunod

eh iyon naman pong brgy sa kabila ay di sumusunod. Wala naman pong pagkakataon na bumaba yung DENR at binigyan kami ng notice na ganoon.

- Yung lugar namin ay di naman mahaba
- May documentation naman kami. May picture naman po iyon
- Yung sa ano wala naman kaming best practices masyado. Nacomply naman namin lahat ang sinasabi para sa solid waste management, kaya lang po yun nga pandemic at di makakilos.

ANNEX VI: CERTIFICATE OF APPEARANCE

<p>RODRIGO A. CORRO Punong Barangay</p>	<p>BARANGAY CERTIFICATION</p>	
<p>KAGAWAD</p>	<p>This is to certify that Cherry Winsom F. Holgado, a resident of this barangay with postal address at No. 81-D Cotabato Street, Brgy. Alicia, Bago Bantay, Quezon City, had appeared before this office in connection with her Special Problem under MENRM-Upland at UP Open University last April 23, 2021.</p>	
<p>LEONARDO C. FLORES III Committee Chairman, Appropriation, Ways and Means</p>	<p>Issued this 23rd day of April 2021.</p>	
<p>ELIZABETH O. BAUTISTA Committee Chairwoman on Family, Women's Desk GAD & BCPC</p>	<p>For and in Authority of the Hon. RODRIGO A. CORRO Punong Barangay By: Felipa L. Estraña Barangay Secretary Brgy. Alicia, Dist. I, Q.C. Tel # 3504756; 4261054</p>	
<p>VENTURA P. PATAUEG Committee Chairwoman Transportation & Communication</p>	<p><i>Valid with official dry seal</i></p>	
<p>ALEXANDER P. BERJA Committee Chairman on Livelihood and Education, Accounting</p>		
<p>ENRIQUE C. ENRIQUEZ Committee Chairman on Environmental Sanitation Health & Beautification</p>		
<p>DANILO A. CLEOFAS Committee Chairman on Peace & Order, Anti-Drug Abuse</p>		
<p>REYNALDO C. SARE Committee Chairman on Infrastructure</p>		
<p>NIKKO ANGELO D. BALAGAS SK Chairman</p>		
<p>FELIPA L. ESTRANA Barangay Secretary</p>		
<p>LIZA T. MELGAREJO Barangay Treasurer</p>		

ANNEX VII: GUIDELINES ON BULKY WASTE COLLECTION

Republic of the Philippines
Quezon City

**TASK FORCE ON SOLID WASTE COLLECTION,
CLEANING AND DISPOSAL SERVICES MANAGEMENT**
Trunkline No. 988-4242 loc. 8362

FOR : RICHARD S. SANTUILE
Action Officer, Task Force Solid Waste Collection
Cleaning and Disposal Services Management

FROM : Romano C. Rios
Acting Chief, Garbage Collection Section and Special Cleaning Section

SUBJECT : Bulky Waste Collection

DATE : 20 January 2020

Submitting herewith is the proposed guidelines for the Bulky Waste Collection:

- Hakot ng Malalaking Basura sa Barangay will now be referred to as **Bulky Waste Collection**.
- Collection of this type of waste will be conducted every Sunday.
- Request letters from the barangays must have an attached accomplished Bulky Waste Collection Request Form (please see attachment) as reference on the type and volume of waste and areas to be covered.
- Requests received by the Task Force on Solid Waste Collection, Cleaning and Disposal Services Management by Wednesday on or before 5:00PM will be accommodated on Sunday of the same week.
- Requests received after the cut-off period will be accommodated the following Sunday.
- These are the types of bulky waste that will be collected:
 - Logs, branches of trees and other bulky garden wastes will be collected provided that these are secured in bundles of convenient weight and size not exceeding one (1) meter in length by the household or by the barangay.
 - Dilapidated furniture and discarded tires shall be stored properly prior its scheduled collection.
- Collection requiring the use of payloader (ex: clearing of earth mounds) will be scheduled.
- Construction debris is the responsibility of the building contractor being constructed, renovated or demolished. This will not be collected by the city contractors.

The undersigned respectfully recommends disseminating the abovementioned guidelines to the Punong Barangays. A similar letter will also have to be sent to the contractors for their compliance.

For your information and approval, please

Attachment: As stated.

/patty/2020/communicationsbulkywaste/

6th Floor, Building Regulatory Offices (Civic Center D), Quezon City Hall Compound, Diliman, Quezon City

ANNEX VIII: SUBMISSION OF BARANGAY ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE AUDIT (ECA) REPORT

Republic of the Philippines
DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT
 National Capital Region
Quezon City Field Office
 • ISO 9001:2015 Certified •

MEMORANDUM

TO : ALL PUNONG BARANGAYS

SUBJECT : REITERATION ON THE SUBMISSION OF THE QUARTERLY BARANGAY ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE AUDIT

DATE : FEBRUARY 3, 2021

This is to reiterate report requirements pursuant to the Supreme Court Continuing Mandamus and in fulfillment of the objectives of the Manila Bay Clean-up Rehabilitation and Preservation Program (MBCRPP).

In line with the abovementioned, the Barangays' compliance to the applicable provisions of Republic Act 9003 or the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 are being monitored quarterly through the accomplishment of the Environmental Compliance Audit (ECA).

Hence, all 142 Barangays are reminded to submit the following on the given timelines:

REPORT	DEADLINE	WHERE TO SUBMIT
Barangay ECA MHF 2.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1st Qtr (Covering December 2020 to February, 2021) Not later than March 15, 2021 2nd Qtr (Covering March 2021 to May, 2021) Not later than June 15, 2021 3rd Qtr (Covering June 2021 to August, 2021) Not later than September 15, 2021 4th Qtr (Covering September 2021 to November, 2021) Not later than December 7, 2021 	To be submitted by Barangays to the Task Force Solid Waste Management

For inquiries, your staff may contact your respective DILG Quezon City District Officer at 8514-3736 or the Quezon City Task Force on Solid Waste Management at 8988-4242 loc. 8350.

For strict compliance.

EMMANUEL D. BORRAMEO, CESO V
 City Director

CC: **RICARDO B. CORPUZ**
 Barangay and Community Relations Department

RICHARD S. SANTUJILE
 Task Force on Solid Waste Collection, Cleaning and Disposal Services Management

"Matino, Mahusay, at Maaasahan"

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 quezoncity.dilg@gmail.com
 www.facebook.com/dilgkyusi

ANNEX IX: MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT WITH RTD JUNKSHOP

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
BARANGAY ALICIA
BAGO BANTAY, QUEZON CITY
DISTRICT I, AREA I
Tel. No.: 350-4756 / 426-1054

MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT

KNOW ALL MEN BY THESE PRESENTS:

This Memorandum of Agreement was made and entered into by and between:

BARANGAY ALICIA, with office and mailing address at #2 Batangas Street, Barangay Alicia, Bago Bantay, Quezon City, represented herein by its Punong Barangay, **RODRIGO A. CORRO**;

- and -

RTD JUNK SHOP, a legal business entity created under the Philippine Law with office and mailing address at #141 Ilocos Sur Street, Barangay Alicia, Bago Bantay, Quezon City, herein represented by its proprietor **MR. RODRIGO DJ. TORRES**;

WITNESSETH:

WHEREAS, the **BARANGAY ALICIA** recognizes the need to fully comply with the requirements of R.A. 9003, otherwise known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management of 2000;

WHEREAS, the **BARANGAY ALICIA** agrees to undertake an agreement with the Junkshop owner operating within its territorial jurisdiction and to name the latter as its accredited **JUNKSHOP-CUM-MRF**;

WHEREAS, to fully implement City Ordinance No. SP-1711, Series of 2006, only junkshops with necessary permits from the City will be accredited as **JUNKSHOP-CUM-MRF**;

NOW THEREFORE, for and in consideration of the foregoing premises and by way of formalizing and confirming their commitment, the parties hereby agree to utilize **RTD JUNK SHOP** as a **JUNKSHOP-CUM-MRF** in the barangay.

I. OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES

A. General Obligations:

1. The parties shall collaborate and combine their human, technical, and material resources to prepare, validate, approve, legitimize and implement the policies on waste segregation and recycling program;
2. The parties hereby agree to meet monthly to appraise each other of the progress of the implementation and/or operation of the **JUNKSHOP-CUM-MRF**.

B. Obligation of the Barangay:

1. To provide the necessary technical support and services and personnel to monitor the operation of the **JUNKSHOP-CUM-MRF**;
2. To accredit eco-aides by way of issuing identification (ID) cards, authorizing them to collect recyclable materials from households;
3. To report in writing the volume of recyclable materials collected to the Quezon City Government thru the EPWMD on a monthly basis;
4. To accredit junkshops that have the necessary local permits and are environmentally compliant.

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 BARANGAY ALICIA
 BAGO BANTAY, QUEZON CITY
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C. Obligation of the Junkshop:

1. To adhere to the criteria of a model junkshop as stated in Ordinance No. SP-1171, Series of 2006;
2. To assign junkshop personnel to collect all the recyclable materials from households;
3. To buy only the barangay's recyclable materials and maintain a record of the monthly sales based on the collected recyclables and provide written reports to the barangay.

II. EFFECTIVITY

This agreement shall take effect upon signing hereof and shall remain in full force and effect unless sooner terminated as provided above or by written agreement of all parties.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the parties have hereunto affixed their signatures this 28 day of March, 2019 at QC.

RTD JUNK SHOP

RODRIGO D.J. TORRES
 Proprietor

BARANGAY ALICIA

RODRIGO A. CORRO
 Punong Barangay

-Witnesses-

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES)
 Quezon City)

At the bove stated place, on the ___ day of _____ 2019 before me personally appeared:

 RODRIGO D.J. TORRES

RODRIGO A. CORRO

Known to me and known to be the same persons who executed the foregoing instrument and their acknowledgement is written and has been signed on each and every page by the parties and their instrumental witnesses on the space provided for.

WITNESS MY HAND AND SEAL on the date and place above-written.

Doc. No. _____
 Page No. _____
 Book No. _____
 Series of 2018

ANNEX X: INFORMATION, EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION (IEC) MATERIALS

HON. LEONARDO C. FLORES, III
Barangay Chairman
Barangay Alicia
#2 Batangas Street
Area 1, District 1
Quezon City

Dear Hon. Flores, III:

In line with the implementation of "Hiwa-hiwalay na Basura sa Barangay" program of Quezon City Government, L.E.G. Hauling Services Corporation (LHSC) distributed/disseminated two hundred (200) flyers regarding waste segregation so as to achieve our aim of informing your constituents on the segregation at sources campaign.

Thank you and we hope for your continuous support.

Sincerely yours,

ALMA I. LAMBATAN
SWM Enforcers cum Campaigner

cc:

MR. LUIS C. ICASIANO
Operations Manager

MS. ESCARLITA M. MONTELLANO
Head, Technical and Planning

MS. ZEIDE L. VALENCIA
Project Development Officer

MGA BAPAT SANDAN AT KALANGAN GAWIS
(Binabaw ng Biodegradable (Nabubulok) o Non-biodegradable (Di-Nabubulok))

BIODEGRADABLE (NABUBULOK)

- Binabaw ang tanang naglalatay at fables o bawag ng pabalat at gabay sa mga bagay na mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran sa ilalim ng pagpapalaganap ng kalikasan ng bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga ito ay maaaring gumamit ng mga bagay na mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.

NON-BIODEGRADABLE (DI-NABUBULOK)

- Binabaw ang tanang naglalatay at fables o bawag ng pabalat at gabay sa mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga ito ay maaaring gumamit ng mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.

Halos lahat ng bagay dumating sa mga paksa sa kolektor ay dapat magamit ang paglalathala o pagmamulat sa mga lugar.

BULKY WASTE

- Makapag-ugnayan sa Barangay upang magpatakil sa mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.
- Ang mga pangangailangan sa mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.
- Hindi obligasyon ng gobyerno na buksan ang mga construction debris. Obligasyon ng may-ari ng bahay at ng kontraktor ang pagtapon ito.

Paalala po! Iwasan maglabas ng basura paglindog-awag ng kolektor.

MONDAY and FRIDAY for Biodegradable (Nabubulok)
WEDNESDAY for Non-Biodegradable (Di-Nabubulok)
PROBLEMA SA BASURAY
TUMAWAG SA 985-4242 LOCAL 8350

BIODEGRADABLE (NABUBULOK)
NON-BIODEGRADABLE (DI-NABUBULOK)
RESIDUAL
GLASS/METAL/PLASTIC
PAPER

KLASE NG BASURA	MGA HALINHAWA	ARAW NG KOLEKTOR	MGA BAPAT SANDAN AT KALANGAN GAWIS
BIODEGRADABLE (NABUBULOK)	COMPOSTABLE	LUNES AT BIERNES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Binabaw ang mga ito sa bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.
	KEPCHEN WASTE		
NON-BIODEGRADABLE (DI-NABUBULOK)	RECYCLABLE	MIYERKULIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Binabaw ang mga ito sa bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.
	RESIDUAL		
SPECIAL WASTE	BULKY WASTE	TUMUNG BULING LINGGONG BAWAT-BEWAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Makapag-ugnayan sa Barangay upang magpatakil sa mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran. Ang mga pangangailangan sa mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran. Hindi obligasyon ng gobyerno na buksan ang mga construction debris. Obligasyon ng may-ari ng bahay at ng kontraktor ang pagtapon ito.
	ELECTRONIC WASTE	Tawag sa mga Magsasaka ng Mabatid ng Basura	

Ano ang nilalaman ng RA 9003?

- Binabaw ang tanang naglalatay at fables o bawag ng pabalat at gabay sa mga bagay na mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.
- Ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.

Ano ang mga ahensyang kasama sa pagpapalaganap ng batas?

- National Solid Waste Management Commission (NSWMC)
- Department of Environment and Natural Resources
- Department of Education
- Commission on Higher Education
- Office of the Press Secretary
- Department of Health
- Department of Labor
- Department of Justice
- Department of Social Welfare and Development
- Department of Trade and Industry
- Department of Transportation
- Department of Tourism
- Department of Agriculture
- Department of Science and Technology
- Department of Energy
- Department of Health
- Department of Labor
- Department of Justice
- Department of Social Welfare and Development
- Department of Trade and Industry
- Department of Transportation
- Department of Tourism
- Department of Agriculture
- Department of Science and Technology
- Department of Energy

Ano ang Materials Recovery Facility (MRF)?

- Ang MRF ay ang pagpapalaganap ng mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.
- Ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran ay dapat magamit ang mga bagay na hindi mabubulok sa bukasang kapaligiran.

Pangkalahatang Balangkas ng RA 9003

Hanny ng mga Munisipyo o Lungsod

Hanny ng mga Barangay

mga pobrikajerkahans

MRF (Materials Recovery Facility)

Ano ang Solid Waste Management (SWM) Plan?

Ang SWM Plan ay naglalaman ng mga programa na nakaayos sa mga kategorya ng batas.

Ano ang nilalaman ng SWM Plan?

- Layunin ng SWM Plan ay:
 - Impormasyon sa dami ng kolektibong basura
 - Uri o komposisyon ng basura
 - Pangangailangan o kailangan (opsional, collection, production area, storage, atbp)
 - Detalye sa kolektibong programa ng isang lugar/komunidad o maagang pagtatag
 - Layunin ng pagpapapatupad ng programa sa pamamahala sa basura
 - Panahon ng pagpapatupad ng programa

Ano ang kinakailangan sa pagpapapatupad ng Segregation at Resource Recovery?

- Magkakahwalay na lalagyan para sa bawat uri ng basura (compostables, recyclables, special wastes at residuals)
- Panatilihin ang naka-schedule na pagkolekta ng mga basura o materyales
- Pagkakaroon ng bakod na pagsasalamin ng mga materyales
- Paglalagay ng Materials Recovery Facility (MRF)
- Alamatin ang pagtataluhan o pagdadalhan ng mga baka-gamit o recyclables at ng special waste kung mamon man

Ipinalatutapad na Programa sa Recycling

- Puri ng mga produkting maaaring magamit muld o isa-urba
- Pagtatag sa proseso at mga materyales na ginagamit sa paggawa ng produkto
- Eco-Labeling
- Pagpapatupad sa paggamit naging bag-ong-likha ng mga produkting mabagal na-recycle
- Pagprotekta ng mga materyal na gumagamit

Pagpapapatupad ng Batas sa mga Lokal na Pamahalaan

Ang mga lokal na pamahalaan ay dapat magpatupad ng batas sa recycling sa kanilang mga teritoryo.

Strategic SWM Committee

**Office of the Secretary
NATIONAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT COMMISSION
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT BUREAU
DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES**

7th Fl. HRD Bldg., DEPT. COMPLEX, Valley Avenue,
Diliman, Quezon City, 1118
Tel. No. (632) 886-2724/886-2778/886-4796/1054-1071 No. 3
<http://www.demr.gov.ph/nswmc>
nswmc2004@yahoo.com

REPUBLIC ACT 9003 WASTE Ano ang RA 9003?

Ang RA 9003 ay naglalaman ng mga alituntunin sa wastong pamamahala ng basura, pagpapalagan ng kagamitan sa wastong programa ng koleksiyon at pagpapapatupad ng mga programang nakatuon sa pakikita ng bawat mamamayan upang mabawasan ang basurang agad lamang tinatapon. Layunin din nito na magpalagan ang benepisyo ng pagkakaroon ng pasilidad sa bawat lugar na maging pag-imbakan ng baka-materyales o lugar para sa proseso ang mga ito.

HIWA-HIWALAY NA BASURA SA BARANGAY PROGRAM

HIWA-HIWALAY NA BASURA SA PINAGMULAN

Ayon sa Republic Act 9003 o mas kilala bilang The Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, ang basura ay dapat pinaghiwalay kung saan-ito nilalika. Dahil dito, ang lahat ng residente ng Lungsod Quezon ay inataskang maghiwa-hiwalay ng kanilang basura magmula sa kanilang bahay, establisyamentong pangkomersyal, institusyon o pakrila. Nakasaad din sa RA 9003 na dapat maglaan ng hiwa-hiwalay na lalagyan para sa mga nabubulok at di-nabubulok na basura.

HIWA-HIWALAY NA KOLEKSYON

Magkakahwalay na kolektahin ang nabubulok at di-nabubulok na basura. Magtatagala ng dalawang (2) araw na koleksiyon para sa nabubulok at isang (1) araw naman para sa mga di-nabubulok. Maglaan din ng dump truck para sa bawat klase ng basura. Lalagyan ito ng markings o signaga kung saan nakasaad ang klase ng basura na kolektahin nito.

HIWA-HIWALAY NA TAPUNAN

Ang mga basurang nakolekta ay mangpat at maayos na dadalhin sa Quezon City Sanitary Landfill (QCSL). Ang mga di-nabubulok na basura ay dadalhin sa pamamantalang Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) upang dumaan ito sa final sorting. Ang matitirang residual waste lang ang itatapon sa QCSL.

BABALAI

Ang babalai ay isang uri ng programang ito ay magiging perawan ng mamang. Phd. 2009-100
Lungsod Quezon, 900-000 o nagsalamin ito sa
Alicia (ang araw 115 deya) hanggang 2010

HIWA-HIWALAY NA BASURA SA BARANGAY

Para sa mga katanungan, maaaring itawag ang mga sumusunod na numero:

LEG HAULING SERVICES CORP.
Tel. no. 404-4407 / 452-6450
EPWMD: 988-4242 local 8350
BARANGAY: _____

Sa paghihiwalay ng basura, kailangan nating magsama-sama.

RASURA

Ita ay mga bagay na itinatapon sa maaaring magamit sa trabaho, pakrila at establisyamentong pangkomersyal.

PAMAMAHALA NG BASURA

Ita ang solusiyong pagkolekta, pagproseso, pagtatagayut at paglalagay ng basura sa tamang lugar. Ita ay ninaanganyang mababasa ang pangalan na dalaw ng basura sa kailangan at kapaligiran.

IBA'T-IBANG KLASANG BASURA

Nabubulok: 48%
Di-nabubulok: 52%

Plastik	16%
Papel	17%
Metal	3%
Bato	3%
Residual	11%

MGA PINAGMUMULAN NG BASURA

- Bahay
 - Optima
 - Kainan (Hal: fastfood at restaurant)
- Institusyong
 - Pasalyal
 - Sinbahan
 - Dospital
 - Tanggapan ng Gobyerno
 - Luwisan
- Pakrila

ALAM NYO BA:

Na ang tung 100 ay nagtatapon ng 0.66 kgs. ng basura bawat araw?
Ang Lungsod Quezon ay may 2,950,134 milyon na populasyon. Ita ay nagtatapon ng mabigat kumulang 1,947,088.44kgs. o 9,271.85cu.m ng basura araw-araw. Samakatuwid, 579 na tonelang ng basura ang kinakailangan upang

ANNEX XI: CONSOLIDATED PHOTOS TAKEN DURING FIELDWORK

1. Garbage collection

2. During interview with small enterprise group

3. During interview with the households

4. Informal settlers' area near the river

